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Jean Monnet Network

*The European Union, Africa and China in the
Global Age*

Bradford (UK), Bujumbura (Burundi), Corinth (Greece), Dar es Salaam
(Tanzania), Gulu (Uganda), Kigali (Rwanda), Lancaster/Shandong
(UK/China), Nairobi (Kenya)

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Special Issue 2020 – Part 1

***Africa, the European Union and China Towards a New Global
Order –
From Pandemic to Renewed Integration and Global
Cooperation?***

**Part 1:
Regional Integration
Economics**

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Introduction

These three special issues of *European Studies / Studii Europene* have brought together scholars from diverse horizons, covering a variety of disciplines, to examine cooperations between Africa, the European Union (EU) and China, in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, and to question how the pandemic is affecting our lives and may redefine the global order. Whilst the pandemic constitutes one of the core threads linking these contributions, the special issues also draw on the activities carried out since 2017 by the EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network in East Africa, as well as on the core research themes of the network: regional integration, and international cooperation, particularly between the European Union, Africa, and China. They explore issues related to Africa, the EU, China, globalisation, and perspectives of international cooperation in a post-COVID-19 world.

This network, entitled '*The European Union, Africa and China in the Global Age*' (EU-EAC) is a sustainability project funded by the EU Commission's *Jean Monnet* Programme, and is directed by its lead partner at the University of Bradford (UK). Five of the network's partner institutions are based in member states of the East African Community (EAC): The United States International University – Africa (USIU-A) in Nairobi (Kenya), Gulu University in Gulu (Uganda), the Protestant Institute of Arts and Social Sciences (PIASS) in Huye (Rwanda), the University of Burundi, and the Uongozi Institute for Leadership and Sustainable Development in Dar Es Salaam (Tanzania). Other partner institutions include the University of the Peloponnese in Corinth (Greece), and Lancaster University (UK). Since the start of its activities in 2017 in Nairobi, numerous new partners have joined forces with the network, many of whom have actively contributed to these special issues.

The EU-EAC research project has been the first *Jean Monnet* Network of its kind with a focus on regional integration studies in Africa. In 2016, the year it was launched, there was almost a total gap of EU Commission *Jean Monnet* programme activities on the map of Africa. The continent had

remained off the beaten track. However, since then, several research projects have gradually started to appear in an area that had been so far virtually uncharted territory for *Jean Monnet* actions, but their impact currently remains limited to a few academic initiatives. Among the more noticeable ones, a second *Jean Monnet* Network, *Africa, the Mediterranean and Europe in the Era of Global Integration* (AMENET), was launched in 2018, with a focus this time on West Africa, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), and the Mediterranean. This project, whose principal investigators are contributing to this special issue, is based at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, and comprises 14 participating academic institutions across Western Africa and Europe. Both the EU-EAC and the AMENET Networks complement each other with their approach of regional integration respectively in Eastern and Western Africa. Both networks are actively working together on African integration issues.

The EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network is aimed at, first, fostering cooperation and understanding between the EU and the EAC; second, promoting academic research and training on regional integration; and third, encouraging closer trilateral cooperation between Europe, Africa and China. In the EU-EAC acronym, 'EAC' refers to two core agendas of the project: first, to the East African Community as a model of regional economic integration in Africa; and second, to the broader context of 'Europe, Africa and China' (E.A.C.). Issues of integration and cooperation have been at the core of the network's reflection. It aims to contribute to knowledge on the benefits and intricacies of regional and continental integration in a comparative perspective. This event-intensive network has organised numerous research and training activities across three continents and most EAC partner states. The purpose has been to foster dialogue between academics, government officials, policy makers, diplomats, EU delegations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), think tanks, interregional and international institutions, and Chinese missions in East African capitals. International conferences and consultative workshops on regional

integration in the EAC were organised in Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda, at the EAC Secretariat in Arusha, Tanzania, and also in Addis Ababa, political capital of Africa, with the participation of the African Union Commission (AUC). The project promotes regional integration 'on the ground' and has run *Training & Dialogue Sessions on Regional Integration* at the EAC Secretariat, and for Ministries of East African Affairs in EAC member states. Furthermore, the project also aims to contribute to building sustainable societies in Africa in trilateral coordination with the European Union and China. It advocates a triologue, with Africa as the centrepiece of these blocks, to boost African development in a coordinated fashion. Tripartite conferences and policy debates were organised in 2019 in Shanghai, in cooperation with the Shanghai Institutes for International Studies (SIIS); in Beijing in cooperation with the Delegation of the European Union to China; and at the Brussels Egmont Palace in cooperation with Egmont Royal Institute. Participants were able to share African, European and Chinese perspectives on potential gains from coordinating efforts towards making African development sustainable.

The emergence of the severe global health crisis induced in 2020 by the COVID-19 infection is redefining virtually every aspect of human relations and activity, which has led to this special issue initiative. Indeed, in the face of such unprecedented global challenge, multiple questions beg an answer. How does the sanitary crisis affect the African continent? How are democracy, the law, social and fundamental rights affected by the pandemic? What are the consequences of the health crisis? What issues does the health emergency raise in terms of migrations? How are the economies in Africa, Europe and China affected by the sanitary crisis? What are the consequences of the pandemic on African, European, Chinese, and global trade? What are the potential consequences of COVID-19 on security issues in Africa? Does the global health crisis enhance international cooperation and solidarity? Or does it reinforce trends towards national sovereignty and borders? How does the pandemic influence Africa's

relationship with the EU and with major European countries? How does the pandemic affect African countries' relations with China, the Belt & Road Initiative, or debt management issues? What are the prospects for furthering regional and continental integration in Africa after the Covid-19 health crisis? Which trends can be anticipated with regards to geopolitical and geo-economic changes in the Global North and in the Global South?

The three special issues of the *European Studies / Studii Europene* aim to address these crucial questions, and to provide African as well as European insights on issues which have become global societal, health and economic challenges. This first issue (Part 1) groups together contributions focusing on regional integration and economics aspects. The second issue (Part 2) focuses on international cooperation, migrations, as well as youth and education. The third and final issue (Part 3) of the trilogy assembles contributions on the theme of culture, questioning, on the one hand, whether Africa can offer a homegrown approach to fight the pandemic; and, on the other hand, providing a country-related approach of how human rights are affected by the spread of the Coronavirus across Eastern Africa. The authors involved in the three issues aim to contribute actively to current debates and enhance research into the short, medium and long-term impacts of the global health emergency: on the African continent; on Africa's current and future relations with the European Union and China; and on the future position of Africa in globalisation.

The editors.

Economie Politique Internationale Post-COVID-19

Serge Magloire MBOUNGOU

msergemagloire@yahoo.fr

Résumé: *L'économie politique internationale, à travers son approche du nouveau régionalisme nous a permis de répondre à la problématique à savoir, comment explorer les questions relatives à l'Afrique et la globalisation, ainsi que les perspectives post-COVID-19 de coopération internationale entre l'Afrique, l'Union européenne et la Chine. Cette nouvelle donne des relations internationales interpelle autant la communauté scientifique, les responsables des organisations internationales que les décideurs politiques. Les pays africains doivent appliquer le nouveau régionalisme afin de booster leur compétitivité. Cette approche peut permettre aussi à l'Union européenne d'être très compétitive, de consolider sa position dans le monde face à la Chine et les Etats-Unis, car son avenir, c'est l'intégration économique plus juste et plus durable.*

Mots clés: *Mondialisation, Régionalisation, Intégration régionale, Globalisation, Espace, Nouveau régionalisme, Coopération, Coordination, Diversification.*

Introduction

La globalisation décrit l'unification des marchés mondiaux de capitaux, des biens, des services et la superposition de deux concurrences, l'une entre des Etats luttant pour la compétitivité de leurs économies et l'autre entre des entreprises combattant pour la rentabilité de leurs activités. Préféré des Anglais, ce terme a remplacé dans l'analyse de la concurrence mondiale ceux d'internationalisation ou de mondialisation.¹ Pour répondre à la problématique à savoir, explorer les questions relatives à l'Afrique et la globalisation, ainsi que les perspectives post COVID-19 de coopération internationale entre l'Afrique, l'Union européenne et la Chine, nous pensons revisiter l'économie politique internationale. Il nous sera utile de passer du

¹ Alain Nonjon, *Comprendre l'économie mondiale* (Paris: Ellipses, Edition Marketing, 1995), 230.

régionalisme à l'approche du nouveau régionalisme.² En effet, les travaux des certains auteurs, qui s'inscrivent plus généralement dans une perspective de l'économie politique internationale, proposent des cadres conceptuels prometteurs et rigoureux pour mener des études comparatives entre régionalisation. Il nous est utile de donner une définition de l'économie politique internationale qui est l'étude de l'interaction réciproque et dynamique dans les relations internationales entre l'accumulation de richesses et la poursuite de la puissance.

A la question de savoir comment ces espaces vont-ils créer des richesses tout en poursuivant leur puissance, nous répondrons d'abord aux questions secondaires à savoir, comment l'économie est-elle affectée en Afrique? Quelles pourront être les conséquences de la pandémie sur le commerce international, le commerce intra-Africain et les relations commerciales entre l'Afrique et les pays de l'UE, ainsi qu'entre l'Afrique et la Chine? Quelles sont les conséquences potentielles du COVID-19 sur les questions de sécurité en Afrique? Une analyse de processus d'intégration sera utile pour déterminer leur participation à la globalisation. Notre hypothèse portera sur l'analyse de causalité, voire de corrélation entre mondialisation-régionalisation. Ce travail porte sur trois sections, une revue de la littérature, une méthodologie et une analyse de processus d'intégration.

1 - Revue de la littérature

Une nouvelle vague de régionalisme doit s'inscrire dans cette perspective de l'économie politique internationale post COVID-19. Les réalités économiques et institutionnelles au sein des différents espaces, mettent ainsi en avant l'idée qu'il n'existe pas *«d'interprétation unique permettant de comprendre la pertinence et les profits d'intégration économique et*

² Sabine Saurugger, *Théories et concepts de l'intégration européenne* (Paris: Presses de Sciences Po, 2009).

*institutionnelles des différentes régions du monde.»*³ De nombreux travaux ont été réalisés sur le thème l'intégration régionale depuis une vingtaine d'années. La littérature que l'on peut qualifier de prolifique présente, analyse et intègre une nouvelle donne des relations économiques internationales. Le régionalisme est défini comme un processus institutionnel initié par les Etats en vue de favoriser la coopération et la coordination de leurs politiques dans certains domaines. Mais ici, il nous faut adopter une définition du régionalisme moins restrictive que celle proposée par l'Organisation Mondiale du Commerce (OMC). Selon cette dernière, «*le régionalisme est défini comme les mesures prises par les gouvernements pour libéraliser ou faciliter le commerce à l'échelle régionale, parfois au moyen de zones de libre-échange ou d'unions douanières.*» Cette définition ne prend en compte que l'aspect commercial.

Echinard, dans l'une de ses publications, a permis de restituer la quatrième vague de régionalisme dans l'histoire économique, de qualifier son contenu et de mettre en évidence un certain nombre de ses déterminants. Cette nouvelle dynamique, pour lui, même si elle affecte l'ensemble des régions du monde, n'est pas uniforme, comme les travaux théoriques récents l'indiquent.⁴ Il pense que différentes typologies essayent de proposer une classification des processus régionaux en cours. En effet, chaque processus développe des spécificités institutionnelle et économique propre. Le caractère protéiforme de cette nouvelle dynamique, d'après Echinard, doit faire l'objet de travaux plus poussés, se basant sur une analyse détaillée et comparative des principaux regroupements régionaux. Il apparaît également judicieux, propose-t-il, de chercher à définir l'espace régional pertinent à partir d'indicateurs de polarisation des échanges, des investissements et donc des stratégies de firmes et non plus seulement à partir d'une définition géographique résultant d'un traité intergouvernemental. L'intégration

³ BCE, «L'intégration économique dans différentes régions hors Union européenne,» *Bulletin Mensuel* (Octobre 2004): 81.

⁴ Yann Echinard, *L'intégration régionale: De quoi parlons-nous?* Présenté dans le Cours de Théorie de l'Intégration Economique Régionale, Grenoble, Octobre 2009.

régionale est une dynamique qui combine deux dimensions à savoir, économique et institutionnelle, affirme-t-il.⁵

Saurugger montre que contrairement aux études sur l'intégration régionale des années 1950 et 1960, le nouveau régionalisme ou mieux, les nouveaux régionalismes rejettent les hypothèses néofonctionnalistes.⁶ La conceptualisation néofonctionnaliste serait trop téléologique dans son analyse et ne permettrait pas d'identifier les variables clefs pour expliquer les formes diversifiées de l'intégration régionale, d'après lui. Par ailleurs, les approches néofonctionnalistes se concentreraient trop sur l'intégration institutionnalisée, ce qui empêcherait d'analyser les intégrations régionales de manière neutre, où plus précisément sans spéculer sur le moment où ils ressemblent à l'intégration européenne, affirme l'auteur. Les approches néofonctionnalistes s'appuieraient trop fortement sur les acteurs non étatiques et nationaux pour expliquer les pressions exercées sur les Etats membres pour davantage d'intégration et prêteraient trop peu attention au système économique mondialisé, aux acteurs étatiques non membres de l'Union européenne ou encore aux organisations internationales, déclare cet auteur.

Les approches «néorégionalistes» n'excluent aucunement l'importance des acteurs non étatiques, mais s'intéressent moins au rôle de l'intégration formelle, à savoir la pression exercée par ces acteurs sur l'Etat, qu'aux phénomènes informels auxquels ces acteurs participent dans des secteurs commerciaux ou d'immigration. Il estime que, pour la majorité des analystes qui s'inscrivent dans le nouveau régionalisme, la critique du néofonctionnalisme se fonde sur une double logique à savoir, d'une part, l'approche serait toujours identifiée comme la théorie principale de l'intégration européenne, particulièrement bien adaptée pour expliquer une intégration régionale spécifique. D'autre part, le tournant qui mène à la

⁵ Yann Echinard, «L'Union européenne: régionalisme ou mondialisation?» *Revue du Marché commun et de l'Union européenne* N° 406 (Mars 1997): 192-202.

⁶ Saurugger, *Théories et concepts*.

normalisation par le bas est considéré par les «néorégionalistes» comme réducteur, dans la mesure où ces conceptualisations tenteraient d'exclure la logique intergouvernementale de leurs analyses. Il montre que ces auteurs s'inscrivent donc davantage et à nouveau dans une logique de relations internationales et d'économie politique internationale.

Paul André nous dit que depuis le lancement des réformes économiques en 1978, l'économie de la Chine s'est profondément modifiée. Sa politique de réforme avait deux objectifs à savoir, la transition vers l'économie de marché et l'ouverture vers l'extérieur. Cette politique de développement a justifié une politique dit de «bon voisinage» de la part de Pékin.⁷ Aujourd'hui, l'interdépendance croissante de la Chine avec ses voisins et l'évolution du contexte géopolitique l'obligent à repenser sa politique de bon voisinage et à envisager la possibilité d'une intégration plus poussée avec les membres de l'ASEAN ainsi qu'avec ses voisins immédiats à savoir, la Taiwan et la Corée du Sud. Il estime que, si elle a connu des avancées importantes depuis la crise financière de 1997-1998, la construction régionale en Asie orientale demeure inachevée et pour le moins incertaine. L'auteur ajoute que, l'hétérogénéité des acteurs, de leur niveau de développement ainsi que de leurs régimes politiques tend à rendre difficile l'obtention d'un consensus sur un projet commun, ou pour le dire autrement, les dirigeants d'Asie orientale sont encore difficilement capables de créer une communauté de vues, d'objectifs et d'idées. Cette intégration régionale ne pourra aller plus en avant tant que le politique ne se sera pas saisi de la question.

Or, la rivalité entre la Chine et le Japon, affirme-t-il, peut apparaître comme une épée à double tranchant. Dans ce contexte, si l'on peut considérer qu'il n'existe pas de réelle intégration au niveau de l'ensemble de la région, en allant du Japon à l'Indonésie, on peut donc considérer que cette rivalité des

⁷ Paul André, *La Chine aujourd'hui: Dynamiques domestiques et internationales* (Villeneuve d'Asecq: Presse Universitaire du Septentrion, 2014).

deux puissances favorise et ralentit tout à la fois la construction régionale. Cette compétition pour le leadership, d'après lui, pousse la Chine et le Japon à prendre l'initiative pour approfondir l'intégration régionale et ce faisant, passer pour le leader naturel de la région et qui peut être un élément majeur allant dans le sens d'une grande intégration. Il précise que, dans le même temps, l'absence d'hégémon régional semble rendre impossible l'aboutissement d'un projet d'union régionale. Pékin n'acceptera pas de prendre part à une union régionale où Tokyo jouerait le premier rôle, le Japon n'acceptera de voir la Chine présider aux destinées de la zone Est-orientale. Il conclut que, porteuse d'espoirs en termes d'une intégration qui rapproche les peuples d'Asie orientale, la construction régionale asiatique n'en demeure pas moins une configuration potentiellement conflictuelle.

CEA, présente dans son deuxième rapport de 2006 sur l'état de l'intégration en Afrique, que les pays africains ont constamment poursuivi leur coopération et leur intégration régionale dans le but d'atteindre une croissance économique forte et autonome et devenir ainsi des acteurs importants et effectifs de l'économie mondiale. Aujourd'hui, l'intégration régionale en Afrique est conduite, mise en œuvre et soutenue par de nombreux acteurs incluant les gouvernements, les institutions régionales et sous-régionales, et les partenaires au développement.⁸ Tous ces acteurs contribuent à l'avancement de ce processus. Cependant, comme cela a été mentionné dans son rapport I, le processus d'intégration en Afrique n'a pas fait de progrès majeurs malgré les nombreux efforts faits. Elle rajoute que, une des conclusions dudit rapport était que pour accélérer le processus d'intégration, une coordination plus efficace parmi les différents acteurs et programmes est nécessaire. La CEA, montre aussi que, de nombreuses institutions ont été créées pour coordonner les actions de coopération au niveau sous-régional et cela a conduit à une duplication des activités et certaines confusions dans les mandats. Par conséquent, son deuxième

⁸ CEA, *Etat de l'intégration régionale en Afrique II: Rationalisation des communautés économiques régionales* (Addis-Abeba, Ethiopie, 2006).

rapport a analysé les défis institutionnels de l'intégration régionale dans cet espace, à examiner les mandats, les activités et les zones d'opération des institutions existantes. Elle conclut que, les bases institutionnelles de l'intégration régionale africaine ont besoin d'être rationalisées et propose plusieurs scénarios pour cette rationalisation. Les institutions en charge de l'intégration ont besoin d'avoir des capacités techniques, légales et financières pour être effective et cela permettra de renforcer les institutions pour qu'elles contribuent de manière plus efficace à l'intégration régionale.

Au regard de ce qui précède, notre article élargit la panoplie des approches sur l'intégration régionale. Nous constatons toutefois que le principal problème des approches de politique comparée appliquées à l'intégration régionale est leur négligence des structures internationales ou mondiales. C'est ce lien entre régionalisation et mondialisation qui est la caractéristique principale des études sur le nouveau ou les nouveaux régionalismes. En cela, le caractère protéiforme des processus régionaux ne se retrouve pas seulement dans le contenu des accords mais aussi dans l'intensité des relations économiques et dans l'interaction des dimensions économiques et institutionnelles qui n'est possible que dans une gouvernance internationale.

2 - Méthodologie d'analyse systémique de processus d'intégration

L'approche du nouveau régionalisme, tout comme «l'ancien régionalisme», s'inscrivent toujours dans les analyses des relations internationales, plus particulièrement dans l'économie politique internationale. Elle offre la possibilité de comparer le processus d'intégration européenne à d'autres phénomènes d'intégration régionale.⁹ C'est une approche qui va nous permettre de faire une analyse systémique de différents processus d'intégration.

⁹ Saurugger, *Théories et concepts*, 377.

Le nouveau régionalisme a comme objectif de dépasser par le haut l'idée que le processus de l'intégration européenne est considéré comme unique et ne peut pas être comparé à d'autres. L'ensemble des théoriciens qui s'inscrivent dans cette logique soulignent que l'intégration européenne peut être abordée comme un exemple parmi d'autres des processus de régionalisation. Cela entraîne une question plus large, celle de savoir si le phénomène de la régionalisation peut être analysé comme une forme territoriale de la mondialisation. De ce fait, la régionalisation et la mondialisation ne sont que deux manifestations d'un processus d'intégration économique qui a lieu à deux échelles différentes et qui entraîne davantage d'interdépendance.¹⁰ Ainsi, puisque le régionalisme dans sa seconde version semble être un phénomène universel, alors, on ne peut le saisir que par une étude comparative de ses processus variés. Les relations de corrélation entre intégration régionale et mondialisation peuvent être conceptualisées.

A partir de la question initialement posée dans les études sur les régionalisations, à savoir pourquoi les Etats souverains acceptent de s'unir dans un ensemble régional et d'abandonner leurs prérogatives, le terrain de recherche s'est élargi pour englober les relations entre différents niveaux de gouvernance, abordé de manière comparative et dépassant clairement les frontières de l'intégration européenne. Cette approche, va nous permettre de faire une fois de plus l'analyse de liens de causalité ou même de corrélation entre mondialisation-régionalisation.

¹⁰ Peter Katzenstein, "Regionalism in comparative Perspective," *Cooperation and Conflict* (1996): 123.

Tableau 1: Présentation de l'ancien et nouveau régionaliste

Ancien	Nouveau régionalisme
<p>Les régions sont:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *structurées dans un contexte de guerre froide; *dépendantes de l'influence d'une puissance extérieure pour exister; *protectionnistes; *sectorielles; *elles ne posent pas ou peu de défis à la souveraineté 	<p>Les régions sont:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *formées dans un contexte multipolaire et globalisé; *initiées et approfondies par des Etats membres et non par des puissances extérieures; *économiquement ouvertes; *multifonctionnelles; <p>Elles participent à la transformation de la souveraineté étatique</p>

Source: Björn Hettne, op. cit.

3 - Analyse de processus d'intégration régionale

Une des spécificités du nouveau régionalisme est l'accent mis sur l'existence du lien entre mondialisation et régionalisation.¹¹ Les divers travaux sur la mondialisation trouvent un consensus dans l'idée que ce processus met en question la souveraineté de l'Etat et sonne le glas d'un système Westphalien dans lequel l'Etat était l'acteur central. L'idée principale du nouveau régionalisme est que s'il faut encore analyser les processus internes de l'intégration, fondée sur les acteurs, de processus, de normes, et des cadres

¹¹ Mariol Telo, "Introduction: Globalization, New Regionalism and the Role of the European Union," dans *European Union and New Regionalism, Regional Actors and Global Governance in a Post- Hegemonic Era*, édité par Mario Telo (Londres: Ashgate, 2^e édition, 2007).

cognitifs, il s'avère également important de s'interroger sur l'influence des facteurs externes ou plus généralement du système global sur ces processus. Le tableau ci-dessous nous présente les facteurs menant aux degrés de régionalisme. Cette analyse se fait au travers des spécificités institutionnelle et économique de l'intégration régionale afin d'élucider la causalité ou la corrélation entre mondialisation et régionalisation.

Tableau 2: Les facteurs menant aux degrés du régionalisme

Facteurs de régionalisation	Caractéristiques
*Espace régional	*Ensemble géographique lié par le commerce et la gestion des conflits
*Complexe régional	*Ensemble structuré par une interdépendance économique très limitée
*Société régionale	*Fondée sur les règles communes, des acteurs étatiques et non étatiques et peut devenir davantage institutionnalisée
*Communauté régionale	*Normes partagées, Société civile transnationale est reconnue comme acteur central
*Etat régional	*Etat pluraliste dans lequel la souveraineté étatique est effectivement remplacée

Source: Björn Hettne, op. cit.

3 - 1 - Les spécificités institutionnelle et économique de l'intégration régionale

L'Union européenne est l'institution la plus ancienne, et la plus importante en nombre de pays et la plus aboutie en termes de degré d'intégration.¹² En effet, dans le processus de son intégration, il est fait explicitement référence à un processus fédéral progressif, à une tendance de la fédéralisation ou encore à une dynamique «proto-fédérale». Sa gouvernance économique s'inscrit dans cette trajectoire puisqu'elle se réalise à plusieurs niveaux. Elle combine centralisation, coordination et décentralisation. Autrement dit, aux côtés de politiques uniques et centralisées, coexistent des politiques coordonnées de manière étroite et d'autres de manière beaucoup plus souple, voire totalement décentralisées. Le succès du processus d'intégration économique européen a indéniablement incité bon nombre de pays à se regrouper. L'Union européenne participe aussi au nouveau régionalisme puisqu'elle développe des relations privilégiées avec sa proximité, à savoir le partenariat Euro-Méditerranéen, le processus de stabilisation en Europe du Sud-Est et depuis 2003, la politique européenne de voisinage des pays d'Afrique (48 pays), des caraïbes (15 pays) et du pacifique (16 pays), du Mercosur et autres.

Quant à l'ASEAN, avec plus de 50 ans après sa création, elle affiche des ambitions économiques modernes. Elle va néanmoins jusqu'en 1992, permettre une intégration progressive des économies des Etats membres et s'institutionnalise dans la période. La communauté économique de l'ASEAN suit des principes bien différents de ceux qui ont présidé à la construction européenne. Elle est pourtant appelée à jouer un rôle moteur dans la structuration de la région Asie pacifique. Cependant, même si l'ASEAN s'est progressivement transformée pour s'adapter aux défis de son environnement, sa construction économique régionale mise en place est marquée par deux grandes constantes. Son régionalisme est ouvert et

¹² Echinard, «L'Union européenne».

développemental, ce qui la démarque des entreprises d'intégration économique observées dans d'autres régions et explique les tensions récurrentes entre agendas nationaux et objectif d'intégration. Il reste que l'ASEAN, quelle que soit sa malléabilité, peut jouer un rôle moteur dans la structuration économique de l'Asie-Pacifique. Avec les bouleversements observés depuis peu, l'occasion lui est offerte de devenir plus proactif, de prendre son sort en main et au-delà, celui de l'ensemble de la région Asie.¹³

En ce qui concerne les Etats africains, ils sont loin d'être tous prêts à consentir les abandons de souveraineté permettant de donner le véritable coup d'envoi de l'intégration. Seuls l'union douanière d'Afrique australe et l'UEMOA, ont jusqu'ici bénéficié de véritables transferts de souveraineté. En effet, la meilleure preuve de cette résistance est donnée par les alliances internationales que les pays contractent sans tenir compte de leurs obligations régionales. On peut dire que, l'Afrique est plus que jamais pleinement intégrée dans les échanges internationaux. Ses avantages comparatifs s'y redéfinissent à travers les cycles de valorisation de ses matières premières mais aussi et surtout l'émergence du continent en tant qu'espace interface où la faiblesse des Etats incite à la globalisation des trafics trans-étatiques.¹⁴

Le caractère protéiforme des processus régionaux ne se trouve pas seulement dans le contenu des accords mais aussi dans l'intensité des relations économiques et dans l'interaction des dimensions économiques et institutionnelles, que seule l'Union européenne combine, avec une pluralité d'expériences institutionnelles, illustré dans le tableau ci-après.

¹³ Françoise Nicolas, *La communauté économique de l'ASEAN: un modèle d'intégration régionale* (Paris: Ifri / Édition Politique économique, 2017), 12.

¹⁴ Daniel Bach, « Régionalisme, régionalisation et globalisation, » dans *L'Afrique en science Politique*, édité par Mamoudou Gazibe et Céline Tiriol 5 (Paris: éd. Karthala, 2009).

Tableau 3: Commerce intra-régional en % du total dans le monde

	1995	2000	2005	2010	2014
Afrique					
Exportations	12,4	9,2	9,2	13,8	15,7
Importation	11,4	13,6	13,5	14,7	14,6
Asie					
Exportation	52,9	51,5	55,8	59,9	61,5
Importation	54,1	59,6	63,6	63,6	62,2
Europe					
Exportation	71,9	72,9	74,1	71,2	69,0
Importation	70,9	68,6	70,1	67,4	67,6

Source: UNCTAD-Stat

Ces données statistiques permettent de mettre en exergue la pluralité des processus régionaux mais aussi de montrer que la réalité institutionnelle ne va pas toujours de pair avec une dynamique économique. «Il y a des accords de libre-échange ou d'unions douanières qui ont été signés en grande pompe par des politiciens, mais sont demeurés des coquilles vides parce que des entreprises n'ont pas occupé l'espace qui s'ouvrait à eux. En revanche, une zone économique peut se former et s'unir de plus en plus parce que des entreprises coopèrent en dépit des frontières qu'aucun traité

n'a amoindries.»¹⁵ La relation entre intégration par le marché et intégration institutionnelle est complexe et non déterminée et leur interaction dépend des régions. Si les deux réalités sont relativement bien développées dans un processus régional, alors ce dernier s'auto-entretient. L'expérience européenne illustre l'endogénéité d'un tel processus.

3 - 2 - Causalité ou corrélation entre Mondialisation-Régionalisation

Les formes de régionalisation sont donc autant influencées par des acteurs positionnés au sein de l'ensemble régional en question que par des processus mondiaux, disait Saurugger. Sous cet angle, les processus de régionalisation sont des formes intimement liées d'un même phénomène de transformation globale, mais peuvent être aussi bien complémentaires que contradictoires.¹⁶ En effet, la perspective endogène souligne mieux les similarités qui existent entre l'ancien et le nouveau régionalisme, en particulier en ce qui concerne la théorisation fonctionnaliste et néo fonctionnaliste, le rôle du mandatant ou mandaté (principal-agent), ainsi que les transformations à long termes des identités territoriales. La majorité des travaux contemporains souligne le caractère multidimensionnel des intégrations, les Etats ne sont que des acteurs parmi d'autres bien que certains auteurs définissent le processus de régionalisation toujours par rapport aux Etats.

Dans le débat autour du lien entre mondialisation et régionalisation, deux thèmes reviennent régulièrement à savoir, d'une part, le constat que le degré de complexité caractérisant le processus de mondialisation existe également dans le processus de régionalisation. Le nouveau régionalisme doit être compris comme un processus qui se déroule sur différents niveaux

¹⁵ Jean Prestieau, «Blocs économiques et libéralisation du commerce,» dans *la Mondialisation: origines, développement et effets*, édité par Thwaites J. (dir), 207 (Laval: Presses de l'Université de Laval, 2004).

¹⁶ Andrew Hurrell, «The Regional Dimension in International relation Theory,» dans *Global Politics of Regionalism, theory and Practice*, ed. Mary Farrell, Björn Hettne et Luc Van Langenhove (Londres: Pluto Press, 2005).

et selon différentes dimensions. Il a lieu dans les arènes divers qui s'appuie sur un ensemble d'acteurs extrêmement hétérogène, agissant aussi bien d'en haut que d'en bas et lient des intérêts, des idées et des identités.

Selon cette lecture, un grand nombre d'éléments que nous trouvons dans les analyses de la mondialisation peuvent être retrouvés dans les analyses de la régionalisation. Cette dernière pourrait ainsi être vue comme une forme de mondialisation à petite échelle. D'autre part, le régionalisme est souvent considéré comme l'obstacle normalement bon à la mondialisation, celui qui permet de protéger la société contre les effets néfastes de la mondialisation libérale. Selon cette perspective, la régionalisation doit être comprise sous l'angle de la mondialisation.¹⁷ L'intégration régionale est donc premièrement le processus qui permet le mieux de concilier les pressions changeantes et de plus en plus pressantes de la concurrence capitaliste mondiale. Deuxièmement, l'intégration régionale offre également une perspective pertinente pour analyser le besoin d'une régulation et d'une gestion politique. Ensuite, les règles de coordination et de régulation sont plus facilement acceptées dans un contexte d'intégration régionale approfondie, dans la mesure où le consensus social est plus élevé. Enfin, pour un certain nombre de pays en voie de développement, en particulier dans le cadre de l'ASEAN et de la CEA, le régionalisme permet de concilier l'économie libérale à un degré de protection sociale et donc en quelque sorte, de renforcer ou de réinstaurer leur autonomie. Une des manières pour les Etats de poursuivre leur autonomie est l'institutionnalisation de la coopération dans le domaine de l'intégration économique. Dans ce contexte, l'approche de l'économie politique internationale offre un ensemble de questions cohérentes qui lient les dynamiques internes de l'union européenne, les politiques internes des Etats et le processus du changement mondialisé.

¹⁷ Ibid.

Pour affirmer notre hypothèse, celui de savoir comment établir la causalité ou même la corrélation entre mondialisation et régionalisation, Björn Hettne,¹⁸ est l'un des premiers qui tente d'y parvenir. Son point de départ sur cette analyse est la théorie économique de Karl Polanyi, selon laquelle, l'expression et l'approfondissement du marché sont généralement suivis par une intervention politique de défense des intérêts sociétaux.¹⁹ Ce double mouvement représente, selon lui, une compréhension nuancée de la mondialisation comparée à la dichotomie qui distingue la mondialisation comme pression exercée sur la régionalisation et la régionalisation comme obstacle à la mondialisation. Dans cette conception, Saurugger affirme que la régionalisation est un mouvement aussi bien participant à davantage de libéralisation que proposant davantage d'orientations interventionnistes. Une telle lecture pour lui, permet d'inclure l'agent ou les acteurs et de considérer le régionalisme comme un processus politique.

La première séquence part de l'observation d'une institutionnalisation délibérée du marché libéralisé et de la destruction des institutions créées pour assurer la protection sociale, un mouvement décrit comme dérégulation en ligne avec l'idée de la mondialisation financière. Comme l'analyse un grand nombre de spécialistes de politiques publiques et de comparativistes, ce mouvement mène ensuite à une nouvelle régulation généralement après une période de mobilisation sociale importante.²⁰ Si le projet de mondialisation est conceptualisé comme le premier pas dans l'institutionnalisation du système demarché au niveau global, on peut supposer que des forces politiques variées vont tenter d'influencer ce processus et de le politiser. Pour Saurugger, il existe donc des acteurs dans ce processus, dont les intérêts ne sont ni compatibles, ni forcément bons. Suivant le même argument Peter (2002), s'appuyant toutefois moins sur l'analyse des politiques publiques, souligne que depuis la fin de la guerre

¹⁸ Hettne, Björn, et al, *Globalism and New Regionalism* (Basingstoke: Macmillan, 1999).

¹⁹ Saurugger, *Théories et Concepts*, 393.

²⁰ Mark Thatcher, *Internationalization and Economic Institutions. Comparing European Experience* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007).

froide, les régions sont devenues les acteurs centraux pour comprendre la politique internationale et il avance l'hypothèse selon laquelle, la mondialisation et l'internationalisation créent des régions poreuses qui offrent des solutions aux contradictions entre Etat et marché, sécurité et insécurité, nationalisme et cosmopolitisme.

A la lumière de ce qui précède, cette pensée ne permet pas de conceptualiser le lien entre mondialisation et régionalisation. Ce qui se gagne et ce qui se perd, affirme Saurugger, dans ce jeu ne dépend pas de la puissance de l'Etat chère aux réalistes classiques. En revanche, nous sommes confrontés à un système complexe géré par un ensemble de normes structurantes créées par des institutions internationales comme l'OMC ou les Nations Unies. L'auteur ajoute que, dans ce contexte, nous pouvons avancer l'argument que la région permet d'influencer ce jeu de puissance et de pouvoirs, le potentiel d'influence sur les négociations étant lié à la capacité de créer des coalitions.

Il conclut que, l'un des facteurs qui rend ce lien mondialisation-régionalisation si important dans l'analyse actuelle de processus d'intégration européenne, est son intérêt pour la corrélation entre facteurs exogènes et endogènes. L'Union européenne pour lui, n'est pas seulement appréhendée comme un système politique quelconque, bien qu'elle représente un grand nombre de ces caractéristiques, elle est également pensée comme un système sur lequel un certain nombre d'acteurs extérieurs exercent une pression. Enfin, il démontre que cette dialectique qui existe implicitement dans les travaux de la sociologie des relations internationales, tout en ne lui accordant qu'une valeur heuristique est ici considérée comme centrale et structure la réflexion jusqu'à pousser un certain nombre d'acteurs à considérer l'Etat comme acteur principal.

Conclusion et recommandations

Le caractère protéiforme des processus régionaux ne se retrouve pas seulement dans le contenu des accords mais aussi dans l'intensité des relations économiques et dans l'interaction des dimensions économiques et institutionnelles. L'intégration régionale est désormais considérée comme étant une des clés de stabilité dans un contexte d'ouverture croissante des économies nationales, au sein de leurs espaces et au niveau mondiale, afin de faire face à la crise post COVID-19.

Sur le lien entre mondialisation et régionalisation, deux thèmes reviennent régulièrement à savoir, le constat que le degré de complexité caractérisant le processus de mondialisation existent également dans le processus de régionalisation, le régionalisme est souvent considéré comme l'obstacle moralement bon à la mondialisation, ce qui permet de protéger la société contre les effets néfastes de la mondialisation libérale. Quant aux hypothèses de causalité ou même de corrélation, la régionalisation est un mouvement aussi bien participant à davantage de libéralisation que proposant davantage d'orientations interventionnistes et qui permet d'inclure l'agent ou les acteurs, et de considérer le régionalisme comme un processus politique et que la mondialisation est conceptualisé comme le premier pas dans l'institutionnalisation du système de marché au niveau global et on peut supposer que des forces politiques variées vont tenter d'influencer ce processus et de le politiser.

Il faut ajouter que, l'un des facteurs qui rend ce lien entre mondialisation et régionalisation est son intérêt pour la corrélation entre facteurs exogènes et endogènes de l'intégration régionale. Toutefois, cette nouvelle donne des relations internationales interpelle autant la communauté scientifique, les responsables des organisations internationales que les décideurs politiques. C'est pourquoi, les pays africains doivent appliquer le nouveau régionalisme comme stratégie de diversification de leurs économies afin de booster leurs compétitivités. Cette approche peut permettre aussi à l'Union européenne

d'être très compétitive afin de consolider sa position dans le monde face à la Chine et les Etats-Unis, car son avenir, c'est l'intégration économique plus juste et plus durable. De ce fait, la gouvernance institutionnelle doit être une stratégie qui peut contribuer à renforcer le lien réciproque entre marché et institutions, autrement dit, entre mondialisation et régionalisation.

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The Post Covid-19 Crisis: Effects on the Development of Africa and its Relations with the European Union – An Economic Geography Approach of Globalisation

Luis A. COLLADO-CUETO

luis.collado@uam.es

José MELLA

jose.mella@uam.es

Abstract: *The New Economic Geography has focused on the study of globalisation and its territorial impacts, including those related to development.¹ In this analytical process, a new element has broken out whose capacity to affect the globalising process and the location of activities is undeniable: the global pandemic COVID-19. Indeed, the rapid spread of the virus itself has been closely linked to the intense globalisation of passenger flows, favoured by the reduction of airfares in recent decades. This paper presents the current state of this debate, analyses the impacts of the pandemic on the economic geography of globalisation, and sets out some economic policies to address these impacts both for health and economic crisis. In particular, the effects of Covid-19 on the processes of loss of relevance of global value chains, the relocation of production from emerging countries in other countries near consumer centres, the reduction of people's mobility and the effects of commodity price declines on the different economies of the African continent are discussed here.*

In short, it is a question of examining the deglobalising effect on the economy, the processes of regionalisation and renationalisation of production or reshoring and its effects on Africa. These changes could lead to a new geography of economic development, which will pose new challenges to Africa, but also to the EU and the relations between both continents. The analysis is based on the DHL Global Connectedness Index (GCI), developed by Altman and Bastian² from trade, capital, information and people flows, and other globalisation indexes.

Key words: *Africa, African Union, economic development, economic geography, European Union, globalisation, regional integration.*

¹ P. Krugman, *Desarrollo, Geografía y Teoría Económica* (Barcelona: Antoni Bosch Editor 1997).

² S. A. Altman and P. Bastian, *DHL Global Connectedness Index: Mapping the Current State of Global Flows* (DHL, Bonn 2019), <<https://www.dhl.com/content/dam/dhl/global/core/documents/pdf/g0-en-gci-2019-update-complete-study.pdf>>

1. Introduction

In recent decades, globalisation has shaped a new world production model with the increasing importance of global value chains that blur traditional production specialisations. Production processes take place throughout several countries, which increases world trade in intermediate goods. At the same time, many of these products do not supply solely or preferably national markets, but are increasingly being sold in international markets. This process has led to a geographical redistribution of productive activity that, on the other hand, is not static. It moves from one country or continent to another, depending on how competitive advantages evolve.

This process began to show the first signs of slowing down as a consequence of the 2007 crisis, with different effects depending on the dimensions of globalisation to which we refer in each case.

Africa's development cannot be oblivious to that reality. The continent must seek its best opportunities to integrate in the process. The African market is not only large, but it is also immersed in an unstoppable expansion, to the point that it will double its population in the next thirty years. Added to this reality are the processes of economic integration of the continent, which favour the current formation of a large African internal market for goods and services. However, these elements should not generate protectionist temptations and a relative disconnection from world markets, as happened in Latin America in the last century. The continent needs to look for its opportunities in the context of globalisation.

The objective of this paper is to know the current trends in the process of economic globalisation in order to identify its evolution and evaluate the dimensions of its decline or expansion. This should allow Africa to define a strategy to better take advantage of the opportunities in this new global context. However, the analysis is extended with the consideration of the effects that the COVID 19 pandemic may have, both those already produced

and the potential ones. These effects should also determine the policies that these countries will take in the coming years.

2. Current trends in the economic geography of globalisation

The New Economic Geography has focused its attention on the analysis of globalisation and its territorial impacts, including those related to development.³ In this sense, one of the topics that has been generating the most interest in recent years is the effect of the 2007 economic crisis on globalisation and, more recently, what has been the incidence of the end of the crisis. In this analytical process, a new element has emerged that is capable of affecting the globalisation process and the location of activities: the global pandemic COVID-19. In fact, the rapidity of the virus' expansion is closely linked to the intense globalisation of passenger flows, favoured by the reduction in airfares in recent decades. This section presents the state of that debate and, immediately afterwards, presents initial analyses and reflections on the impact of the pandemic on the economic geography of globalisation, which will surely take up a good part of the work of the next years.

The crisis suffered by the world economy since 2007 has not interrupted the globalisation process, but it has meant a brake on its growth pace. This situation has been favoured not only by the fall in demand and its effects on international trade, but also by a certain recent return to US-led protectionist practices.

Protectionism adds to the emergence of a growing deterioration of multilateralism, which is at the basis of the repatriation of productive activities and new forms of protectionism. Both, repatriation and protectionism, are even more damaging to globalisation processes than the increases in customs tariffs (the so-called trade and technological "cold wars" between China and the US).

³ Krugman, *Desarrollo, Geografía y Teoría Económica*.

In this global context, U.S. leadership in the world is stuck when it comes to addressing global problems. In addition, the country may abandon the Paris Agreement on climate change in the coming months and has already announced the abandonment of the World Health Organization (WHO).

These conditions increase the relevance of the EU's role. Its collaboration with WHO in its test, therapy and vaccine plan is essential to strengthen health systems in Africa and to avoid an economic and humanitarian catastrophe in the continent. We must not forget that, unlike other crises, the current Covid-19 is global has no borders, affects virtually every country in the world, and exiting it requires close international cooperation and global solutions.

This is also accompanied by a certain decline in the importance of global value chains, mainly motivated by the increase in labour costs in emerging countries, where a considerable part of their production is located, but also by the impact of these protectionist policies on foreign investment. These elements favour not only the relocation of productions from emerging countries to others with lower production costs, such as from China to Africa. They also promote processes of renationalisation or reshoring towards the countries of origin, which try to reduce uncertainty in the production chains.⁴ These practices revitalise other types of comparative advantages, such as those derived from just-in-time, even more so when production is located near consumption centres, which also contributes to create value for the consumer.

⁴ L. M. Ellram, W. L. Tate, and K. Petersen, "Offshoring And Reshoring: An Update On The Manufacturing Location Decision," *Journal Of Supply Chain Management*, 49, 2 (2013): 14-22.

Figure 1. DHL Global Connectedness Index 2001-2018

Source: Altman and Bastian (2019)

The DHL Global Connectedness Index (GCI), proposed by Altman and Bastian⁵ from the flows of trade, capital, information and people since 2001, shows an increasing global trend since 2002, although with setbacks in 2008, 2011, 2015, 2016 and 2018 (Figure 1). Although these setbacks do not counteract the tendency of globalisation to expand, they can be an indication of how the economic crisis has been able to slow down the process. If we consider the data for the last year published, it can be seen that the fall experienced in 2018 by the GCI responds precisely to the reduction in foreign direct investment flows, a trend that has been occurring since 2016, according to data from UNCTAD in 2019.

This data constitutes, in turn, an indication of a certain setback in the formation of global value chains, regardless of the effect of US fiscal policies that favoured the repatriation of profits obtained abroad that year. Regarding international trade, the data from the WTO reveal that its trend continues to grow, although in recent years its increases are similar to those

⁵ S. A. Altman and P. Bastian, *DHL Global Connectedness Index: Mapping the Current State of Global Flows*.

of GDP or even lower (2014, 2015 and 2016), which could be also considered as a sign of the aforementioned slowdown process. However, the GCI still does not collect data that allow us to conclusively affirm that is taking place regionalisation of greater intensity than globalisation itself, although trade, capital and people flows are indeed more intense between neighbouring countries.

From this recent context, which could even be seen as foreseeable in the context of the cycles of the world economy, a new crisis has arisen as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. In the short term, the health crisis has led to a global recession that the World Bank quantified at 5.2% in its Global Economic Prospects of June 2020.⁶ Many authors foresee a rapid recovery, probably in the form of a V or a U, to the extent that its origin is not due to problems in the financial or political markets since the exit has followed this pattern in the case of other global pandemics.⁷

Although the recovery would be relatively quick, it is still early to evaluate and, even more, to quantify the effects that this new crisis may have on the world economic geography, the economic development and the process of globalisation itself. However, it is plausible to think that protectionist measures and the relocation processes of activities could be intensified, with a very notable return towards the closest or even national markets, in which case world trade flows would be reduced.⁸ The model carried out by Olivié and Gracia⁹ from the Elcano Global Presence Index based on three

⁶ World Bank, Global Economic Prospects, June 2020, Washington, DC. (2020), <<https://open.knowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/33748>>

⁷ P. Carlsson-Szlezak, M. Reeves and P. Swartz, "What Coronavirus Could Mean for the Global Economy," *Harvard Business Review*, 3 March 2020, <<https://hbr.org/2020/03/what-coronavirus-could-mean-for-the-global-economy>>

⁸ E. Fanjul, "El coronavirus, ¿nuevo impulso a la desglobalización?" *Blog Elcano*, 12/03/2020, Madrid: Real Instituto Elcano, <<https://blog.realinstitutoelcano.org/el-coronavirus-nuevo-impulso-a-la-desglobalizacion/>>

⁹ I. Olivié and M. Gracia, "¿El fin de la globalización? Una reflexión sobre los efectos de la crisis del COVID-19 desde el Índice Elcano de Presencia Global," *Blog Elcano ARI 43/2020*, Madrid: Real Instituto Elcano, <http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/portal/rielcano_

possible scenarios of crisis intensity (equal to that of 2008, worse than it or with sectorial differentiated transformative effects), indicates that only in one of them, that of a crisis worse than that of 2008, effective deglobalisation would occur. In the first scenario, the pace of the post-crisis globalisation process would be maintained. In the last one, it would only stop, based on a slight setback in economic globalisation (trade in energy, raw materials, goods and services, as well as investment flows) that would be offset by increases in the so-called “soft dimension”, linked to technology, information, culture, science, education, sports, tourism, migration and development cooperation.

If we go deeper into the effects of the crisis, we could first identify possible changes on the demand side. Its origin would be found, initially, in the reduction in consumption derived from periods of confinement. From there, the possibility of changes in consumption patterns arising from those that could lead to consumer tastes or even a loss of confidence is raised,¹⁰ regardless of the drop that occurs as a result of the reduction in income during the time that the recession and crisis continue. Some preliminary data indicates the existence of price falls in the markets for raw materials, especially agriculture and energy,¹¹ which could indicate that the effect of demand has been even greater than the supply shock that we will later analyse.

Within these effects of demand, the crisis of COVID-19 can affect in a very intense way the mobility of people, beyond that imposed by the periods of confinement implanted to stop the spread of the virus. The expansion of air transport and the lowering of its rates, something that favoured the

es/contenido?WCM_GLOBAL_CONTEXT=/elcano/elcano_es/zonas_es/ari43-2020-olivie-gracia-fin-de-la-globalizacion-reflexion-efectos-crisis-covid-19-indice-ecano-de-presencia-global>

¹⁰ Carlsson-Szlezak, Reeves and Swartz, “What Coronavirus Could Mean for the Global Economy.”

¹¹ L. Cadamuro and F. Papadia, *Three macroeconomic issues and Covid-19* (Brussels: Bruegel 2020), <<https://www.bruegel.org/2020/03/three-macroeconomic-issues-and-covid-19/>>

formation of a sort of “global office” as well as the globalisation of tourist destinations, threatens to experience a sharp decline. This decline would be the result of a drop in demand, due firstly to the perception of risk and, additionally, to the fall in income levels. In this situation, tourists may choose, largely, for domestic destinations or even international, but limited to closer places or with hygienic-sanitary conditions perceived as safer. The intensity of these changes will be conditioned by the intensity of the health crisis itself. This drop in demand will be reinforced by the increase in airfares, as a consequence of the supply shock resulting from the reduction in the number of passengers.

This effect of COVID-19 on tourism flows will generate, at least in the short term, a negative impact for countries with greater sector specialisation in this activity. However, damage will be even greater in those with lower income levels, in which tourism concentrates a large part of employment and is one of the main sources of foreign exchange. Thus, it seems likely that in the short term there will be a deglobalising effect of this activity in favour of more regional or even national tourism, which could alter competitiveness in some current tourist destinations and even a global reconfiguration of them.

With regard to the changes on the supply side, the short-term effects, derived from the temporary closings of activity by the authorities, could be reinforced by additional changes derived from the regionalisation and renationalisation of production. The shortage of raw materials and intermediate goods, caused by the closings of the activity in the countries of origin and the restrictions on transport,¹² could increase the perception of risk of operating in the global value chains. This is especially important for Africa, where less than 15% of its inputs come from the continent and whose imports of capital goods and intermediate products from third countries have been slowed by the pandemic. In this context, the preference

¹² Ibid.

for national or closer suppliers could increase, in line with the trend indicated by Ellram, Tate, and Petersen,¹³ towards more decentralised value chains.¹⁴ These processes would generate a further brake on the globalisation process. Changes in the supply chain of companies and their effects on the formation of value chains could also affect the evolution of foreign direct investment (FDI), widening the negative trend experienced since 2016.¹⁵

This twin supply and demand shock has a great capacity to affect world economies and the globalisation process itself if the appropriate political measures are not taken. In this sense, the special vulnerability of Africa to external shocks should be highlighted due to its current dependence on income and financing from other continents (remittances, FDI and foreign aid), its exports (mainly oil and other commodities), and also its imports (capital and intermediate goods), as shown in the databases and reports of the World Bank, International Monetary Fund and World Trade Organisation.

At the present time, the main challenge of the New Economic Geography is to interpret the recent changes that the globalisation process is undergoing and its impacts on the different territories. In this sense, it is necessary to understand not only the consequences of the 2007 crisis and its evolution, but also what the impacts of the COVID-19 crisis will be. Some of these possible effects have been tried to point out in this section based on the first studies and reflections that experts and academics are proposing.

The first data indicates that the consolidation of the brake on globalisation as a consequence of the new crisis is foreseeable, as are the recent

¹³ Ellram, Tate and Petersen, "Offshoring And Reshoring: An Update On The Manufacturing Location Decision."

¹⁴ Carlsson-Szlezak, Reeves and Swartz, "What Coronavirus Could Mean for the Global Economy."

¹⁵ A. A. Agyemang and F. Gallardo, "Inversión directa extranjera en África: retos de future," *Información Comercial Española*, Mayo-Junio, no. 914 (2020): 37-56.

processes of regionalisation and renationalisation or reshoring. These changes could affect not only manufacturing, but also services, especially tourism, at least in the short term. These changes could give rise to a new geography of economic development, with a certain return to internal and, where appropriate, regional markets, reinforced by protectionist measures, probably justified under the security umbrella.

The joint consideration of the aforementioned elements also allows us to think about the possibility of a certain structural change in the world economy, with an increase in the importance of the digital economy, which relegates possible advances that may occur in globalisation to some of the activities grouped under “soft” globalisation. This process would increase the competitive advantages of the most advanced countries and regions in terms of digitising their productive activity and with better connectivity infrastructures, which would widen their economic gap compared to those with worse conditions in these two aspects.

3. Economic policies for Africa in a globalised post-Covid 19 context

There is an intense debate on economic policy options that can be adopted on the African continent, under the current conditions of Covid-19. Different national and international institutions, governments, foundations, research institutes, universities, etc. have been expressing their opinions, not always coincidental.

It is often said that there is no single Africa. There are several Africas. This statement is particularly appropriate at the moment. There is an Africa of oil-exporting countries, an Africa of countries specialising in non-renewable natural resources (minerals and metals) and a non-resource-intensive Africa. Appropriate affirmation, because the impact of the Covid-19 is felt strongly through the fall of commodities’ international prices, paralysis of tourist flows, reduced remittances of migrants and difficulties in accessing international financial markets.

The fall in international prices directly affects the African continent by lowering the prices of oil, minerals and metals, causing export revenues to collapse, especially in countries such as Nigeria, Angola and South Africa.

The paralysis of tourist flows represents a severe blow to the economies of countries strongly specialized in the sector such as Cape Verde, Seychelles, Mauritius, and The Gambia, among others.

The reduction in remittances of migrants has an immediate impact on all African countries, heavily dependent on financial resources from the diaspora, to the point that they have become the main source of funding, ahead of foreign investment and official development aid. The impact of the above three effects leads to large losses of income, sharp increases in public deficits, immediate increases in debt (public and private) and services of the same (return of capital and interest payments).

In short, Africa is sinking into a deep recession, the first in decades, with production declines between 5-8% by 2020, according to the scenarios.¹⁶ Difficulties in accessing international financial markets are a consequence of a drastic reduction in government fiscal margins and their low ability to cope with debt financing commitments, while simultaneously facing a double health and economic crisis.

The countries that will suffer the most from this situation will be those with high levels of indebtedness (Angola, Nigeria, Ghana) and therefore with greater limitations to meet payments. Under these conditions, economic policies should act decisively on five fronts: healthcare, socio-business, industrial (Arkebe), monetary, fiscal, and EU-African Union common initiatives.

¹⁶ J. A. Obregón, "Perspectivas económicas en África en tiempos de la Covid-19," *Información Comercial Española*, Mayo-Junio, no. 914 (2020): 25-36.

3.1 Health policy

Strengthening national health systems is necessary and urgent, prioritising investment in them (more health workers, more hospital equipment and equipment, in particular to detect contagion bags), developing international cooperation in the areas of epidemiological knowledge, prevention and treatment protocols. Despite the limited number of current Covid-19 cases, there is no place for complacency. The epidemic is advancing. It should now be borne in mind that, in the coming months, a second and third wave of contagion is foreseeable, posing new risks to the recovery of African economies. Note that Europe and North America are approaching a change of season towards Autumn and Winter, characterised by increased exposure to all types of viruses, including Covid-19.

Africa is moving, as a whole, with weak detection capacity, but at the same time has a stronger will to accelerate governance reforms. Willingness to take measures such as containing the spread, conducting sufficient tests and ensuring that health professionals are sufficiently protected. Work must be done on a plan to reopen economies, as it is a question of combating the pandemic and at the same time minimising collateral damage, both economically, socially and from protection and health care systems. On health care in Africa, it should always be borne in mind that malaria continues to kill more than coronavirus. Measures against Covid-19 should not relax the fight against other infectious diseases such as malaria, AIDS, tuberculosis or measles. Quarantines and routine vaccination campaigns should be organised well, not paralysed, even if an effort must be made so that some health activities do not harm others.

Health prevention activities against AIDS, tuberculosis and malaria significantly reduce the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, Africa needs to strengthen health systems with new investments and develop its participation in research projects of universities and research centres of the more than 100 projects underway today in the world to achieve an effective

vaccine.¹⁷ Incentives and African brain-harvesting programmes, working at universities in developed countries, should be promoted to incorporate them into research programmes at the best African universities. In this regard, strong incorporation of African scientists in the fight against the pandemic and their participation in public debate, promoting technological innovation and cooperation in medical research and the development of health infrastructures is essential,¹⁸ both in the cities and in the countryside.

The role of cities in the fight against this pandemic is very important.¹⁹ The more efficient they are in terms of mobility, transport, sanitation and agglomerations of people, the more efficient they will also be as instruments to combat the contagious spread of the virus. Local authorities should take measures that would reduce to a maximum people's physical proximity, increase the mass use of masks and frequent hand washing.

In rural areas, access to services is even more severe. Women and children need to travel long distances to seek water or go to health services. Then, to improve the provision of local health services, supported by new technologies (such as smart metering, decentralised water points monitoring and waste management) become crucial.

In both areas, improving access to clean water, proper sanitation, and hygiene is crucial. At present, when people in Africa are relaxing their confinements, these local measures are becoming more and more relevant.

¹⁷ WHO Draft landscape of Covid-19 candidate vaccines, 2020, <www.who.int/publications/m/item/draft-landscape-of-covid-19-candidate-vaccines>

¹⁸ A. B. Hogan, et al, "Potential impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on HIV, tuberculosis, and malaria in low-income and middle-income countries: a modelling study," *The Lancet Global Health*, Volume 8 (9) (2020): 1132-1141, <[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30288-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30288-6)>

¹⁹ UN-Habitat *Covid-19 in African countries. Impacts, Responses and Policies*, United Nations Human Settlements Programme, Economic Commission for Africa, Addis Ababa (2020), <<https://www.uncdf.org/Download/AdminFileWithFilename?id=10615&cultureId=127&fileName=covid-19-in-african-cities-impacts-responses-and-policies.pdf>>

3.2 Socio-business policy

It is necessary and urgent to act with social safety nets, food supply and productive boost in the areas of poor families, the unemployed, the informal, street vendors, the self-employed and small/medium-sized and micro-enterprises.

Fieldwork carried out in South Africa shows that COVID-19 has led to the impoverishment of many families. The data is eloquent. COVID-19 has changed the living conditions of individuals and families. Rent level drops, pension plan cuts, strong stress and anxiety levels. A report published on 15/07/2020²⁰ quantifies the effects of Covid-19, deepening the strong levels of inequality already in place in the country. A third of people who had an income in February have lost it in April, half of employees have been permanently laid off, showing that the effects of the pandemic are being lasting or at least perceived as such. The country's unemployment rate, 30% in the first quarter, has risen considerably later.

This same study also shows the unequal effects of economic constraints. Women account for most of the lost jobs, 2 of the 3 million. Manual workers (Blue collars) were fired three times more than professionals were (White collars). Between March 2020 and May 2020, there was a huge internal migration movement: 5 to 6 million people (15% of adults) changed residence. The process of urbanization was reversed. Millions of people returned to their places of origin in rural areas to be reunited with their families. So far, a large majority have not yet returned to the cities.

This phenomenon is not without relevant effects. The first is the pressure on families receiving relatives without jobs or income; they are driving them out of means to feed. Nearly half (47%) of the answers say that they have not been able to buy enough food in the month of April, which represents

²⁰ See *The Economist*, 18 July 2020.

more double the proportion of those who could do so in 2017, according to the available data.

The country's social security system should have cushioned the blow, but unfortunately, mismanagement has not allowed it. It was supposed to serve 15 million unemployed, but by early June 2020 it had paid only 600,000 unemployed insurance, even though the government recognized that 60% of applications could have been admitted.

The situation is exceptionally difficult. The level of business confidence has been at its lowest point since 1975. The unemployment rate could rise to 50%. Public finances are rapidly worsening. Deficit forecasting for the years 2020/21 had been estimated at 6.8% but has been resituated at 15.7%. More than a fifth of the budget will be spent on debt service. Do not forget that South Africa is the fourth most affected country in the world (according to Johns Hopkins University), hospitals are saturated and the epidemiological models used predict that the peak of the pandemic will be reached in July to September 2020, depending on the provinces.

3.3 Industrial and regional integration policies

Ethiopian Minister Arkebe Oqubay argues about the importance of industrial policy in combating the Covid-19 pandemic in Africa.²¹ It proposes that an effective policy strategy should be based on advances in the latest technology and innovations, industrial capacity (hospitals, personal protection equipment and products) and the integration of value chains. It sets an example of the Ethiopian government's approach, which is one of the few exceptions not to adopt confinement at the national level, because of its difficulty of implementation and its negative effects on the poor layers of the population. It carried out rapid mobilisation of quarantine, isolation measures and treatment centres. At the time, it adopted economic policies,

²¹ A. Oqubay, "Industrial policy and Covid-19 responses," *Información Comercial Española*. May-June, no. 914 (2020): 97-114.

reinforcing the strategy of creation of industrial parks and airlines (in a landlocked country such as Ethiopia), which guarantee the provision of medical equipment to the country, the export of meat and fruit and vegetable goods and integration into regional and global value chain creation.

In this crisis, exports have been deeply hit, raising the need to increase productive diversification. The African Union's (AU) large continental initiative of an African Continental Free Trade Area (AfFTA) offers opportunities to drive the industrialisation process, which allows companies to overcome restrictions imposed by overly narrow domestic markets. There are initiatives by Afrexibank, UNECA and the African Union Trade Commission that call for the removal of tariff and non-tariff barriers to trade in sanitary products.²²

Note that African intra-regional trade has a relatively higher weight of industrial content than that in place with the rest of the world. Therefore, it is an advantage that must be exploited to increase the added value, through freedom of trade in broader markets, a more efficient allocation of resources, a greater specialisation and productivity. The current context of the international economy, in which global value chains are diversifying and manufacturing is getting closer and closer to consumers, may be an auspicious time for the African continent to take advantage to develop its economy.

The economic development can be accelerated, by the impetus of the fight against Covid-19, in three areas: the pharmaceutical industry, digitisation and renewable energies. The pharmaceutical industry, with already important bases in countries such as Egypt, Kenya, South Africa, Ethiopia

²² The Presidency South Africa. *African Union Chair, Presidency Ramaphosa launches the Africa Medical Supplies Platform, Africa's Unified Continental Response to fight the pandemic*, 18 June 2020, <www.thepresidency.gov.za/press-statements/covid-19%3A-african-union-chair%2C-president-ramaphosa-launches-africa-medical-supplies-platform%2C-africa%E2%80%99S-unified-continental-response-fight-pandemic>

and Cameroon, could produce for the entire continent, where almost all demand is supplied with imports.

The Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030)²³ should lead to an African digital single market, with corresponding positive effects on economic growth. The prospects for expansion are enormous, given the potential for growth of internet networks, because of still unmet demands from a growing young population and the connectivity needs of families, businesses and governments.

In addition, Covid-19 opens up opportunities for the transition to renewable energy, which offers significant competitive advantages, allows access to electricity for hundreds of millions of people currently without electricity, and is a leading instrument in the fight against climate change.²⁴ Renewable energy undoubtedly contributes to the strengthening of local value chains and job creation, the promotion of investments in electricity interconnection and storage networks, the promotion of reliable access to electricity from health facilities and the Post-Covid-19 economic recovery.

3.4 Monetary policy

Many African countries have seen their debt levels increase in recent years by large loans for infrastructure investments. These loans have become more non-concessional debts with higher interest rates, lower repayment periods, and higher refinancing risks. In addition, the same percentage of debt over GDP is now suddenly a much bigger problem with negative

²³ African Union, *The Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030)*, <<https://au.int/en/documents/20200518/digital-transformation-strategy-africa-2020-2030>>

²⁴ Economic Commission for Africa, *The Impact of Covid-19 on Africa's energy sector and the role of RE to empower a long term and sustainable recovery*, United Nations, Addis Abeba, 24 June 2020.

growth rates. In reality, the Covid-19 crisis has plunged Africa into a debt crisis.²⁵

It is necessary and urgent to provide liquidity, in reduced or zero interest, donations (to the poorest) and promote local/regional debt markets to create resources in the fight against the pandemic, as has already been done in West African countries in recent weeks. Funding needed to alleviate balance-of-payments constraints, relieve/forgive debts, and support families, businesses and governments with guarantees, guarantees and moratoriums. According to Goldman Sachs' Financial Conditions Index, which takes into account the evolution of interest rates and spreads in a set of economies, including Africans, these have risen at levels similar to those observed in 2008-2009.²⁶

This financial tightening is accompanied by a sharp drop in net inflows of foreign capital from a dimension not seen since those years, which is reflected in an extreme depreciation of African currencies against the dollar (compared to January 2020) of 20% for South Africa.

This phenomenon carries with it two weaknesses. First, a reliance on foreign funding and the sensitivity of African economies to sudden capital inflows, especially given the scarcity of reserves, can exacerbate liquidity problems. Second, a high exposure to dollar-denominated debt. It is key to avoid the shortage of dollars and the need to reactivate the Fed's swap lines with African central banks. However, aside from financial tightening and the crunch dollar, one-third point is the one on public solvency, which could lead to an increase in CDS premiums and downward revision of credit ratings due to investors' perception of increased risk.

²⁵ World Bank, *Debt Service Suspension and Covid-19*.

²⁶ Goldman Sachs, *The Case for a Financial Conditions Index*, 16-07-2018, <<https://www.goldmansachs.com/insights/pages/case-for-financial-conditions/report-the-case-for-financial-conditions-index.pdf>>

African borrowers need more grants than loans to facilitate debt sustainability and repayment.²⁷ Given the current difficulties of access to international capital markets, debt relief measures are key to the recovery of African economies. There is no doubt that African countries need to increase tax bases, improve tax collection capacity and transparency, and reduce tax evasion for multinational companies to increase their funding capacity.

3.5 Fiscal policy

In this situation, the Covid-19 shock leads to a reduction in the scope of public policy action. It is necessary and urgent to mobilise the lever of investment, based on a determined political will, to resume economic activity, to create decent sanitary conditions, to recover and improve educational activities, and to lay the foundations for sustainable and inclusive development.

There had already been, before Covid-19, trends towards retreat and the establishment of economic barriers. The idea is that there are certain countries that want to “repatriate” certain supply chains, although it does not seem that if that approach can go beyond health activities. Because the truth is that African economic actors plan to develop their export markets, based on the obvious fact that African raw materials need exits.

The big challenge for Africa is how to add value and keep it in Africa. The resilience of African countries is different depending on their levels of fiscal deficit, debt, external reserves and the current account balance deficit. Countries such as Angola, Congo, Gabon, Libya, Nigeria and South Sudan, oil exporters, are more vulnerable to dealing with payments for imports of health equipment or repayment of dollar-denominated debt.

²⁷ S. Morris, C. Landers, and A. Gardner, *More World Bank Borrowers Will Need Grants, Not Loans. As a Result, More World Bank Donors Will Need to Pony Up*, Center for Global Development, 4/06/2020, <www.cgdev.org/blog/more-world-bank-borrowers-will-need-grants-not-loans-result-more-world-bank-donors-will-need>

3.6 EU-African Union Common Policies

The EU's role in Africa, as a neighbour and natural partner, was defined on 30 June 2020 by the EU Commissioner for International Cooperation as a basis for preparing for the forthcoming EU-African Union (AU) Summit in autumn 2020, when the Heads of State and Government of Africa and Europe meet to identify priorities for a common future. The EU proposal is to work together on 5 global trends: 1. A partnership for a Green transition and access to energy; 2. A partnership for a digital transformation; 3. A partnership for sustainable growth and job creation; 4. A partnership for peace, security and governance; and 5. A partnership on Migration and Mobility.²⁸ This EU proposal really is an ambitious programme of integration EU-AU.

4. Concluding remarks

Reading the media in Africa suggests that Covid-19 reveals the urgency of implementing institutional and governmental reforms. This phenomenon is somewhat underlying, pre-pandemic; but it is manifestly visible today. The continent is becoming aware of the problem of global logistics chains, the need to obtain health equipment and to act all together.

African debt is a very serious problem, a priority. Africa should have access to the help it needs to lighten the weight of it, which is enormous, and not just benefit from a deferment of debt repayment, with the support of the IMF and the World Bank. The G-20 has taken action on trade debt. Even though, more needs to be done. China, as a great creditor, is also playing its role. In the long term, of course, the goal is wealth generation, with better governance and greater leadership.

²⁸ European Council, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council. Towards a comprehensive Strategy with Africa*, Brussels, 9.3.2020 JOIN (2020) 4 final.

Nevertheless, better governance currently involves very difficult challenges. WHO will need to undertake in-depth reforms. China and the US have transferred their rivalry to the WHO ring, with Dr Tedros Ghebreyesus in his role as “punch bag”. In reality, they are disproportionate international games in relation to what WHO really is. The only instance capable of driving reforms is the G-20, because the main countries on the planet are sitting around a table. Hence, the AU has to become a much stronger institution.

For it is very difficult for every African country, however powerful, to be able to orient itself in the confrontation between the US and China. Even countries such as Nigeria and Ethiopia, which are countries that matter in the international arena, are deemed mid-sized actors in the global sphere. Hence, Africa would need its own means to appear in the front row of the concert of nations (According to Toni Blair in 2020).²⁹

Cooperation in the fight against the pandemic is necessary. It is convenient for Africa to take part. On the contrary, it would be a serious mistake. It is in the Africa’s interest to cooperate with the US, China, Russia and Europe (as Paul Kagame stated in 2020).³⁰

The EU and the AU must jointly defend multilateralism within the United Nations to ensure stability and economic growth. Africa and Europe are the main bloc at the United Nations. With unity, the two geopolitical areas reach major international agreements such as the sustainable development agenda by the 2030 horizon, the Paris agreement on climate change and must fight to partner and align in all international forums, such as the G20 and the WTO. They will have to hold a public diplomacy together for

²⁹ T. Blair, “L’Afrique peut couper le cordon de l’assistance,” *Jeune Afrique*, no. 3090, 1 Juillet 2020, 136.

³⁰ P. Kagame, “La grande interview,” *Jeune Afrique*, no. 3090, 1 Juillet 2020, 18.

multilateralism on both continents, address directly to young people, university students and citizens, who are shaping the future world order.³¹

At this moment, when African countries are being prepared for opening their borders, it is more relevant than ever to plot Covid-19 movements across countries, limiting transmissions and infections.

The debt problem is crucial. Poor countries that need to devote their limited budgetary resources to the repayment of external debt rather than investment is a serious drawback. That is why Africa is asking its creditors to agree on a time for African countries to invest rather than repay.

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³¹ European Council, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council. Towards a comprehensive Strategy with Africa*.

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The Evolution of the Free Movement of Lawyers in the European Union and the East African Community Compared: Achievements and challenges in implementing integration freedoms in England and Wales and Rwanda

Helen TROUILLE

h.trouille@yorksj.ac.uk

Mbembe BINDA

bindael@gmail.com

Abstract: *Freedom of movement (FOM) of legal services has brought considerable economic growth to the legal services market in England and Wales and very real benefits to legal practitioners within the European Union (EU). At the same time, another successful Regional Economic Community (REC), the East African Community (EAC), is struggling to commit to FOM of legal services, and Partner States, fearful of competition, prefer to protect their legal services markets rather than embrace integration which could bring growth. This article explores the stream-lined situation in England and Wales and contrasts the concerns associated with the loss of FOM on leaving the EU expressed by legal professional bodies and lawyers there with the reticence encountered in the EAC, focussing on Rwanda.*

It examines how the relevant provisions in the EU directives and EAC Common Market Protocol,¹ which provide the framework for FOM of legal services and lawyers, are enabled by Community and domestic provisions in England and Wales and in Rwanda respectively. This article analyses the EAC's reluctance to embrace liberalisation of the market in legal services despite the commitments of the Common Market Protocol, and concludes finally that, in both contexts, lawyers are losing out – EU lawyers practising in the UK, English and Welsh lawyers practising in the EU, seeing their rights to practice restricted. Similarly, the slow progress to liberalisation of legal services has obstructed cross border practice for Rwandan lawyers in the EAC and hampered growth in the legal services market.

Key words: *Freedom of movement; legal services; freedom of establishment; European Union; East African Community; Brexit.*

¹ Protocol on the Establishment of the East African Community Common Market (Common Market Protocol).

Introduction

The end of the twentieth century and the start of the twenty-first have seen considerable changes to the way in which legal professionals in Europe are called to operate. The expansion of cross-border trade has signified complex commercial transactions and an internationalisation of the legal profession. The traditional model of the small practice or sole practitioner has given way to large or medium-sized law firms offering a range of commercial services,² either as global law firms in their own right or operating across borders in collaboration with foreign partners.³ In addition, the deepening of European integration has signified a greater need for legal experts' advice for consumers and businesses on EU regulatory frameworks. However, the different legal frameworks in EU Member States, the local character of the law, and the fact that it is a highly regulated profession can create obstacles. The route to FOM of legal services in the EU is accompanied by a plethora of case law, a testimony to the challenges of achieving these freedoms.⁴

EU legal texts and case law ensure the freedom of movement of legal services, which enables economic growth,⁵ and at the same time the regulation of legal services. It is not surprising, therefore, that legal professionals in the UK are concerned about the impact that withdrawing from the EU will have on them on both an economic and personal level.

² G. Muller, "Free Movement of Lawyers Within the EU Internal Market." 26 (3) *European Business Law Review* (2015): 355-390, at 355.

³ May, A., "Globalised Law and Best Friends Networks," *The Principle*. (2019) Available at <<https://www.allaboutlaw.co.uk/commercial-awareness/commercial-insights/globalised-law-and-best-friends-networks->> Accessed 24 June 2019.

⁴ See, for example, the frequently cited *Gebhard v Consiglio dell'Ordine degli Avvocati e Procurati di Milano* (Case C-55/94) [1995] ECR I-4165; *Thieffry v Conseil de l'Ordre des avocats à la Cour de Paris* (Case 71/76) [1977] ECR 00765; *Van Binsbergen v Bestuur van de Bedrijfsvereniging Voor de Metaalnijverheid* (Case 33/74) [1974] ECR 1299; *Vlassopoulou v Ministerium für Justiz, Bundes und Europaangelegenheiten Baden-Württemberg* (Case C-340/89) [1991] ECR2357; *Jany* (Case C-268/99) [2001] ECR I-8615 and recent case of *Monachos Eirinaios v Dikigorikos Syllogos Athinon* (Case C-431/17) [2019] ECR 00000.

⁵ Muller, "Free Movement of Lawyers Within the EU Internal Market," 356-7.

The EAC, another very successful REC in its own geographical region, currently anticipates FOM of legal services with more reticence and appears to have hit an obstacle in the liberalisation of legal services markets. This article analyses the provisions in both RECs for FOM of legal services, assesses the advantages and perceived disadvantages of FOM of legal services, and examines whether the barriers facing EAC lawyers may be overcome. It reflects on the similarities in the challenges confronting both RECs and questions what the way forward for them might be, the one as it leaves profitable relationships in a highly successful REC, the other as it struggles to convince key players of the advantage in moving towards greater integration of legal services.

Within the UK, the legal landscape is complicated by the fact that there are three jurisdictions: England and Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland, each with two regulatory bodies which oversee the practice of the two branches of the legal profession, solicitors and barristers. This paper will focus on practice in England and Wales. In every case, the use of the word lawyer is understood to describe legal professionals educated to degree level and holding a professional qualification or certificate to practice as a solicitor, barrister or advocate in these RECs.

PART ONE:

FREEDOM OF MOVEMENT OF LEGAL SERVICES IN THE EU

1.1. The benefits of the freedom of movement of legal services in the EU

The UK has benefitted significantly from the internationalisation of the legal sector.⁶ This includes, among other things, the creation of jobs and the promotion of London as the main ‘European hub’ for US law firms, which allows them to access the European market.⁷ London has become the world’s leading centre for international legal services and dispute resolution, due to the preference of business parties for English common law as a means to resolve international commercial disputes.⁸ This international

⁶ The legal sector contributed over £26 billion to the UK economy in 2016 (TheCityUK, “Legal Excellence, Internationally Renowned UK Legal Services 2018.” November 2018. Available at <<https://www.thecityuk.com/assets/2018/Reports-PDF/86e1b87840/Legal-excellence-internationally-renowned-UK-legal-services-2018.pdf>> Accessed 21 June 2019, p4) and represented the equivalent of 1.5% of the UK’s GDP in 2017 (J. Djanogly MP, in Westminster Hall Debates, “Leaving the EU: Legal Services.” HC Deb, 21 November 2018, c381WH. Available at <<https://www.theyworkforyou.com/whall/?id=2018-11-21b.380.0>> Accessed 15 July 2019, p 2).

⁷ Over 380,000 people are trained and employed in the UK legal services market, which is the second largest in the world after the United States, and the largest legal services sector in the EU. In addition, the UK legal services sector was responsible for a net export of £4 billion in 2017: see APPG on Legal and Constitutional Affairs, *The effect of Brexit on legal services*. October 2018. Law Society of England and Wales. Available at <<https://www.lawsociety.org.uk/policy-campaigns/articles/appg-legal-constitutional-affairs-effect-of-brexit-on-legal-services/>> Accessed 21 June 2019, p. 3.

⁸ In 2017, three quarters of cases before the London Commercial Court were international in character: see Queen Mary University London and White & Case, “2018 International Arbitration Survey: The Evolution of International Arbitration.” Available at <[http://www.arbitration.qmul.ac.uk/media/arbitration/docs/2018-International-Arbitration-Survey---The-Evolution-of-International-Arbitration-\(2\).PDF](http://www.arbitration.qmul.ac.uk/media/arbitration/docs/2018-International-Arbitration-Survey---The-Evolution-of-International-Arbitration-(2).PDF)> Accessed 24 June 2019, p. 5. In an international arbitration at the London Court of International Arbitration and the International Chamber of Commerce, it is not uncommon to find that neither of the parties are English, and that none of the legal representatives are London-based, but clients will be represented by London-based lawyers from international law firms, or English barristers instructed from overseas. Over 200 foreign law firms now have their offices in the UK, and employ over 10,000 people: see TheCityUK, pp. 7-8.

activity provides a substantial source of work for the English Bar and for English Law firms. Within this sector of activity, the EU holds a significant place.⁹ About 100 of the foreign UK-based law firms are EU law firms,¹⁰ and a significant number of EU lawyers benefit from the EU's freedom of movement provisions.¹¹ As freedom of movement rights are reciprocal, UK lawyers have also been able to practice in the EU.¹²

A rapid rise in cross-border transactions in the late nineties helped to stimulate this demand for legal professional services,¹³ but there are concerns amongst legal practitioners that, as a consequence of Brexit, the loss of freedom of movement will have a negative impact on the UK legal services market,¹⁴ and, in an attempt to preserve these rights, some Anglo-Welsh lawyers are registering with the Irish professional bodies.¹⁵

⁹ Statistics from the London Court of International Arbitration show that up to twenty-five per cent of the arbitrations referred to this Court in 2015 were from the EU, as compared to 15.6 per cent from the UK, 14.8 per cent from Russia and the Commonwealth of Independent States, and 12 per cent from Asia and the Caribbean. The London Maritime Arbitrators' Association estimated that in 2015, European lawyers were involved in fifty per cent of arbitrations dealt with by documents only: see Bar Council Brexit Working Group *International Arbitration*. March 2017. Paper Two. The General Council of the Bar, pp. 3-5.

¹⁰ Bar Council Brexit Working Group "Legal Services." June 2017. Paper One. The General Council of the Bar, 3.

¹¹ 2.1 per cent of practising solicitors in England and Wales in July 2017 were non-UK European lawyers. There were 661 Registered European Lawyers and 2,364 Exempt European Lawyers in July 2017: see Beqiraj, J. "FAQ: Professional Qualifications after Brexit." (October 2017). *British Institute of International and Comparative Law*, 3. These rose to 741 and 3,548 respectively in September 2019: see SRA, "Population of Solicitors in England and Wales." 2019. Available at <https://www.sra.org.uk/sra/how-we-work/reports/statistics/regulated-community-statistics/data/population_solicitors/> Accessed 2 November 2019.

¹² There were 2,731 solicitors practising in the other EU Member States, and thirty-six of the top UK law firms had at least one office in one of the twenty-seven other EU Member States in 2016: see The Law Society of England and Wales, "House of Lords call for evidence," *Internal Market Sub Committee Submission of evidence*. 5 October, 2016, 4.

¹³ M. Henssler, and Terry, L. S. "Lawyers without Frontiers - A View from Germany." *Dickinson Journal of International Law*, 19, 2 (2001): 269-299, p. 272.

¹⁴ The loss of freedom of movement may affect London's central role in international arbitrations and its potential to generate income from legal services across borders within

Until January 2021, lawyers can move without imposition of immigration controls between EU Member States on a permanent or temporary basis, but to date, there are only a few bilateral arrangements regarding future relationships under discussion (e.g. with Belgium, France and Germany¹⁶) and some Memoranda of Understanding outlining possibilities of co-operation in training (with Poland and Slovakia).

Although, in the short term, Brexit is likely to create a rise in demand for legal work, the legal sector expects to be negatively affected by the

the EU and EEA: see Bar Council Brexit Working Group, op. cit. *supra*, note 14, p. 3. Legal professionals fear that international firms will in future prefer to have recourse to EU courts, where they will be able to appeal decisions to the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). A small majority of respondents in a survey of just under a thousand private practitioners, arbitrators, in-house counsel, academics, experts and other stakeholders carried out by Queen Mary University London and White & Case on international arbitration seats felt that Brexit was unlikely to affect the choice of London as a seat for arbitration. However, a significant number (thirty-seven per cent) were less optimistic, and seventy per cent of those questioned speculated that Paris would be the seat to benefit the most from any negative impact of Brexit on London: Queen Mary University London and White & Case, "2018 International Arbitration Survey," 11.

¹⁵ In an attempt to preserve these rights, some Anglo-Welsh lawyers are registering with the Irish professional bodies. Barristers whose work currently involves work with the CJEU are registering with the Irish Bar in an attempt to preserve their rights of audience before the EU courts, or give privileged legal advice on EU competition law to clients: G. Peretz, "Make mine a Guinness: why I've joined the Irish Bar." *The Times*, 26 July, 2018. Available at <<https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/make-mine-a-guinness-why-i-ve-joined-the-irish-bar-rfwn2tsc>> Accessed 15 July 2019; since the referendum, 2,722 solicitors have registered in Ireland. Lawyers from England and Wales now represent one in every seven lawyers on the roll in Ireland as opposed to about 100 per year pre-2016: J. Hyde, "Brexit hitch as firms eye Ireland." *Law Society Gazette*, 20 May, 2019, 3.

¹⁶ S. Kahmann, "British young lawyers' practising rights: how will Brexit impact the future in Brussels and beyond?" *The UK Law Societies' Joint Brussels Office*, 30 October 2019. Available at <<https://www.lawsocieties.eu/viewpoint/british-young-lawyers-practising-rights-how-will-brexit-impact-the-future-in-brussels-and-beyond-by-siobhan-kahmann/6000484.article>> Accessed 24 November 2019.

transition and loss of freedom of movement, with turnover in growth expected to fall in the long term.¹⁷

1.2. Legal framework for the FOM of legal services in the EU

The four fundamental freedoms of movement were initially set out in the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community (TEC) - the Treaty of Rome - signed in 1957. They can now be found in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which, along with the Treaty on European Union, contain the provisions of the EEC Treaty as it was amended following the Treaty of Lisbon. The Single European Act of 1986 (SEA), which provided for the completion of the internal market and the movement without restriction of goods, services, capital and persons within the EU by 1992, furthered the implementation of the freedoms¹⁸ which form the basis upon which the freedom of movement of lawyers and legal services is built. The aim in constructing the common market had been to consolidate peace in post-war Europe and promote economic prosperity, this latter to be achieved by removing barriers to trade between Member States, such as tariffs and quotas, which are generally considered to raise the cost of traded goods and decrease efficiency and productivity. Despite the existence of the common market and jurisprudence on FOM from the European Court of Justice (ECJ), significant barriers to trade still existed within the EU in the 1980s. Since 1993, the single market has created a single territory, which today numbers more than 500 million inhabitants and over the years, internal borders and regulatory restrictions to the free movement of goods

¹⁷ The Law Society of England and Wales *Legal Services Sector Forecasts 2017-2025*. (2018) Available at <<https://www.lawsociety.org.uk/support-services/research-trends/legal-services-sector-forecasts/>> Accessed 24 June 2019, pp. 4 and 22.

¹⁸ Article 13 Single European Act *OJ L 169, 29.6.1987*, now enshrined in Art 26 TFEU: 'The Community shall adopt measures with the aim of progressively establishing the internal market over a period expiring on 31 December 1992... The internal market shall comprise an area without internal frontiers in which the free movement of goods, persons, services and capital is ensured in accordance with the provisions of this Treaty.'

and services have been dismantled.¹⁹ At the same time, unrestricted movement of people throughout the territory has enabled the workforce to move freely to find employment and provide labour where there is a greater demand than supply, to pursue career choices in another member state, or to achieve family reunification. Initially viewed as factors of production, workers and their families are now considered citizens of the EU,²⁰ and are possessed of a range of rights in the host member state based on EU law. Like workers, the self-employed also enjoy free movement rights: the right to provide services in another member state and the right to establish themselves, and the right to settle their families with them. These free movement provisions enable lawyers to practice across borders within the EU.

The principle EU Treaty provisions regarding freedom of movement are found in Articles 45, 49 and 56 of the TFEU (ex Articles 39, 43 and 49 TEC). These articles provide for the freedom of movement of workers, the freedom of establishment in another EU member state and the free movement of services across borders respectively. Initially, according to former ECJ Judge Mancini, ‘Community Law did not purport to have an impact on internal rules governing individual employment relationships... except in so far as was necessary to do so in order to eliminate the obstacles which hindered the integration of workers coming from other Member States,’ but the ECJ has progressively taken a leading role in defining and confirming the FOM rights of workers ‘extend[ing] the jurisdiction of the Community to make up for the set-backs ... suffered at the decision-making level at the hands of the Member States.’ Migrant workers are not now

¹⁹ Jan in 't Veld, “The economic benefits of the EU Single Market in goods and services,” *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 41, 5(2019): 803-818, 803.

²⁰ Art 20 TFEU.

required to comply with the hurdles which confronted them in the past, and the Court's interpretation of the rules has literally been 'emancipatory'.²¹

Article 45 TFEU lays out the framework for the free movement of workers, and states that their freedom of movement '... shall entail the abolition of any discrimination based on nationality between workers of the Member States as regards employment, remuneration and other conditions of work and employment.'²² No definition of what constitutes a worker was or is provided in the Treaties or in EU legislation (other than in contrast to the freedom to pursue self-employed activities and the freedom to provide services expressed in Articles 49 and 56), a situation which could risk leading to inconsistency in application.²³ The task therefore fell to the Court of Justice to develop a definition via case law, a role which it adopted resolutely from an early juncture, in order to avoid Member States 'modify[ing] the meaning of the concept of "migrant worker"' and eliminating 'at will the protection afforded by the Treaty to certain categories of person.'²⁴ In the words of Judge Mancini 'the Court conferred on itself what we might describe as a hermeneutic monopoly for the purpose of counteracting the unequal and discriminatory application of the rules on freedom of movement,'²⁵ and thus 'claimed ultimate authority to define its meaning and scope.'²⁶ The ECJ has crafted a wide and inclusive definition of worker status, and this is now found in *Lawrie-Blum*. The essential feature of an employment relationship is found to be satisfied if

²¹ Mancini, G *Democracy and Constitutionalism in the European Union*, (Hart Publishing 2000): 100, 127.

²² Art 45 (2) TFEU.

²³ See reflection by Kountouris: 'Some provisions, especially in secondary instruments regulating working conditions, appear to reserve the role of defining terms such as "employee" or "contract of employment or employment relationship" exclusively to national law.' N. Kountouris, N., "The concept of 'worker' in European Labour Law – Fragmentation, Autonomy, and Scope," *Industrial Law Journal*, 47, 2, (2018): 193.

²⁴ *Hoekstra v Bestuur der Bedrijfsvereniging voor Detailhandel en Ambachten* (Case 75/63) [1964] ECR 177, para 1.

²⁵ Mancini, *Democracy and Constitutionalism in the European Union*, 124.

²⁶ P. Craig, and de Búrca, G *EU Law*, (6th edition, OUP, 2015): 749.

‘for a certain period of time a person performs services for and under the direction of another person in return for which he receives remuneration.’²⁷ This combines a ‘subordination’ requirement and a ‘remuneration requirement’ (which the ECJ sees in the broadest sense, including remuneration via benefits in kind and subsidies from public funds²⁸), and builds on the foundation provided by *Levin* in 1982, that the ‘rules cover only the pursuit of effective and genuine activities, to the exclusion of activities on such a small scale as to be regarded as purely marginal and ancillary.’²⁹ EU migrant salaried lawyers, even engaged on part-time contracts, are therefore entitled to equal treatment alongside workers in the host state. In contrast, ‘any activity which a person performs outside a relationship of subordination must be classified as an activity pursued in a self-employed capacity,’³⁰ which is protected by different FOM provisions.

The right to freedom of establishment is contained in Article 49 TFEU, which allows nationals of Member States to ‘take up and pursue activities as self-employed persons’ and to set up firms ‘under the conditions laid down for [their] own nationals’. Discrimination against them on grounds of nationality is prohibited and they are granted the possibility to be engaged in the economic activity of their host state in a durable manner and, as expressed in *Gebhard*, ‘pursue professional activity on a stable and continuous basis in another Member State’.³¹ In *Reyners* in 1974, the ECJ affirmed the right of self-employed migrants to establish themselves, confirming the principle of non-discrimination, and asserted this as directly effective, even though the implementing measures at Community or national levels may not be fully in

²⁷ *Lawrie-Blum v Land Baden-Württemberg* (Case C66/85) [1985] ECR 02121, para 16.

²⁸ Kountouris, “The concept of ‘worker’ in European Labour Law – Fragmentation, Autonomy, and Scope,” 199.

²⁹ *Levin v Staatssecretaris van Justitie* (Case 53/81) [1982] ECR 1035, para 17.

³⁰ *Jany* (Case C-268/99) [2001] ECR I-8615, para 34.

³¹ *Gebhard v Consiglio dell’Ordine degli Avvocati e Procurati di Milano* (Case C-55/94) [1995] ECR I-4165, para 25. *Gebhard* concerned a German lawyer who set up his own chambers in Italy.

place.³² This freedom of establishment extends also to legal persons, defined in Article 54, thus to law firms, and these may additionally set up subsidiaries in another Member State as well.³³ Law firms have increasingly availed themselves of this opportunity to extend the reach of their business into other EU Member States.

The initial focus of the European economy was on trade in goods when the internal market was established, but services have become increasingly important and now constitute over 70% of the European economy.³⁴ The freedom to provide services is laid out in Article 56 TFEU, which prohibits ‘restrictions on the freedom to provide services within the Union ... in respect of nationals of Member States who are established in a Member State other than that of the person for whom the services are intended.’ Article 57 TFEU defines services as activities that are ‘normally provided for remuneration’ and ‘not governed by the provisions relating to the freedom of movement for goods, capital and persons’, highlighting ‘the professions’ as a category of services. It stipulates specifically that ‘the person providing a service may ... temporarily pursue his activity in the Member State where the service is provided, under the same conditions as are imposed by that state on its own nationals. These articles provide the basis for lawyers to work across borders on a temporary basis. The fact that a lawyer is providing services on a temporary basis rather than establishing him or herself does not prevent him or her from equipping him or herself with ‘some form of infrastructure in the host Member State (including an office, chambers or consulting rooms) ... for the purpose of performing the services in question,’³⁵ nor for providing those services regularly or for a sustained

³² *Reyners v Belgium* (Case 2/74) [1974] ECR 631, paras 24-30.

³³ A. Cuyvers, “Freedom of establishment and the freedom to provide services in the EU” in *East African Community Law* eds. Ugirashebuja, E., Ruhangisa, J.E., Ottervanger, T. and Cuyvers, A. (Leiden. Brill Nijhoff, 2017): 391.

³⁴ *Ibid*, 376.

³⁵ *Gebhard v Consiglio dell’Ordine degli Avvocati e Procurati di Milano* (Case C-55/94) [1995] ECR I-4165, para 22.

period of time.³⁶ Article 56 only applies where a cross-border element is concerned, but both service provider and recipient may rely on this provision.³⁷ Cuyvers explains the breadth of the possibilities available under the FOM of legal services:

‘Four possible cross-border scenarios can be envisioned. Firstly, the service provider may travel to another Member State to provide a service. Secondly... service recipients may travel to another Member State to receive a service. Thirdly, the service itself may cross a border, for example via the internet. Fourthly, the service provider and the service recipient may travel together to another Member State, for an example with an Irish consultant joining his Irish client on a business trip to Malta.’³⁸

Article 53 TFEU provides for the issuing of directives to bring about the mutual recognition of diplomas, certificates and other evidence of formal qualifications.

The provisions contained in these Articles are fleshed out by a number of Directives, which are then translated into the domestic law of the Member States by local laws and regulations. The freedoms extend to the legal professions, regardless of the ‘relatively deep differences’ in entry requirements and ‘the varying structures, customs, cultures, and legal traditions’ of individual Member States across the EU, which have caused

³⁶ ‘It follows that the mere fact that a business established in one Member State supplies identical or similar services with a greater or lesser degree of frequency or regularity in a second Member State, without having an infrastructure there enabling it to pursue a professional activity there on a stable and continuous basis and, from the infrastructure, to hold itself out to, amongst others, nationals of the second Member State, is not sufficient for it to be regarded as established in the second Member State.’ *Schnitzer* (Case C-215/01) [2003] ECR I-14847, para 32.

³⁷ *Luisi and Carbone* (Cases 286/82 and 26/83) [1984] ECR 377.

³⁸ Cuyvers, “Freedom of establishment and the freedom to provide services in the EU,” 384.

obstacles to the FOM of lawyers and legal services in the past.³⁹ An abundance of case law in the 1970s and 1980s is testimony to the initial reticence to apply the general liberalising provisions on the freedom to provide services and the freedom of establishment to the legal professions.⁴⁰ However, the only exception to the freedom of movement rights specifically made in the EEC Treaty relates to employment within public services and activities connected with the exercise of official authority, which does not affect the majority of work carried out by lawyers,⁴¹ and, in 1974, *Reyners* confirmed that lawyers are not caught by the exception.⁴² The Directives which refer specifically to the legal professions now confirm without doubt that lawyers also are entitled to benefit from the freedoms.

The following provisions outline the freedom of movement rights of self-employed EU lawyers across the EU: i) the Lawyers' Services Directive,⁴³ which grants lawyers the right to provide legal services under their home state professional title throughout the EU on a temporary basis; ii) the Professional Qualifications Directive,⁴⁴ which grants the right to practice under the same conditions as nationals of the host state, thanks to the mutual recognition of academic and vocational qualifications; and iii) the

³⁹ J. Lonbay, "Assessing the European Market for Legal Services: Developments in the Free Movement of Lawyers in the European Union." *Fordham International Law Journal*. 33, (2010): 1640.

⁴⁰ V. Višinskis, Žalėnienė, I. and Tvaronavičienė, A.. "Legal environment within the EU: free movement of lawyers and legal services," *Business: Theory and Practice*. 10, 1 (2009): 30-37, 31.

⁴¹ See Articles 45 and 51, TFEU.

⁴² *Reyners v Belgium* (Case 2/74) [1974] ECR 631, para 52.

⁴³ Directive 77/249/EEC of 22 March 1977 to facilitate the effective exercise by lawyers of freedom to provide services, *OJ L 78*, 26.3.1977, p. 17–18.

⁴⁴ Directive 2005/36/EC on the recognition of professional qualifications *OJ L 255*, 30.9.2005, p. 22–142, recently amended by Directive 2013/55/EU amending Directive 2005/36/EC on the on the recognition of professional qualifications and Regulation (EU) No 1024/2012 on administrative cooperation through the Internal Market Information System ('the IMI Regulation') Text with EEA relevance *OJ L 354*, 28.12.2013, p. 132–170. Directive 2005/36/EC consolidates and replaces Directives 89/48/EEC, 92/51/EEC and 99/42/EC.

Lawyers' Establishment Directive,⁴⁵ which grants the right to set up a practice providing legal services in another Member State on a permanent basis.

For lawyers not establishing themselves on a permanent basis outside of their home state, but wishing to offer services to clients from another Member State, the Lawyers' Services Directive, implemented in 1977, provides the framework for EU qualified lawyers to carry out cross-border legal services, using their home professional title. This is the first of the above directives to be passed specifically referring to the activity of lawyers, who had been meeting restrictions to their attempts to exercise free movement rights. It followed the decision in *Reyners*,⁴⁶ which had served to confirm that legal services did not fall within the official authority exception of Article 45 TEC (now Article 51 TFEU). There is no provision in the Directive for the mutual recognition of diplomas or harmonisation of legal training – these were sensitive areas at the time – it but stipulates that host Member States must recognise as lawyers those persons practising the professions in the various Member States.⁴⁷ The Directive states that there is no need to register with the professional body in the host state, although lawyers are expected to observe the rules of professional conduct of the host state,⁴⁸ and may be required 'to work in conjunction with a lawyer who practises before the judicial authority' of the host state.⁴⁹

The Lawyers' Services Directive outlined the framework within which lawyers could practise cross-border on a temporary basis, but did not regulate for those wishing to establish themselves permanently in another Member State, for which more 'detailed measures' would be necessary. A

⁴⁵ Directive 98/5/EC to facilitate practice of the profession of lawyer on a permanent basis in a Member State other than that in which the qualification was obtained *OJ L 77, 14.3.1998, p. 36–43.*

⁴⁶ *Reyners v Belgium* (Case 2/74) [1974] ECR 631.

⁴⁷ Preamble, Directive 77/249/EEC.

⁴⁸ Article 4(2) Directive 77/249/EEC.

⁴⁹ Article 5 Directive 77/249/EEC.

step in this direction was made through the first Diploma Directive of 1989, replaced now by the Professional Qualifications Directive (PQD).⁵⁰ The mutual recognition of qualifications was elaborated through case law of the ECJ at first but was nonetheless intended to be reinforced by the development of directives, as can be seen from the TEC.⁵¹ A sectoral approach was adopted initially, focussing on medical and health-related professions, but harmonisation of minimal standards of professions across Member States posed challenges, and a mutual recognition approach based on trust was preferred and adopted with the 1989 Diploma directive. For client protection, some professions, such as law, are highly regulated in all EU Member States, and the differences in education and training vary considerably from state to state. The Diploma Directives provide for the mutual recognition of higher education diplomas in general and aim to remove barriers facing EU nationals to pursue their careers in a Member State other than the one in which they studied and qualified. They grant automatic recognition of professional qualifications for those professions with harmonised minimum training conditions (nurses, midwives, doctors, dental practitioners, pharmacists, architects and veterinary surgeons).⁵² More generally, they specify that professional qualifications must be recognised by Member States, who must allow beneficiaries to gain access in another Member State to the same profession as that for which they are qualified in their home Member State, and to pursue that profession under the same conditions as its nationals.⁵³ Specific mention is made in the Directive of recognition of professional qualifications and training for lawyers.⁵⁴ The PQD sets out five levels of qualification and diploma that can

⁵⁰ Directive 2005/36/EC on the recognition of professional qualifications, which replaced Directive 89/48 on a General System for the Recognition of Higher Education Diplomas Awarded on Completion of Professional Education and Training of at Least Three Years' Duration O.J 19/16; amended by Directive 2013/55/EU.

⁵¹ Article 53 TFEU (ex Article 47 TEC).

⁵² L. Kortese, "Exploring professional recognition in the EU: a legal perspective," *Journal of International Mobility*, 1, 4, (2016): 43-58, p. 46.

⁵³ Art 4 (1), Directive 2005/36.

⁵⁴ Para 42, Directive 2005/36.

be recognised ranging from primary to higher education,⁵⁵ based on the principle of mutual recognition. It allows compensation measures to be imposed if the applicant's qualifications are not considered to be equivalent to those required by the host state, and can require the sitting of an aptitude test or completion of an adaptation period in order to attain the required standard.⁵⁶ This Directive takes its inspiration from the ruling in *Vlassopoulo*.⁵⁷ In this case, the European Court acknowledged that Member States may lay down specific requirements for access to the Bar, but must not hinder non-nationals in their right of establishment and must take into account previously acquired qualifications. Qualifications must be compared with national requirements to ascertain whether they are equivalent, and if they are, they must be accepted as such. If the qualifications are not found to be equivalent, then the host state has the right to require the applicant to bring forward evidence of any additional knowledge, aptitude and experience s/he may have acquired.⁵⁸ In the case of non-regulated professions, the principles outlined by the ECJ in *Vlassopoulou* also appear to apply,⁵⁹ following Article 49 TFEU.

This Directive is now somewhat less significant for lawyers, due to the effects of the Lawyers' Establishment Directive of 1998, which specifically allows lawyers to set up in another Member State, but it marks a significant step in the path to freedom of establishment.

Lawyers tend to have self-employed status, being typically members of the self-employed Bar, sole practitioners or partners in a law firm and the

⁵⁵ Article 11, Directive 2005/36/EC.

⁵⁶ Article 14, Directive 2005/36/EC.

⁵⁷ *Vlassopoulou* concerned a Greek lawyer who had practised at the Athens Bar. She subsequently gained a doctorate in law in Germany, and worked at the German Bar under the supervision of German lawyers. Her application to the German Bar was turned down on the grounds that she had not followed the traditional route to the Bar of German lawyers.

⁵⁸ *Vlassopoulou v Ministerium für Justiz, Bundes und Europaangelegenheiten Baden-Württemberg* (Case C-340/89) [1991] ECR2357.

⁵⁹ Craig and de Búrca, *EU Law*, 846.

Lawyers' Establishment Directive allows EU nationals who are members of a legal profession in one of the Member States to set up a practice in another Member State.⁶⁰ Self-employed status is held by the ECJ to consist of an economic activity carried out by a person 'outside any relationship of subordination concerning the choice of that activity, working conditions and conditions of remuneration; under that person's own responsibility; and in return for remuneration paid to that person directly and in full.'⁶¹ The Directive addresses issues such as the use of professional title, registration requirements and rules of professional conduct. It effectively provides two different means of accessing a Member State's legal market. Firstly, an EU lawyer moving to another Member State may practise, in all areas of law, in the host state under the professional title obtained in his or her home state, subject to some potential restrictions, where it may be necessary to practise alongside a lawyer holding a qualification from the host state.⁶² For example, pre-Brexit an English solicitor was able to open a practice in France and, using their home professional title of solicitor, give legal advice on most areas of English law, French law, European law and international law. The second possibility is to apply for admission to the local law society or Bar Association of the host state after three years of effective and uninterrupted practice in the host state, essentially becoming a host state lawyer, without the need to sit the formal examinations passed by host state lawyers.⁶³ In this case, there will be no restrictions on areas of practice,⁶⁴ which has caused concern that migrant lawyers may not have adequate knowledge of the law of their new host state. However, an element of control exists in so far as lawyers are bound by codes of conduct, of both home and host state, and will potentially face disciplinary action by their professional bodies if

⁶⁰ It should be noted that the Establishment Directive applies to both salaried and self-employed lawyers: Article 1 (3), Directive 98/5/EC.

⁶¹ As defined in *Jany* (Case C-268/99) [2001] ECR I-8615, para 71.

⁶² Article 4, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁶³ Articles 10 and 14, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁶⁴ In M. Schelkens, "The Freedom of Establishment of Lawyers in the European Union," *Jura Falconis*, 51, 2, (2014-15): 214-241, 235.

they accept instructions outside their range of competence.⁶⁵ This issue was raised by Luxembourg, but the court ruled:

It would therefore seem that the Community legislature, with a view to making it easier for a particular class of migrant lawyers to exercise the fundamental freedom of establishment, has chosen, in preference to a system of *a priori* testing of qualification in the national law of the host Member State, a plan of action combining consumer information, restrictions on the extent to which or the detailed rules under which certain activities of the profession may be practised, a number of applicable rules of professional conduct, compulsory insurance, as well as a system of discipline involving both the competent authorities of the home Member State and the host State. The legislature has not abolished the requirement that the lawyer concerned should know the national law applicable in the cases he handles, but has simply released him from the obligation to prove that knowledge in advance. It has thus allowed, in some circumstances, gradual assimilation of knowledge through practice, that assimilation being made easier by experience of other laws gained in the home Member State. It was also able to take account of the dissuasive effect of the system of discipline and the rules of professional liability.⁶⁶

More recent case law demonstrates that trainee lawyers who have not yet completed their training also possess free movement rights with regard to their qualification process, which must be respected. The case of

⁶⁵ See Council of Bars and Law Societies of Europe Code of Conduct, para 3.1.3: 'A lawyer shall not handle a matter which the lawyer knows or ought to know he or she is not competent to handle, without cooperating with a lawyer who is competent to handle it.' CCBE, "Charter of core principles of the European legal profession & Code of conduct for European lawyers." Available at <https://www.ccbe.eu/fileadmin/speciality_distribution/public/documents/DEONTOLOGY/DEON_CoC/EN_DEON_CoC.pdf> Accessed 11 June 2020.

⁶⁶ *Luxembourg v European Parliament* (Case C-168/98) [2000] ECR I-09131, para 43.

*Morgenbesser*⁶⁷ concerns a French national, holding a French *maîtrise en droit* but not qualified as an *avocate* in France. She had carried out a period of training in Italy, and wished to apply for enrolment on the register of trainee lawyers in order to complete qualification as a lawyer in Italy. Her application was refused on the grounds that she did not hold an Italian Law degree, which was a prerequisite for registration. *Morgenbesser* challenged this decision. Neither the QPD nor the Lawyers' Establishment Directive applied to *Morgenbesser*, as the traineeship was not a 'regulated profession' and she was not a fully qualified lawyer in France. However, the ECJ held that national authorities must take into consideration the professional qualifications of an applicant and any professional experience regardless of where it was acquired, and compare them to those required in the host state. If the applicant's qualifications were considered equivalent, then they had to be accepted. If not, the host state could require the applicant to demonstrate that they had acquired the knowledge, skills and qualifications deemed lacking either in the host State or elsewhere, or to acquire the missing elements in order to be registered. This effectively extends rights to those still training to become lawyers, who may potentially 'mix and match' their training and qualification process (subject to the requirements of the host state in respect of knowledge of, for example, domestic law), and may have 'a highly deregulatory effect on accredited access routes to the professions.'⁶⁸

These Directives and case law demonstrate that, pre-Brexit, EU lawyers could set up independently or as members of a set of chambers in the UK, work for an Anglo-Welsh law firm, for an international law firm or as an in-house lawyer in the UK, or provide cross-border legal services on a

⁶⁷ *Morgenbesser v Consiglio dell'Ordine degli avvocati di Genova* (Case C-313/01) [2003] ECR I-13467.

⁶⁸ J. Lonbay, "Assessing the European Market for Legal Services: Developments in the Free Movement of Lawyers in the European Union." *Fordham International Law Journal*. 33, (2010): 1629-1669, 1655.

temporary basis, and UK lawyers could do the same in another EU Member State.

1.3. Regulation of FOM of legal services in the UK

The UK implemented the EU legislation on freedom of movement of legal services in England and Wales and Northern Ireland via the European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000, and in Scotland via the European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) (Scotland) Regulations 2000. These domestic regulations implemented the Lawyers' Establishment Directive. The Lawyers' Services Directive was implemented across the UK in domestic legislation by the European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order (S.I. 1978 no. 1910). These regulations and the statutory instrument led to the creation of the status of Registered European Lawyers (REL), for lawyers practising in the UK on a permanent basis and Exempt European Lawyers (EEL) practising in the UK on a temporary basis. In addition, the Legal Services Act 2007, which regulates who may provide reserved legal activities (such as the right of audience, the conduct of litigation, reserved instrument activities, probate activities, notarial activities and the administration of oaths), applied to both UK and EU lawyers practising in England and Wales.

1.3.1. Registered European Lawyers

There were around seven hundred RELs who operated on a permanent basis in England and Wales in 2018.⁶⁹ This signified 'maintaining a regular practice

⁶⁹ J. Hyde, "No-deal Brexit would halt European lawyer scheme overnight, says SRA," *Law Society Gazette*, 12 October 2018. Available at <<https://www.lawgazette.co.uk/no-deal-brexit-would-halt-european-lawyer-scheme-overnight-says-sra/5067954.article>>. Accessed 15 July 2019. There has been a steady increase in RELs. In 2008, there were in the region of 325 RELs in the UK (CCBE, "CCBE Lawyers' Statistics 2008". Available at https://www.ccbe.eu/fileadmin/speciality_distribution/public/documents/Statistics/EN_ST_AT_2008_Number_of_lawyers_in_European_countries.pdf> Accessed 17 July 2019), and this had risen to 581 RELs registered as solicitors and 12 registered as barristers in 2016 (Bar Council of England and Wales, "Response to the question from the House of Commons

as a lawyer in the UK⁷⁰, e.g. working there two days a week or more.⁷¹ They had to practise under their home professional titles⁷² in order to ensure transparency for clients as to their legal training,⁷³ and could advise on the law of their home member state, on EU law, international law and on the law of the host member state.⁷⁴ They were entitled to provide the full range of legal services, including the right to provide reserved legal services and to work as sole practitioners. It may seem somewhat alarming that lawyers can carry out under their home country professional title all the activities of lawyers in the host State with no training in host state law, but this possibility already existed in some Member States before the Lawyers' Establishment Directive was adopted, and the aim of the Directive was to eliminate unfair distortions of competition between lawyers in the European Union.⁷⁵ For certain activities, there was an obligation to work in conjunction with a solicitor or barrister who has qualified in England and Wales, since some areas of practice, such as representing a client in court, completing land transfers and probate court forms, are reserved to lawyers

Justice Select Committee: What is the value that EU lawyers bring to this country, in particular to the City of London?" 20 July, 2016. Available at <<https://www.parliament.uk/documents/commons-committees/Justice/Further-evidence-from-Bar-Council-of-England-and-Wales-on-legal-services-regulation.pdf>> Accessed 17 July 2019). In 2010, it was estimated that just under 4,000 EU lawyers were registered outside their home jurisdiction (Lonbay, "Assessing the European Market for Legal Services: Developments in the Free Movement of Lawyers in the European Union," 1642).

⁷⁰ Regulation 2.3(a)(iv), Solicitors' Regulation Authority (SRA) Practising Regulations 2011; SRA 2018, p.7; Bar Standards Board 2019, Section D.

⁷¹ SRA, SRA Renewals Registered European Lawyers (REL) Guide October 2018. Available at <<https://www.sra.org.uk/globalassets/documents/mysra/registered-european-lawyers-guide.pdf?version=4a1abe>> Accessed 2 November 2019, p. 3.

⁷² Ss.6-7, The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000; Article 2, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁷³ Para (9) Directive 98/5/EC.

⁷⁴ S. 6, The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000; Article 5, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁷⁵ Katsirea, I. and Ruff, A. 'Free movement of law students and lawyers in the EU: a comparison of English, German and Greek legislation' 12 (3) *International Journal of the Legal Profession* (2005), pp. 367-406, p. 387.

with a home professional title,⁷⁶ and this was perceived as adding an element of protection for the consumer.

EU-qualified lawyers had to maintain their practising status/certificate in their home state in order to be able to register as a REL in the UK,⁷⁷ and then, in England and Wales, register with one of the lawyers' professional bodies, the Law Society of England and Wales or the Inns of Court and the General Council of the Bar of England and Wales.⁷⁸ They were then subject to the same Code of Conduct as home qualified solicitors and barristers.⁷⁹ They were thus subject to two professional codes of conduct, the code of their home state and their host state, in respect of all activities carried out in the host state, a phenomenon known as 'double deontology'.⁸⁰

The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000, enabled a REL to be admitted to practise as a barrister or a solicitor after three years of regular and effective practice in England and Wales.⁸¹ It was not mandatory to apply for registration as a solicitor or barrister, and a REL could practice in the UK under his or her home title for as long as he or she wished. However, if an EU lawyer wished to become a solicitor or a barrister in less than three years, he or she had the option to qualify by sitting an aptitude test.⁸²

⁷⁶ S. 6, 11-14 The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000; Article 5, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁷⁷ S. 16(2), The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000; Article 3(2) and para (12), Directive 98/5/EC.

⁷⁸ S. 4 and Appendix 2, The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000.

⁷⁹ S. 25, The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000. Article 6, Directive 98/5/EC.

⁸⁰ CCBE, "Guidelines for Bars and Law Societies on Free Movement of Lawyers within the European Union." 2016. Available at <https://www.ccbe.eu/fileadmin/speciality_distribution/public/documents/EU_LAWYERS/EUL_Guides___recommendations/EN_FML_2016_Guide.pdf> Accessed 25 July 2019, p. 9.

⁸¹ S. 29, The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000; Article 10(3), Directive 98/5/EC.

⁸² S. 29(1), The European Communities (Lawyer's Practice) Regulations 2000. Para (3), Directive 98/5/EC; Article 14, Professional Qualifications Directive 2005/36 EC.

From 1 January 2021, the REL regime has come to an end and RELs have lost their associated practice rights in England and Wales (except in relation to a defined group of Swiss lawyers since separate arrangements have been made between the UK government and Switzerland).

1.3.2. Exempt European Lawyers

EU legislation offered another possibility for the free movement of legal services within the EU, enabling lawyers to practise in another member state on a more temporary basis. This was represented in the UK under the status of the Exempt European Lawyer (EEL). If an EU lawyer did not intend to practise in the UK on a permanent basis, he or she was not eligible to register as a REL.

EELs were principally EEA/EU lawyers based entirely in offices outside of England and Wales. They were lawyers who were nationals of an EU member state, established in another member state and entitled to practise as a member of a profession specified in the Lawyers Establishment Directive. They were allowed to provide legal services in the UK which were otherwise reserved to UK lawyers, on an occasional basis, under the Lawyers Services Directive.⁸³ To be approved as an EEL, the SRA or BSB required sight of a certificate of attestation from the home Bar Association or Law Society⁸⁴ but would charge no fee as, unlike RELs, there was no registration necessary. In England and Wales, restricted practice areas included exercise of rights of audience in courts, conduct of litigation, reserved instrument activities, probate and notarial activities, and administration of oaths. In order to represent clients in legal proceedings before the UK courts, an EEL had work in conjunction with a lawyer who practiced before the judicial

⁸³ Implemented in the UK in s. 4, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978.

⁸⁴ Ss. 12-14, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978; Article 7, Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

authority in question,⁸⁵ i.e. an Anglo-Welsh qualified lawyer. EELs were prohibited from carrying out reserved activities such as drawing up formal documents for obtaining title to administer estates of deceased persons, and the drafting of formal documents creating or transferring interests in land, as only certain groups of lawyers, regulated under the Legal Services Act 2007, may do this.⁸⁶ EELs practised under their home titles,⁸⁷ and, for out of court activities, were bound by the Code of professional conduct of their home state,⁸⁸ except where representing a client in legal proceedings, where he or she was bound by the Code of Conduct of the host state.⁸⁹ In the event of a conflict between home and host State professional rules, the host Member State's professional rules prevailed.⁹⁰

These EU directives also enabled UK lawyers to work in the EU. UK lawyers were able to attend to the cross-border needs of businesses and individuals from satellite offices in the EU and on a fly-in fly-out basis from their UK office, and this was a daily business practice for many firms.⁹¹

From 1 January 2021, the fly in/fly out practice rights of EU lawyers (with the exception of Swiss lawyers), have come to an end, and EELs may no longer be owners or managers of a law firm in England and Wales.

⁸⁵ S. 5 European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978. Article 5 Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

⁸⁶ S. 9, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978. Article 1, Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

⁸⁷ S. 11, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978. Article 3, Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

⁸⁸ Ss. 15-16, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978. Article 4(4), Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

⁸⁹ S. 15, European Communities (Services of Lawyers) Order 1978. Article 4(2), Lawyers Services Directive 77/249.

⁹⁰ CCBE, "Guidelines for Bars and Law Societies on Free Movement of Lawyers within the European Union." 9.

⁹¹ APPG, *The effect of Brexit on legal services*, 6.

1.3.3. Registered Foreign Lawyers

There are similar possibilities for non-EU nationals wishing to practise in the UK. They may register with the regulatory bodies as Registered Foreign Lawyers (RFL) on condition that the profession of which they are a member is approved by the Law Society as appropriately regulated, and the Law Society may impose such conditions as it considers fit.⁹² This will be dependent on bilateral agreements between the states. If approved by the Law Society, they may even practise without registering unless they are to be partners or managers in a law firm, but regardless of status – registered or not – they may not appear in open court under any circumstances, may not carry out reserved activities nor court-based immigration work unless supervised by an Anglo-Welsh qualified lawyer,⁹³ and will be regulated by the SRA or BSB. There are therefore some differences between the status of RFLs and RELs which may, in reality, be quite significant.

From 1 January 2021, this is the regime which will apply to EU lawyers wishing to practice in England and Wales.

⁹² Schedule 14, Courts and Legal Services Act 1990.

⁹³ SRA, “Ethics Guidance: RFLs and practice with solicitors in England and Wales,” (2010). Available at <<http://www.sra.org.uk/solicitors/code-of-conduct/guidance/rfls-and-practice-with-solicitors-in-england-and-wales.page.page>> Accessed 25 July 2019.

PART TWO:

**THE FREE MOVEMENT OF LEGAL SERVICES IN THE EAST AFRICAN
COMMUNITY**

The East African Community is often considered to be the most successful of the regional integration schemes on the African continent, having received the highest score for regional integration amongst the RECs on the Regional Integration Index of the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa.⁹⁴ Its integration process roadmap includes a customs union, a common market, monetary union and ultimately a political federation.⁹⁵

However, although it may be one of the best-performing integration initiatives on the African continent, there is reason to wonder whether the free movement of legal services will ever be realised.

In order to ascertain the potential implementation of the free movement of legal services, it is necessary to evaluate what the free movement of legal services in the EAC means, what the commitments of the Partner States are, how free movement of legal services is supposed to function and what the challenges are which need to be overcome in order for this to be achieved. This will be done through the prism of the Rwandan legislation.

2. Legal framework for the FOM legal services in the EAC

One of the specific objectives of the EAC Common Market, in order to accelerate economic growth and development of the Partner States, was to attain the free movement of goods, persons and labour, the rights of establishment and residence and the free movement of services and capital

⁹⁴ United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA), "Africa Regional Integration Index Report 2016." Available at <[https://www.uneca.org/sites/default/files/Publication Files/arii-report2016_en_web.pdf](https://www.uneca.org/sites/default/files/Publication%20Files/arii-report2016_en_web.pdf)> Accessed 11 October 2019, p. 14.

⁹⁵ Preamble to the Treaty Establishing the East African Community, para 15.

in general.⁹⁶ Accordingly, the Partner States (Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania and Uganda of the EAC) have committed to liberalise the movement of services within the EAC, within their respective territories. Among the services they agreed to liberalise are legal services which were intended to enjoy full free movement rights within the community by the end of 2015.⁹⁷ This meant, for example, that a Rwandan lawyer should have been able to travel to provide legal advice or represent a client before a court in another EAC partner state.

This was to be implemented in four ways or Modes.⁹⁸ The first Mode relates to cross border supply, the supply of services from the territory of a Partner State into the territory of another Partner State, meaning that for example a Kenyan lawyer based in Kenya should be able to provide legal services or legal advice to Rwandan clients in Rwanda without either party leaving their territory, so that there is a cross-border supply of legal advice and services. The second Mode concerns consumption abroad: the supply of services in the territory of a Partner State to service consumers from another partner state. A Rwandan client in Uganda should be able to receive legal services without any kind of discrimination and should be treated in the same way as a Ugandan.⁹⁹ The third Mode concerns the commercial presence of the service supplier in the territory of another partner state: for example, a Rwandan law firm should be able to establish itself in Burundi and provide legal services for clients within the territory of Burundi. The fourth Mode concerns the presence of a natural person in a partner state, where self-

⁹⁶ Art. 4(2)(a) and Art. 16 Protocol on the Establishment of the East African Community Common Market (Common Market Protocol); Art. 104 East African Community Treaty 1999.

⁹⁷ East African Community Common Market Schedule of Commitments on the Progressive Liberalisation of Services Annex V, November 2009.

⁹⁸ See East African Community Common Market Schedule of Commitments on the Progressive Liberalisation of Services Annex V, p. 80.

⁹⁹ Art. 3 (2)(a) Common Market Protocol; Regulation 10(1) EAC Common Market (Right of Establishment) Regulations Annex III.

employed individual lawyers should be able to represent or assist their clients in the territory of another partner state.¹⁰⁰

The liberalisation was to be progressive.¹⁰¹ There are two main commitments: a standstill commitment, which means that, from the entry into force of the Common Market Protocol in 2010, it was agreed that no barriers to the free movement of services would be introduced. The second obligation from 2010 was that Partner States had to rollback, or remove, all barriers to the free movement of services.¹⁰² A principle of variable geometry, which ‘allows for progression in co-operation among a sub-group of members in a larger integration scheme in a variety of areas and at different speeds’, was built into the EAC Treaty,¹⁰³ allowing Partner States to integrate at their own pace. These conditions also applied to the right of establishment.¹⁰⁴ For example, when the Common Market Protocol was signed, of the four Modes, Burundi did not impose any restrictions on cross-border supply (Mode I) or consumption of legal services by citizens of other Partner States (Mode II). With regard to commercial presence, however, Burundi maintained that it was not bound to accept the establishment of foreign law firms in Burundi (Mode III). With regard to Mode IV, Burundi would only allow individual lawyers from other Partner States to come and present cases in Burundi subject to the EAC Common Market (Free Movement of Workers) Regulations.¹⁰⁵ Compliance with the (Free Movement of Workers) Regulations, which are Annexes to the Common

¹⁰⁰ These latter two Modes are regulated by the EAC Common Market (Right of Establishment) Regulations (Annex III).

¹⁰¹ K. Gasthorn, “Freedom of Establishment and the Freedom to provide Services in the EAC,” in *East African Community Law* eds Ugirashebuja, E., Ruhangisa, J.E., Ottervanger, T. and Cuyvers, A. (Leiden. Brill Nijhoff, 2017): 365-375, 372.

¹⁰² Art 16 (5) Common Market Protocol.

¹⁰³ Art 1 EAC Treaty 1999.

¹⁰⁴ Art 13 (5) Common Market Protocol.

¹⁰⁵ See the East African Community Common Market Schedule of Commitments on the Progressive Liberalisation of Services Annex V, p 80.

Market Protocol,¹⁰⁶ entails fulfilling a set of conditions which include requirements such as having a travel document or identity card, obtaining a work permit and special pass where necessary, being in possession of an employment contract, but benefitting from equal treatment with Burundian lawyers.¹⁰⁷

In contrast, Rwanda has, since 2010, had no restriction in market access or national treatment for Modes I to III. This means that free movement of legal services across borders, freedom for citizens from Partner States to consume legal services in Rwanda and freedom of establishment are authorised in Rwanda, but self-employed lawyers from Partner States are subject to the Schedule of the EAC Common Market (Free Movement of Workers) Regulations (Annex V), which indicates timelines for the liberalisation of a number of services, including legal services. Whatever the situation, Partner States agreed that by 2015 they should have removed all barriers to free movement of services and establishment. As far as the national treatment principle was concerned, with regard to discriminating against citizens of other Partner States and favouring nationals, which is specifically prohibited by the Common Market Protocol,¹⁰⁸ both Burundi and Rwanda committed to remove all barriers by 2010. Annex V of the EAC Common Market Schedule of Commitments on the Progressive Liberalisation of Services shows that Partner States have all committed to the same aims, which means that by now legal services should be moving freely in the EAC, since there was a commitment to remove barriers by 2015

¹⁰⁶ There are six Annexes: Annex I: Free Movement of Persons Regulations; Annex II: Free Movement of Workers Regulations; Annex III: Right of Establishment Regulations; Annex IV: Right of Residence Regulations; Annex V: Schedule of Commitments on the Progressive Liberalisation of Services; Annex VI: Schedule on the Removal of Restrictions on the Free Movement of Capital. The purpose of the Regulations is to implement the provisions of the Protocol and to ensure that there is uniformity among the Partner States in the implementation of the Article and that to the extent possible, the process is transparent, accountable, fair, predictable and consistent with the provisions of the Protocol.

¹⁰⁷ Regulations 5, 6 and 12, EAC Common Market (Free Movement of Workers) Regulations.

¹⁰⁸ Art 3(2) Common Market Protocol.

at the latest. However, this is not borne out by reality, when the free movement of services in the EAC is considered.

2.1. The long road to the Mutual Recognition Agreement

To foster the free movement of workers, including the self-employed such as lawyers, Partner States had to commit to mutual recognition of academic and professional qualifications awarded, experience obtained, requirements made, licences or certificates granted to individuals and to firms in other Partner States,¹⁰⁹ meaning that they committed, via the EAC Common Market Protocol, to recognise degree qualifications that citizens of the EAC obtained from the territories of other Partner States. This means that a lawyer obtaining a licence to practice in one partner state should have that licence recognised by another partner state.

Partner States also agreed to harmonise the curriculum of legal education, to review their examination systems, standards, certification of accreditation of secondary education, and training institutions, and this aim is expressed in Article 126 of the EAC Treaty of 1999:

In order to promote the achievement of the objectives of the Community as set out in Article 5 of this Treaty, the Partner States shall take steps to harmonise their legal training and certification; and shall encourage the standardisation of the judgements of courts within the Community.

This harmonisation is a long-term process and is still on-going.¹¹⁰ But, unlike the EU where an arsenal of directives have been adopted to regulate the free movement of legal services as described above, so far there are no additional equivalent legal texts in force enacted by EAC organs to achieve this. The EAC Cross-Border Legal Practice Bill 2014, which provides for the

¹⁰⁹ Art 11 and art 13(7), Common Market Protocol.

¹¹⁰ This is also echoed in Article 11(1)(b) Common Market Protocol.

conduct and regulation of cross-border legal practice and requires Partner States to take steps to harmonise training and certification, has still to enter into force.¹¹¹ The delayed entry into force of the EAC Cross Border Legal Practice Bill 2014 is just another obstacle added to the lengthy discussion on the adoption of a Mutual Recognition Agreement (MRA) – whereby the qualifications granted in the home state will be recognised in the host state and vice versa – for the implementation of the free movement of legal services.

However, neither the Common Market Protocol nor the Treaty establishing the EAC have any clear mention of a requirement for a signature of an MRA for the implementation of the free movement of legal services. Certain countries such as Rwanda and Kenya have pressed for free movement of legal services, meeting reticence from other Partner States, who have refused to proceed without an MRA.¹¹² Partner States have now drafted EAC Common Market (Mutual Recognition of Academic and Professional Qualifications) Regulations 2011, which stipulate the process by which Common Market Protocol Article 11 on mutual recognition of academic and professional qualifications and experience would be implemented. Negotiating and signing of the MRA under Annex VI was to be undertaken by ‘Competent Authorities’, that is to say a Ministry, a department, office, institution or agency designated by a Partner State to carry out the functions required under these regulations. As a result, a process of negotiating mutual recognition agreements has commenced, which has been time-consuming and frustrating. Although the MRA is now drafted and should in principle allow advocates who meet the requirements set out in the mutual recognition agreement to make an application to a competent authority in a Partner State within which they do not practice and to be recognised as

¹¹¹ There does not appear to be significant progress on the ground in this area, and the EAC Cross Border Legal Practice Bill 2014 remains a project rather than a reality.

¹¹² K. Agutamba, “Is cross-border legal practice really possible?” *The New Times*. 20 April, 2015. Available at <<https://www.newtimes.co.rw/section/read/188004>> Accessed 31 October 2019.

practising advocates of that Partner State, this has yet to be agreed by the EAC Council of Ministers and later by the Summit.¹¹³

Via the Common Market Protocol, Partner States also agreed to treat legal services and lawyers from other Partner States no less favourably than their own lawyers.¹¹⁴ This means that if there are conditions to be met, both citizens from other EAC states and the nationals of the host country would be required to comply with them. However, the EAC Common Market Protocol went one step further, stating that it might be necessary for EAC states to accord different treatment to service suppliers from Partner States, if providing identical treatment to service suppliers from Partner States had the effect of placing them at a disadvantage in terms of competition with service suppliers of the home state.¹¹⁵

The ongoing discussions for the adoption of an MRA in the EAC to operationalise the FOM of legal services is not new. The EU went through a similar path. However, the history of the EU bears testament to the fact that the Commission and the ECJ have played a paramount role in building the European legal framework. Given the slowness of relevant EAC organs to adopt the EAC Cross Border Legal Practice Bill, 2014 and the MRA, the East African Court of Justice could play a salutary role through a pro-integration interpretation by following in the footsteps of its European counterpart, if

¹¹³ Despite support for the MRA from Ministries of Justice and Constitutional Affairs/Attorneys Generals, Judges, Law Societies, Bar Associations, and representative of the Ministries responsible for EAC Affairs of all Partner States at a meeting in August 2016 and at other subsequent meetings convened by the East African Law Society (EALS), the MRA remains unsigned. There appears to have been no further progress since a September 2017 meeting organised by the EALS and the EAC Secretariat, in which Attorneys General refused to sign the agreement amidst concerns about who the appropriate signatories for the MRA were, accompanied by fears that their states might be unable to deliver the required changes and that the national laws ensuring the implementation of the Common Market Protocol were not yet in place (EALS Institute).

¹¹⁴ Art. 17, Common Market Protocol.

¹¹⁵ Art. 17(2) Common Market Protocol.

cases involving violations of the free movement of lawyers were brought under its consideration.¹¹⁶

2.2. Regulation of the practice of foreign lawyers in Rwanda

Despite the entry into force of the EAC Common Market Protocol in 2010, the law establishing the Bar Association in Rwanda (hereinafter RBA Law) lists being a Rwandan national as the first condition of eligibility to practice as a lawyer in Rwanda.¹¹⁷ However, there are two possible routes for non-Rwandans to practice in Rwanda. The first possibility applies if there is a reciprocal agreement in place and the foreign advocate is a national of a state which also allows Rwandans to practice in that country subject to international agreements. This extends beyond Partner States of the EAC. In the case of reciprocal agreements, the President of the Rwanda Bar Association (RBA) has the power to authorise such a lawyer to practice in Rwanda upon the presentation of a recommendation from the President of Bar of the advocate's state of origin and of proof of the fulfilment of reciprocity requirement.¹¹⁸ Lawyers thus authorised are entitled to practice in Rwanda only 'occasionally',¹¹⁹ meaning that they are not considered as permanently settled in Rwanda.

¹¹⁶ In *Patrick v Ministre des Affaires Culturelles*, an issue relating to the recognition by a EU member state of a qualification obtained in another member state was raised in a context where no directive on the mutual recognition of diplomas/qualification had been adopted (1977). The court found that 'the fact that those directives have not yet been issued does not entitle a Member State to deny the practical benefit of that freedom to a person subject to Community law.' *Patrick v Ministre des Affaires Culturelles* [1977] ECR 1199, para 17. The same reasoning was applied by the Court in the case of *Vlassopoulou*, relating to qualifications/diplomas to provide legal services.

¹¹⁷ Art. 6(1^o) Law No. 83/2013 of 11/09/2013 establishing the Bar Association in Rwanda and determining its organisation and functioning. This is a clear indication that the compliance with EAC law was not a concern of the lawmaker during the enactment of the RBA law.

¹¹⁸ In 2019, a total of 50 lawyers from Belgium, France, UK, Cameroon, Mauritania, Ghana, Gambia and DRC were practicing in Rwanda pursuant to this provision.

¹¹⁹ Art. 78 para 1 of Internal Rules and Regulations of Rwanda Bar Association.

The second route is open to nationals from a country that has concluded a regional integration agreement with Rwanda,¹²⁰ such as applies to lawyers from other EAC Partner States, who may wish to provide legal services in Rwanda.¹²¹ The RBA Law subjects the practice of lawyers in this category to the provisions of the regional integration agreement concerned (for example, in the case of the EAC, the Common Market Protocol), but it does not provide further details.¹²² There is no specific domestic legislation to implement the EAC Common Market protocol for the freedom of movement of legal services in Rwanda, and the RBA Law governs legal practice in Rwanda in general. Although Article 7 of the RBA Law authorises foreign lawyers to practice in Rwanda, it is unclear whether the Rwandan legislator had the implementation of the EAC Common Market Protocol in mind when the RBA Law was drafted, as this provision equally applies to lawyers from COMESA (Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa) and ECCAS (Economic Community of Central African States) countries, for instance. In any event, unlike foreign lawyers from countries that do not have a regional integration agreement with Rwanda, lawyers from EAC Partner States ‘enjoy the freedom to practice in case of need’ and are not required to present a recommendation of the president of their home Bar, although they must obtain the approval of the President of the RBA to commence practice.¹²³

It is worth mentioning that Rwanda and Kenya find themselves at odds with other EAC Partner States in pressing ahead and implementing the freedom of movement of legal services, despite the fact that the EAC Cross-Border Legal Practice Bill and the MRA have not yet been enacted. In principle, the applicability of supra-national norms at domestic level depends on whether the state concerned is monist or dualist. Although both Rwanda and Kenya

¹²⁰ Art. 7 RBA Law.

¹²¹ In 2019, a total of 42 lawyers from Burundi, Kenya and Uganda were on the list of the Rwanda Bar Association.

¹²² Art. 7 para 2 RBA Law.

¹²³ Art. 78 para 2 of the Internal Rules and Regulations of Rwanda Bar Association.

are monist states,¹²⁴ signifying that international law is directly applicable in their national legal systems, this has little to do with their progress in the implementation of the freedom of movement of legal services.¹²⁵ In fact, pursuant to Article 8(4) of the EAC Treaty, community laws have precedence over Partner States' laws on matters pertaining to the implementation of the treaty provisions. Similarly, EAC laws have a direct effect into Partner States' legal orders.¹²⁶ Therefore, the legal systems of Partner States should not be an excuse for delaying the implementation of rights and freedoms enshrined in EAC instruments, although this appears to be the case in practice.

During their period of practice in Rwanda, foreign lawyers in both categories outlined above are subject to a double deontology, like RELs in England and Wales, and must pay annual contributions to the RBA, pro rata for the number of months they intend to practice in Rwanda.¹²⁷ Contrary to the situation in the EU, the legal landscape for the regulation of the free movement of legal services in the EAC is in an embryonic phase. With regard to Rwanda, there are still many uncertainties, such as whether a certain type of service is exclusively reserved to Rwandan lawyers, whether foreign lawyers should practise under their home country title in Rwanda, whether some areas are subject to practice in conjunction with Rwandan lawyers. It

¹²⁴ See Art. 168 of the Constitution of Rwanda as modified in 2015, and Art. 2(6) of the Constitution of Kenya (2010). Kenya was traditionally a dualist country until the advent of the Constitution of 2010. L. Franceschi and PLO Lumumba. *The Constitution of Kenya: A Commentary* (2nd edition, Strathmore University Press 2019): 77.

¹²⁵ Both countries appear to be pro-integration and are therefore fast-tracking the implementation of EAC laws based on the principle of variable geometry. For more discussion on the application of the principle of variable geometry in EAC, see M. Binda, "Legal Framework of the EAC," in *East African Community Law* eds Ugirashebuja, E., Ruhangisa, J.E., Ottervanger, T. and Cuyvers, A. (Leiden. Brill Nijhoff, 2017): 103-118, 106.

¹²⁶ M. Binda, *Good Governance and Foreign Direct Investment: A Legal Contribution to a Balanced Economic Development in the East African Community*, PhD Thesis, Utrecht University, (2015): 184. <<https://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/318087>> Accessed 26 June 2020.

¹²⁷ Art. 78 para 4 of Internal Rules and Regulations of Rwanda Bar Association.

may be that if the EAC adopts directives that clearly follow the EU approach and address these issues, it would help build the confidence of the legal fraternity in the integration process. Nature abhorring a vacuum, it may be that it is the lack of legal instruments regulating specific aspects of this free movement that nurtures reluctance in some Partner States' constituencies, and causes difficulties in implementing the Common Market Protocol in Rwanda.

2.3. Structural/practical challenges to the FOM of legal services in the EAC

The challenges of implementing the EAC Common Market Protocol and validating the MRA are not the only impediments to free movement of legal services in the EAC. Of particular note is the resistance of professional bodies in some Partner States, and it is actually the professional bodies, Law Associations or Bar Associations in some Partner States which could be responsible for delaying the implementation of the Common Market Protocol and introducing the idea of the MRA.

A further issue in the EAC relates to language barriers. In Rwanda, court proceedings take place in Kinyarwanda;¹²⁸ in Tanzania, in Kiswahili; in Kenya in English or Kiswahili. Even if the movement of legal services were realised in law, there could still be considerable challenges for a Rwandan lawyer to present a case before a Kenyan court, for example. However, it should not be forgotten that legal services are not limited to presenting cases before court. They are in fact far more likely to involve giving legal advice to companies and individual clients from their practices. Depending on the circumstances of each individual case, there may not necessarily be a language barrier, or indeed, the presence of a lawyer who masters other

¹²⁸ See for instance Art. 203 of the Law No. 027/2019 of 19/09/2019 relating to criminal procedure. Although the same provision allows the use of other official languages (French, English, and Kiswahili) in court proceedings, Kinyarwanda is by far the most commonly used language.

languages could be a commercial advantage which extends the pool of potential clients.

The slow rate of harmonisation also presents challenges. In the EAC, the average duration for delivering a law degree is four years, but this is not universal. In some East African countries, there is no internal standardisation regarding the length of the law degree programme. Law schools may offer three-or four-year degree programmes. In Rwanda, for instance some private universities deliver a bachelor's degree in Law after a three-year programme; while at the public university, the University of Rwanda, it will take students four years to obtain a law degree. This suggests that Partner States may have to harmonise their undergraduate programmes internally before they harmonise them with other Partner States, and then determine between Partner States whether a postgraduate professional qualification in legal practice is also a requirement.

Furthermore, the Partner States of the EAC do not all espouse the same legal systems. Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania are largely common law countries; Burundi is a civil law country; Rwanda has a hybrid legal system; South Sudan has a dual system consisting of statutory and customary law. This has led to complications. In Uganda, for instance, lawyers from non-common law countries were not recognised. Some progress has been made in this area, as is demonstrated in the recent case of Tony Katungi, where a Ugandan law graduate, who had passed his Bar training course in Kenya and been admitted to the Kenyan Bar, was refused admission to the Ugandan Bar without supervised training. Subsequently, the Ugandan High Court held that he had in fact satisfied all the statutory requirements to enable him enrol as an Advocate of the High Court of Uganda. Both Uganda and Kenya are common law jurisdictions, however, in the judgment, the Court specifically referred to the harmonisation of national laws within the EAC regarding the legal professions:

Uganda as a Partner State is enjoined to harmonize the national laws in respect of the legal profession. Uganda as a member country signed the East African Community Common Market Protocol (EAC CMP) and undertook to provide free legal practice by 2015. Although we may have some varied academic routes and professional qualification requirements and owing to quality assurance or protectionist reasons, access to a number of professions including law is regulated. Uganda is bound to open up the space for workers through the East African Integration or devise a better approach to allow Free Movement of Workers in order to be compliant with the EAC Common Market Protocol.¹²⁹

This progress is echoed in the case of Kenyan Francis Muiruri Kimangi, who studied law in Uganda and was admitted to practise in Rwanda, yet had been denied enrolment with the Kenyan Bar. Kenyan Justice Weldon Korir determined that the Kenyan Advocates Act 2012¹³⁰ created a special category of persons eligible for admission to the Roll of Advocates: any person who is an advocate of the High Courts of Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi and Tanzania, and that to refuse enrolment contradicted the vision of the EAC.¹³¹ However, this apparent development in the Tony Katungi and Francis Muiruri Kimangi cases is sporadic and must be contrasted by the recent decision by the Ugandan High Court preventing Andrew Bataamwe from enrolling as an Advocate of the High Court of Uganda on the ground that he ‘undertook his Post Graduate Bar Course in Rwanda, which is not a common law jurisdiction.’¹³² This decision a couple of months after the Katungi case and by the same court divides the community into common

¹²⁹ *Katungi Tony vs Attorney General* (Misc. Cause No.204 of 2017) [2019] UGHCCD 1 (25 January 2019), para 44.

¹³⁰ S. 13(1)(d), Advocates Act 2012.

¹³¹ The East African, ‘Lawyer trained in Uganda allowed to practise in Kenya’. *The Daily Monitor*. 3 August, 2019. Available at <<https://www.monitor.co.ug/News/National/Lawyer-trained-in-Uganda-allowed-to-practise-in-Kenya/688334-5221558-111g1qw/index.html>> Accessed 1 November 2019.

¹³² *Andrew Bataamwe vs Attorney General* (Misc. Cause No. 280 of 2019) (13 May 2020).

law and civil law states and confirms Partner States' reluctance to implement the Common Market Protocol provisions related to the liberalisation of legal services within the EAC. This apparent groping in the darkness reveals the need for guidelines – most probably via decisions from the East African Court of Justice – to foster uniform implementation of EAC law with regard to the free movement of legal services in the EAC.

Conclusion

These concerns are, of course, not peculiar to the EAC, and each REC, due to its different contexts, must approach the challenges in its own peculiar manner. The EU has also had to confront the issues of different legal systems across its territory,¹³³ a large number of different languages, and different routes to qualification in slightly differing legal professions. These issues have been dealt with by requiring lawyers to register with the professional bodies in the home and host states as appropriate, and being subject to the Codes of Conduct and potential disciplinary proceedings if they exceed their levels of competence. However, the EAC has adopted a different approach to that of the EU regarding the recognition of academic and professional qualifications and proposes going further by harmonising legal education across Member States.¹³⁴ Advocates eligible to practise in one member state would then automatically be eligible to practice in all. This has raised practical considerations and concerns about oversight of competence, which have yet to be overcome.¹³⁵

¹³³ Only England and Wales, Northern Ireland, Ireland and Gibraltar have common law systems; Cyprus and Malta are mixed; the remaining states have civil law systems.

¹³⁴ Article 166 TFEU specifically excludes harmonisation of laws and regulations of the EU Member States with regard to vocational training policy.

¹³⁵ European states took steps to confront similar concerns via the Bologna Process, which established the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) in 2010. The EHEA through its 48 Member States ensures the mutual recognition of qualifications and learning periods abroad completed at other universities, implements a system of quality assurance and aims to increase staff and student mobility and facilitate employability.

Other apprehensions exist, such as the potential flooding of a market with lawyers from Partner States and a need to ‘share the cake’ between more competitors. However, the EU model tends to demonstrate that liberalising the legal services market leads to an increased offer with new markets opening up and greater possibilities for lawyers and law firms to expand their work: an ever-growing cake, like a cornucopia, to share. Rwanda and Kenya have already opened up their legal services market to some extent and could be benefitting from this. As of November 2019, ninety-two foreign lawyers are registered as practicing in Rwanda, forty-three per cent being from EAC Partner States.¹³⁶ This is progress, since in 2010, there were virtually no foreign professionals practising in any of the states,¹³⁷ and only Rwanda and Kenya allowed legal practitioners from Partner States to practice within their borders.¹³⁸ Certainly, it would seem that an expansion in legal services providers in the EAC could be accommodated if not welcomed. In 2011, there were approximately 280 solicitors per 100,000 people in England and Wales¹³⁹ as compared to approximately five per 100,000 in Rwanda and Uganda, nineteen per 100,000 in Kenya and two per 100,000 in Tanzania in 2009.¹⁴⁰ According to a report compiled for the World Bank in 2010, the legal sector in East African states is dominated by small firms, which cannot meet the demand for large and complex projects, a fact which policy makers have recognised, acknowledging the need to

¹³⁶ Records from the Executive Secretary of RBA.

¹³⁷ N. Dihel, Fernandes, A.M., and Mattoo, A., “Developing Professional Services in Africa Through Regional Integration.” 15 September 2010. Available at <<http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTPREMNET/Resources/EP32.pdf>> Accessed 2 November 2019, p. 27.

¹³⁸ The East African, Legal practice far from integration. 13 July, 2009. Available at <https://www.theeastafican.co.ke/news/2558-622446-view-printVersion-4ft75c/index.html> Accessed 2 November 2019.

¹³⁹ Based on SRA figures. SRA, “Population of Solicitors in England and Wales.” 2019. Available at <https://www.sra.org.uk/sra/how-we-work/reports/statistics/regulated-community-statistics/data/population_solicitors/> Accessed 2 November 2019.

¹⁴⁰ N. Dihel, Fernandes, A.M., Mattoo, A. and Strychacz, N., “Reform and Regional Integration of Professional Services in East Africa The World Bank.” September 2010. Available at <<http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTPREMNET/Resources/EP32.pdf>> Accessed 2 November 2019, p. 2.

develop legal services,¹⁴¹ and this is relevant to the successful evolution of cross-border trade. For example, an East African business seeking to establish itself in a different partner state, or a multinational East African firm expanding further will not necessarily be able to use the services of its own in-house legal team nor local legal advisers if that particular partner state has not implemented the freedom of movement provisions of the Common Market Protocol. This is a crucial restriction at a time when, according to the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa's (UNECA) Economic Report on Africa for 2019, regional integration is an imperative for Africa in the fight against poverty. East Africa is the fastest growing REC in Africa, with growth rising from 6.1 per cent in 2017 to 6.2 per cent in 2018, and enhanced regional integration through the RECs as well as the African Continental Free Trade Area offers the possibility of considerable economic growth across East Africa.¹⁴² A case study into trade in Kenya carried out by Dihel et al found that 'more than half of Kenyan service exporters have clients in Tanzania and/or in Uganda and one third have clients in Rwanda' and concluded that 'regional markets are important for exports of accounting, architecture, engineering, insurance, and legal services'.¹⁴³ Further case studies by Dihel and Goswami¹⁴⁴ 'demonstrate that entrepreneurs are able to circumvent formal barriers to cross-border trade in services and that there is substantial demand for services imports, suggesting that liberalization and services trade facilitation – to remove the need for bribes and more generally lower transactions costs and the ability

¹⁴¹ Dihel et al, "Developing Professional Services in Africa Through Regional Integration," 1-2.

¹⁴² United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) "Fiscal Policy for Financing Sustainable Development in Africa. Economic Report on Africa 2019." Available at <<http://repository.uneca.org/bitstream/handle/10855/41804/b11928190.pdf?sequence=1>> Accessed 2 November 2019, pp. 6 and 13.

¹⁴³ N. Dihel, A. Fernandes, R. Gicho, J. Kashangaki and N. Strychcz. "Becoming a Global Exporter of Business Services? The Case of Kenya." In *Exporting Services: A Developing Country Perspective*, A. Goswami, A. Mattoo and S. Sáez (eds.), (World Bank 2012): 237-69, 248.

¹⁴⁴ N. Dihel, and A. Goswami (eds.) *From Hair Stylists and Teachers to Accountants and Doctors - The Unexplored Potential of Trade in Services in Africa* (World Bank 2016).

of incumbent services industries (e.g. professional associations) to restrict foreign entry – has great potential to both expand trade further and increase welfare (the gains from trade).¹⁴⁵ Fears of aggressive competition which will lead to less legal work are likely to be unfounded.

Large sectors of Law will remain domestic, and knowledge of local practices and language and nuance will play a paramount role in the choice of lawyer, particularly for private clients or for small local businesses. Furthermore, enhanced economic growth is also vital in enabling African states to meet the UN’s sustainable development goals, which aim ‘to leave no one behind’ as countries develop.¹⁴⁶

For the UK, much still remains to be determined with regard to the free movement of legal services in the future. UK lawyers working in the EU under UK qualifications will fall under regulations for non-EU lawyers and will no longer benefit from the automatic recognition of their qualifications. The Law Society of England and Wales predicted that leaving the EU with no deal would likely lead to a loss of legal services turnover of £3.5 billion (nearly 10%) and of 10,000 jobs. The Law Society points out that the UK will be negotiating legal market access with 31 different regulatory regimes (EU, EFTA, EEA), with different levels of restrictions placed on third country lawyers.¹⁴⁷ EU lawyers wishing to practice in the UK will have to apply through the RFL route, but may see their practice areas restricted.

¹⁴⁵ B. Hoekman, “Integrating African Services Markets in Regional Integration in Africa,” proceedings of the 20th Senior Policy Seminar, Nairobi: African Economic Research Consortium, 2018. Available at <<https://www.eui.eu/DepartmentsAndCentres/RobertSchumanCentre/Africa-Platform/Publications>> Accessed 2 November 2019, p. 7.

¹⁴⁶ See UN Sustainable Development Goals Knowledge Platform, “Helping governments and stakeholders make the SDGs a reality.” Available at <<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/>> Accessed 2 November 2019.

¹⁴⁷ The Law Society of England and Wales, *The UK-EU future partnership – legal services sector*. 1 August 2019. Available at <<https://www.lawsociety.org.uk/policy-campaigns/articles/uk-eu-future-partnership-legal-services/>> Accessed 3 November 2019, p. 2.

As English and Welsh lawyers face their post Brexit future, they may well be looking on with some envy at their East African counterparts, for whom the free movement of legal services still remains a possibility, even if clouded with uncertainty and some suspicion in certain quarters.

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L'intégration régionale du Burundi au sein de la Communauté Est-Africaine: Défis liés à l'harmonisation des lois nationales en vue de l'opérationnalisation du Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est-Africaine

Nicelate MATEMERE

nicelatemateme@gmail.com

Résumé: *Après avoir adhéré à la communauté Est Africaine le 1^{er} Juillet 2007, la République du Burundi a ratifié, aux côtés des autres Pays Partenaires de la Communauté, le Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine en 2010, avec un engagement ferme de le rendre pleinement opérationnel en 2015. Cependant, force est de constater que cette échéance s'est écoulée sans la mise en œuvre effective dudit protocole. Ce retard étant dû aux obstacles auquel le processus d'harmonisation des textes législatifs et règlementaires nationaux fait face, notamment des problèmes d'ordre conjoncturel, politique, institutionnel, technique et financier.*

Mots clés: *Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est, Marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est, Harmonisation des lois nationales.*

Introduction

Bien que ce soit un phénomène ancien, l'intégration régionale à travers le monde a connu un dynamisme sans précédent durant ces dernières décennies. Des groupements économiques régionaux se sont multipliés partout dans le monde, que ce soit en Europe, en Asie, en Amérique et pour l'Afrique, ces organisations régionales prolifèrent dès les années 1980.¹

Créée en 1967 entre la Tanzanie, l'Ouganda et le Kenya, la Communauté Est Africaine a fonctionné jusqu'en 1977. Au moment de sa dissolution (1977), elle était parvenue à un haut niveau d'intégration caractérisé par une

¹ Mattli Walter, *The logic of Regional Integration; Europe and Beyond* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1999).

gestion commune des politiques monétaires et fiscales y compris une banque centrale et une monnaie unique (le Shilling), une union douanière, de l'enseignement supérieur, des postes, des ports, des chemins de fer et une compagnie aérienne commune, pour ne citer que ceux-ci.² (Atsiaya, *Challenges facing Economic Integration. A case study of East African Community 2000-2012*, 2014).

La Communauté est Africaine a été relancée en 1999, avec la signature du Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine et le Burundi a joint cette communauté en 2007.³

La Vision de la Communauté Est Africaine est «Une Afrique de l'Est prospère, compétitive, sûre, stable et politiquement unie». La Mission de la Communauté Est Africaine est d'«élargir et renforcer l'intégration économique, politique, sociale et culturelle en vue d'améliorer la qualité de la vie des peuples d'Afrique de l'Est à travers une compétitivité plus accrue, la production à valeur ajoutée, le commerce et l'investissement.» La Communauté Est Africaine a pour objectif de développer des politiques et des programmes visant à élargir et à approfondir, pour le bénéfice mutuel, la coopération entre les Pays Partenaires dans les domaines de l'économie, de la politique, des affaires sociales et culturelles, de la recherche, de la technologie, de la défense, de la sécurité ainsi que des affaires juridiques et judiciaires.⁴

Les étapes prévues par le processus d'intégration au sein de la Communauté Est Africaine sont: (i) L'Union Douanière; (ii) Le Marché Commun; (iii) L'Union Monétaire; et (iv) la Fédération Politique en phase ultime, avec la

² Angela M. Atsiaya, *Challenges facing Economic Integration. A case study of East African Community 2000-2012* (Nairobi: University of Nairobi, 2014).

³ Traité portant accession du Burundi à la Communauté Est Africaine, 2007.

⁴ Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine, 1999.

Confédération Politique de la Communauté Est Africaine comme une phase transitoire vers la Fédération Politique de la Communauté Est Africaine.⁵

Pour accélérer le processus d'intégration au sein de la Communauté Est Africaine, il est important que le Burundi intègre les instruments et les décisions communautaires dans les cadres juridiques et réglementaires nationaux ainsi que dans les politiques, les programmes, les stratégies et les projets. Pour ce faire, les lois et règlements deviennent le fondement de toute intégration. Ainsi, la Communauté Est Africaine, à travers le traité portant sa création, les protocoles, les régulations et différentes décisions, a mis sur pied un cadre légal auquel les pays partenaires se référeraient afin de s'acquitter de leurs devoirs d'une part et de bénéficier des dividendes de l'intégration d'autre part.

La République du Burundi après avoir adhéré à la Communauté Est Africaine le 1^{er} Juillet 2007, a ratifié le Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine, un deuxième pilier de l'intégration de la Communauté Est Africaine. Les Etats Partenaires de la Communauté se sont engagés à le rendre opérationnel en fixant des échéances; le Burundi ayant fixé l'année 2015.⁶

Cependant, force est de constater que l'année 2015 s'est écoulée sans la mise en œuvre effective dudit protocole et l'une des raisons de ce retard étant le blocage dû au fait que les lois et réglementations nationales du Burundi sont divergentes à celles préconisées dans ledit protocole, nécessitant ainsi un amendement, une révision et harmonisation.

Ainsi au Burundi, le processus d'harmonisation de ses textes et lois nationaux regorge des opportunités qui cependant se heurtent aux défis liés

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Protocole portant création du marché commun de la communauté est africaine et ses six annexes déjà négociés, annexe v sur la libéralisation progressive des services.

à la conjoncture, aux problèmes politiques et institutionnels, techniques et financiers.

I. Approche méthodologique

Cette recherche a été une recherche descriptive sans contrôle sur les variables mais rapportant ce qui s'est passé et qui se passe en explorant leurs causes.⁷

Dans un premier temps il a été question de réviser les différentes théories pertinentes du domaine de la coopération internationale et d'intégration régionale.

Ensuite l'analyse a porté sur des données secondaires c'est-à-dire des données provenant des documents disponibles. Ces documents englobaient les documents officiels du Gouvernement du Burundi et de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est tels que le Traité portant création de la Communauté, le Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est, les divers rapports, les décisions importantes, les décrets et autres.

II. Repères conceptuels, théoriques et les tendances dans les faits

II.1. Repères conceptuels et théoriques

L'intégration régionale vise la prospérité des pays membres et cette forme de coopération couvre les domaines économiques pour la plupart, sociales, culturelles, politiques, etc. Le concept d'intégration régionale offre ainsi aux Etats une opportunité de renforcer et d'élargir leurs interactions lesquelles font nécessairement appel à un cadre légal commun. De ce fait, la révision des lois, régulations et règlements nationaux des Etats membres afin de se

⁷ C. R. Kothari, *Research Methodology, Methodes and Techniques*, Second Revised Edition (New Delhi: New Age International Ltd Publisher, 2004).

conformer aux lois communautaires (Traités, Protocoles, Décisions Communes, etc.) s'avère indispensable.

De même que les autres groupements régionaux au monde, la Communauté Est Africaine vise le développement économique durable de ses pays partenaires.⁸ Pour y arriver, ces derniers ont signé, puis ratifié les différents protocoles qui, une fois opérationnalisés, faciliteraient la réalisation des objectifs de leur intégration. Ainsi, en 2005, le protocole établissant l'Union Douanière fut signé, suivi de celui du Marché Commun en 2010 et de l'Union Monétaire en 2014, en suivant le modèle d'intégration proposé par Bella Balassa (1961), du moins si l'on considère les cinq étapes de l'intégration régionale (Zone de libre échange, Union douanière, Marché commun, Union économique et Union politique). La Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est envisage même de franchir une étape ultime qui est la Fédération Politique.

Stanley Hoffman, dans sa théorie intergouvernementaliste, insiste sur le rôle de l'Etat en tant qu'acteur clé dans le processus d'intégration régionale. De même la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est est une Organisation Intergouvernementale Régionale composée actuellement de Six (06) Etats, en l'occurrence le Burundi, le Kenya, l'Ouganda, le Rwanda, la Tanzanie et le Sud Soudan. Ce sont les Etats partenaires qui déterminent par un consensus les domaines de coopération, les institutions à mettre en place pour superviser cette coopération et la façon dont ils veulent mettre en œuvre cette coopération. Ainsi, l'intégration au sein de la Communauté Est Africaine est basée sur Quatre (04) principaux piliers qui sont l'Union Douanière, le Marché Commun, l'Union Monétaire, et la Fédération Politique.

L'Article 127 du Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine stipule que les Pays Partenaires s'engagent à coopérer dans tous les

⁸ Article 5 du Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine, 1999.

domaines de la vie des peuples Est Africains à savoir la Politique, l'Economie, les Affaires Sociales et Culturelles, la Recherche, la Technologie, la Défense, la Sécurité ainsi que les Affaires Juridiques et Judiciaires.

Au sein de la Communauté Est Africaine, l'intégration économique fait appel à la révision ou la réforme des lois nationales des pays Partenaires en vue de la mise en œuvre effective des engagements pris au niveau Communautaire. Cela nous rapproche à ce que Ernst Haas démontre par la théorie du Néo Fonctionnalisme en ce sens que les pays en participant dans une intégration fonctionnelle dans un domaine bien déterminé, au fur et à mesure que l'intégration se renforce, ces pays sentent la nécessité ou l'obligation de coopérer dans les autres domaines que ceux initialement déterminés «the functional spillover.»

Par conséquent, la primauté des acteurs étatiques (les Chefs d'Etat et de Gouvernements) dans les décisions relatives aux projets et programmes d'intégration fait appel à une intégration dans les autres domaines notamment la coopération en l'occurrence la réforme institutionnelle et réglementaire au sein des pays partenaires de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est.

II.2. Les tendances dans les faits

Depuis son adhésion entière à la Communauté Est Africaine en 2007 et la signature du Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine en 2010, le Burundi a entrepris le processus d'harmonisation de ses textes législatifs et réglementaires nationaux en vue de rendre opérationnel le Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine dans la marge de l'échéance fixé.

Cependant, ce travail se heurte à bien d'obstacles qui ont conduit le pays à ne pas honorer ses engagements dans les délais malgré les opportunités dont il dispose. L'un des faits marquants du processus d'intégration du Burundi est son expérience dans ses efforts d'harmoniser ses lois nationales,

un préalable pour la mise en œuvre du Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est.

Dans le but d'atteindre les objectifs fixés par le traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine, les Pays Partenaires s'attèlent à harmoniser leurs lois nationales en vue de faciliter la mise en œuvre des différents protocoles, décisions et régulations communautaires.⁹ Bien plus le protocole portant création du Marché Commun stipule en son article 47 l'harmonisation des politiques et lois des pays partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine. Et d'une façon explicite, l'art.32 du même protocole appelle tous les Pays Partenaires de la Communauté à aligner leurs lois nationales afin de rendre opérationnelle le Marché Commun au sein de la région. La mise en œuvre du Droit Communautaire au sein des Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine part du principe prévu par le Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine spécialement en son Article 8(5), qui prévoit que chaque Pays Partenaire doit adopter les mesures légales nécessaires sur le Plan Interne pour assurer la primauté du Droit Communautaire sur le Droit Interne.

Au niveau régional, à part le traité, les protocoles et autres décisions communautaires, des organes chargés de s'assurer d'une part de la conformité des lois au traité et du suivi de leur mise en œuvre dans les Pays Partenaires d'autre part. (Art.14 3(h) et l'Art.62, ont été mis sur pied et sont actuellement opérationnels, à savoir l'Assemblée Législative de la Communauté Est Africaine (EALA), la Cour de Justice Est Africaine(EACJ), le Conseil Sectoriel sur la législation et les Affaires Judiciaires. Ainsi, la République du Burundi s'est engagée à mettre en œuvre le Droit Communautaire dont les sources sont:

- Le Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine;

⁹ Article 126 du Traité portant création de la Communauté Est Africaine, 1999.

- Le Traité d'Accession par la République du Burundi à la Communauté Est Africaine (The Treaty of Accession of the Republic of Burundi into the East African Community);
- Loi N° 1/08 du 30 juin 2007 portant Ratification par la République du Burundi de l'Acte d'Adhésion de la République du Burundi à la Communauté Est Africaine, signé à Kampala, Ouganda, le 18 juin 2007;
- Les Protocoles et leurs Annexes;
- Les Memoranda d'Entente;
- Les Lois adoptées par l'Assemblée Législative de la Communauté Est Africaine et signées par les Chefs d'Etat de la Communauté Est Africaine;
- Les Règlements;
- Les Décisions et Directives;
- Les Recommandations;
- La Coutume Internationale; et
- La Jurisprudence.

Dans le souci d'assurer cette primauté du Droit Communautaire sur le Droit Interne, la République du Burundi à l'instar des autres Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine, doit s'assurer que la Ratification des Protocoles et autres Instruments Juridiques signés par tous les Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine se fassent dans les délais prescrits par la norme communautaire. Consécutivement à cette étape, la mise en œuvre effective du Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine devrait se réaliser. Les Citoyens Burundais, en contribuant d'une part au développement des lois de l'Assemblée Législative de la Communauté Est Africaine (EALA), et en harmonisant les textes législatifs et réglementaires nationaux d'autre part, ils mettent en place un Cadre Légal approprié d'une bonne mise en œuvre du Droit de la Communauté Est Africaine au sein des Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine.

Ainsi, au niveau national, en plus de ces organes de la communauté, le Ministère de la Justice, le Service National de la Législation (SNL) et les Ministères sectoriels sont des institutions chargées de mener le processus d'intégration à bon port à travers l'harmonisation des lois nationales, bien sûr en collaboration avec des commissions ad hoc mises sur pied selon la nature de la loi à harmoniser (Ministère, 2017).

III. De l'expérience du Burundi dans la mise en œuvre du Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est: des opportunités, des réalisations et des défis

III.1. Des opportunités

Le Burundi, comme les autres Pays de la communauté Est Africaine, a franchi la deuxième étape de l'intégration (le Marché Commun) et est également engagé aux côtés des autres pays partenaires dans la mise en œuvre dudit protocole par la révision de ses lois nationales en vue de les rapprocher, les rendre conformes à celles dudit protocole.

L'existence des institutions et des organes chargés des affaires légales et judiciaires est un atout important que le Burundi dispose. Vient alors en tête le Ministère de la Justice et ses services y afférents entre autre le Service National de Législation(SNL).¹⁰

Bien plus, en 2010, le Gouvernement du Burundi a donné une nouvelle orientation au Ministère à la présidence chargé des Affaires de la Communauté Est Africaine, par son élévation auprès du cabinet de la Présidence de la République afin de lui rendre directement compte de toute activité en rapport avec l'intégration du Burundi dans la Communauté Est Africaine en tant qu'institution de coordination.¹¹

¹⁰ Décret-loi n° 1/024 du 13 juillet 1989.

¹¹ Décret présidentiel n° 100/02 du 29 Aout 2010.

Cependant, quoi qu'essentiel, des institutions à elles seules ne suffisent pas pour la réussite de l'agenda communautaire. A côté de ce cadre institutionnel; des cadres et experts, des membres des commissions ad hoc selon la nature de la loi à harmoniser s'attèlent au travail de rapprocher les lois nationales avec celles de la Communauté afin de rendre ces dernières opérationnelles. De ce fait, un travail non négligeable d'harmonisation des textes législatifs et réglementaires nationaux dans le cadre de la Communauté Est Africaine a été déjà entrepris, même si les résultats atteints, en termes de nombre de textes législatifs et réglementaires déjà harmonisés (2/ 40 depuis 2014) laissent à désirer.¹²

III.2. Des réalisations dans le cadre du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine

Le Marché Commun constitue le stade le plus élevé du niveau d'intégration économique entre les Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine et repose sur la Libre Circulation des Marchandises, des Personnes, de la Main d'œuvre, des Services, des Capitaux et sur les Droits corollaires d'Etablissement et de Résidence.¹³

En effet, le Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine a été négocié depuis Février 2008 et signé le 29 novembre 2009. Il est entré en vigueur le 1^{er} juillet 2010.

Au niveau de la Libre Circulation des Marchandises, il y a eu la suppression des taxes pour toutes les marchandises en provenance des Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine et la mise en œuvre du Projet de Facilitation du Commerce et du Transport au sein de la Communauté Est Africaine.

¹² Sur 6 lois déjà priorisées par le processus d'harmonisation, seulement 2 ont été harmonisées, 2 autres en attente d'approbation par les instances habilitées et enfin, le travail est en cours pour les 2 autres.

¹³ Article 2 du Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine.

Au niveau de la Libre Circulation des Personnes, il y a eu la suppression des Visas pour tout citoyen de la Communauté Est Africaine entrant dans un autre Pays Partenaire de la Communauté Est Africaine, et l'introduction du Passeport Biométrique de la Communauté Est Africaine.

Au niveau de la Libre Circulation de la Main d'Œuvre et de la Libre Circulation des Services et des Capitaux, il y a la reconnaissance mutuelle des titres académiques et des qualifications professionnelles, l'harmonisation des curricula et l'harmonisation en cours des procédures et du format de demande de permis de travail. On peut aussi noter la mobilité des enseignants et des étudiants et celle des facteurs de production.

S'agissant particulièrement de la Libre Circulation des Capitaux, les infrastructures du Marché des Capitaux se mettent progressivement en place. De même, dans le cadre de la facilitation du commerce des biens et services, l'Autorité sur la Concurrence a été mise en place au niveau régional, cependant au niveau national, la mise en place de l'Autorité sur la Concurrence accuse un certain retard.

Concernant les Droits corollaires d'Etablissement et de Résidence, l'harmonisation des procédures et du format de demande de permis de résidence est en cours.

Avec la mise en œuvre du Protocole portant création du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine, des projets et programmes intégrateurs ont été également développés et d'autres sont en cours de développement, y compris la mise sur pied des Centres d'Excellence et des Institutions spécialisées sur des questions pointues d'intégration selon les secteurs.¹⁴

Le développement des projets et programmes intégrateurs se nourrit également des initiatives de la Communauté Est Africaine à négocier des Arrangements avec les Pays et les Organisations tiers. Il s'agit notamment

¹⁴ Annexe sur les Projets et programmes selon les secteurs.

des initiatives de négocier des Accords Commerciaux avec des Pays tels que les Etats-Unis d'Amérique (USA), la Chine, la Turquie, le Brésil, l'Inde et le Royaume-Uni, pour ne citer que les pays qui ont déjà fait part de leur manifestation d'intérêt.

Il sied aussi de souligner, pour la Communauté Est Africaine, sa capacité juridique à négocier des Accords de Libre Echange avec les Communautés Economiques Régionales avoisinantes, notamment l'Accord portant création de la Zone de Libre Echange entre le Marché Commun de l'Afrique Orientale et Australe (COMESA), la Communauté Est Africaine (EAC) et la Communauté de Développement de l'Afrique Australe (SADC); et sur le plan continental, l'Accord portant création de la Zone de Libre Echange Continentale Africaine (ZLECAf).¹⁵

Enfin, on note également les négociations entre la Communauté Est Africaine (EAC) et l'Union Européenne (UE) d'un Accord de Partenariat Economique (EPA EAC-UE). Cet Accord a achoppé sur des questions émergentes y compris les sanctions qu'ont imposées l'Union Européenne contre le Burundi et le retrait de la Grande Bretagne de l'Union Européenne (Brexit).

En rapport avec l'harmonisation des lois nationales, la République du Burundi a déjà accompli un travail comprenant notamment:

- L'identification des textes législatifs et réglementaires à harmoniser et dont la liste est disponible depuis 2014;¹⁶
- L'Organisation des Séances de Sensibilisation sur le Processus d'harmonisation des Lois nationales dans le cadre de la Communauté Est Africaine à l'intention des Partenaires Nationaux;

¹⁵ Les Communautés Economiques Régionales constituent les piliers de l'intégration continentale africaine.

¹⁶ Rapport sur les textes législatifs et règlementaires à être en harmonie avec le Protocole portant création du Marché commun de la Communauté Est Africaine.

- L'Organisation des travaux d'amendements de ces textes au cours des différentes Retraites financées par le Gouvernement du Burundi;
- L'Organisation des réunions d'évaluation à mi-parcours de ces travaux d'amendements;
- Certaines lois nationales harmonisées pour les rendre compatibles aux dispositions du Protocole du Marché Commun de l'Afrique de l'Est notamment:
 - ✓ La loi n° 1/07 du 26 avril 2010 du Code de Commerce a été déjà harmonisée;
 - ✓ La loi n° 1/07 du 27 avril 2015 sur le Partenariat Public et Privé(PPP) a été déjà harmonisée;
 - ✓ La loi sur l'Insolvabilité, est déjà révisée et est en attente d'approbation;
 - ✓ La loi n° 1/09 du 30 mai 2011 sur les Entreprises est déjà révisée et est en attente d'être approuvée;
 - ✓ La loi sur les contrats de vente des marchandises est en cours de révision;
 - ✓ Le décret-loi n° 1/037 u mois de juillet 1993 sur l'Emploi et l'Ordonnance Ministérielle n° 666/086/92 du 17 avril 1992 sur l'Emploi des Etrangers au Burundi est en cours de révision.

III.3. Des défis

Même s'il y a un pas déjà franchi, force est de constater que malgré tous les efforts fournis en vue d'accélérer ce processus d'harmonisation des textes législatifs et réglementaires nationaux en vue de rendre opérationnel le Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine, le processus demeure lent au niveau national et ne satisfait pas aux attentes du Public Est Africain, y compris le public burundais, sans passer sous silence le dépassement de l'échéance fixé.

Cela est dû au fait que ce processus rencontre des obstacles réels dont la difficulté linguistique, les systèmes juridiques différents ainsi que l'absence d'une Commission de Réforme du Droit qui serait mis en place dans le cadre de l'harmonisation institutionnelle initiée par la Communauté Est Africaine. De cette expérience, il est aussi à constater que la mise en œuvre des engagements communautaires dépend de plusieurs facteurs endogènes et exogènes notamment la volonté politique, la définition des priorités, les ressources financières, et le contexte sociopolitique. Bien plus, la non-appropriation, les aléas sanitaires qui surgissent en l'occurrence le Corona Virus 19, peuvent être aussi des menaces à la réalisation du processus d'harmonisation des lois nationales et autres projets et programmes communautaires.

Concrètement les défis institutionnels liés au fait que certaines structures institutionnelles ne sont pas autonomes constituent un des défis majeurs. Par exemple, le Service National de Législation (SNL) a des compétences relativement limitées s'il s'agit de la révision d'une loi quelconque du fait qu'il ne peut pas s'auto saisir; viennent aussi s'ajouter les intérêts nationaux, une problématique qui fait appel à la priorisation des actions à mener selon la volonté politique.

D'autres obstacles sont d'ordre technique et financier et font retarder le processus d'harmonisation et par conséquent discréditent le Burundi qui devrait honorer les engagements pris envers le protocole du Marché Commun (dépassement de l'échéance fixé), sans oublier la bureaucratie qui est aussi une problématique dans ce processus d'harmonisation des lois nationales au Burundi. Cette dernière est liée au fait que les décisions se prennent en suivant la procédure hiérarchique par laquelle chaque niveau hiérarchique de prise de décision est contrôlé par un autre niveau qui lui est hiérarchiquement supérieur tel que expliqué par Max Weber dans ses six principes bureaucratiques.

En vue de la mise en œuvre des engagements communautaires, les Pays Partenaires de la Communauté Est Africaine doivent procéder à une harmonisation institutionnelle dans les domaines jugés cruciaux et conformément aux Décisions des Conseils des Ministres de la Communauté Est Africaine prises à cet effet. Certaines Institutions ont été déjà créées dans ce cadre et d'autres ne le sont pas encore à l'instar de la Commission de Réforme du Droit, ce qui handicape énormément la mise en œuvre des Projets et Programmes intégrateurs de la Communauté Est Africaine.

Bien que l'intégration régionale vise l'amélioration des conditions de vie des citoyens de la communauté, certains semblent être eux-mêmes une barrière au changement (Le projet de mise en place d'une Commission Permanente du Burundi chargée des réformes juridiques et judiciaires est en attente d'approbation depuis 2015). Ainsi la Commission de Réforme du Droit est l'une des Institutions qui n'ont pas encore été créées au Burundi, bien que le Conseil des Ministres de la Communauté Est Africaine l'ait déjà décidé. Plusieurs interrogations se posent alors sur cette situation et ce questionnement porte sur la résistance au changement de la part de certains décideurs, les contraintes budgétaires pour la création et le fonctionnement de cette institution, l'intérêt national et la priorisation.

Actuellement, dans le contexte de la menace mondiale liée à la Pandémie du CoronaVirus dit Covid-19 qui sévit, il est à faire remarquer que des activités relatives à l'intégration du Burundi dans la Communauté dont celles relatives à l'harmonisation des lois nationales dans le cadre du Marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est ont pris du retard.

IV. Conclusion et recommandations: une harmonisation des lois nationales pour la réussite de l'intégration du Burundi au sein de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est

Le Burundi, ayant pris des engagements aux côtés des autres pays partenaires de la Communauté, devrait, pour mieux s'intégrer, mener des

actions concrètes en commençant par l'harmonisation de ses lois nationales, clé de la mise en application du Protocole du Marché Commun de la Communauté Est Africaine 2010.

Le Burundi a des opportunités diverses pour une intégration Est Africaine réussie tels que le cadre légal tant régional que national, un personnel compétent et dévoué, des structures légales bien que certaines d'entre elles nécessiteraient quelques révisions, etc.

De ce fait, la volonté politique des décideurs nationaux et acteurs principaux dans le processus d'intégration est d'une importance capitale, sans passer sous le silence la nécessité d'une étroite collaboration des décideurs régionaux et nationaux afin d'atteindre les objectifs fixés par la communauté.

Force est de constater que le cadre légal actuel en charge du processus d'harmonisation nécessite quelques révisions pour mener à bon port le travail d'harmonisation des lois nationales, soit par dotation des missions additionnelles relatives à l'intégration économique régionale, soit par restructuration afin d'être en harmonie avec les structures similaires des pays partenaires de la communauté Est Africaine en vue de son autonomisation pour plus d'indépendance dans la conduite de ses activités.

Bien plus un travail en synergie entre les instances communautaires et nationales est d'une importance capitale, ce qui permettrait d'avoir une harmonisation effective et efficace au sein de la région Est Africaine.

La résistance au changement étant un handicap majeur au développement, des campagnes de sensibilisation en vue de conscientiser les Burundais sur les avantages de l'intégration pourraient être multipliées, ce qui, à la longue, produirait un changement de mentalité et par conséquent de comportement.

Enfin, la situation qui a été créée par la pandémie du Coronavirus (COVID-19) nécessitera des ajustements dans la conduite des affaires au niveau de la Communauté Est Africaine en général et dans le processus d'harmonisation des lois nationales au Burundi en vue de la mise en œuvre effective du Protocole du marché Commun de la Communauté de l'Afrique de l'Est en particulier.

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L'avenir du G5 Sahel à l'épreuve du temps covidien

Emmanuel Odilon KOUKOUBOU

koukoubouodilon@gmail.com

Résumé: *Les diverses conséquences de la crise sanitaire liée au Covid-19 rendent l'avenir du G5 Sahel actuellement quelque peu incertain. Osant inviter le futur à l'analyse, nous appréhendons l'avenir de ce mécanisme à la lumière de la sociologie politique de l'action publique et dégageons quelques constances et tendances. Nous constaterons qu'à moyen terme, le G5 Sahel ne risque pas grands bouleversements et qu'à long terme, il peut être l'objet de rivalités géostratégiques entre la Chine et la France.*

Mots clés: *G5 Sahel, Covid-19, Temps covidien, Terrorisme sahélien, Insécurité.*

Introduction

Qu'est-ce que le G5 Sahel? A cette question, la littérature semble répondre quasi unanimement qu'il s'agit d'une organisation internationale mise en place par quelques Etats, dotée d'un acte constitutif¹, d'organes de gestion, de personnalité juridique et d'objectifs fixés par les Chefs d'Etats. Mais une telle conception a la faiblesse de prendre le G5 Sahel pour son contenant – sa force institutionnelle – en reléguant à la périphérie son contenu, c'est-à-dire l'ensemble des initiatives portées par les Etats dans ce cadre institutionnel. Mieux, cette réponse considère peu le caractère typique de ce mécanisme institutionnel qui est une réponse spécifique de quelques acteurs étatiques à un problème spécifique qui lui préexistait et qu'il compte juguler. C'est pour aller plus loin que l'approche traditionnelle que notre réponse à cette question adopte une autre perspective jusqu'ici inexplorée: le G5 Sahel est à la fois une action publique internationale de sécurité et un instrument d'action publique. Action publique internationale en ce sens qu'il s'agit d'un ensemble d'initiatives prises par quelques acteurs

¹ Convention portant création du G5 Sahel du 19 décembre 2014.

(étatiques notamment) pour répondre à un problème public complexe que constitue l'insécurité transnationale dans la région sahélienne. Instrument d'action publique pour considérer le mécanisme institutionnel mis en place en vue de porter et mettre en œuvre de façon cohérente les initiatives prises. Notre usage du groupe de mots "G5 Sahel" est donc double. Il désigne à la fois le contenu – les politiques mises en place – et le contenant institutionnel.

En cela, le G5 Sahel est soluble/traitable en sociologie politique de l'action publique. Ce cadre théorique permet d'étudier le G5 Sahel comme une construction collective d'acteurs multiniveaux en interactions contextualisées². Il s'agit donc d'une analyse centrée sur les acteurs pris dans leur pluralité post-moderne: acteurs étatiques, infra-étatiques, supra-étatiques, trans-étatiques... La question que suggère une telle posture est alors de savoir quels sont les acteurs du G5 Sahel. Il y en a plusieurs catégories. Il y a d'une part les acteurs centraux qui sont à l'origine et aux manettes de l'action publique. Il s'agit d'abord des cinq Etats membres (Burkina-Faso, Mali, Mauritanie, Niger, Tchad), mais aussi de la France qui fait office de parrain de cette action publique, avec l'Union européenne qui en est le bailleur principal. Il s'agit ensuite des acteurs périphériques comme les populations des Etats de la région, les organisations régionales ou des Etats étrangers comme les voisins algériens ou sénégalais ou encore les Etats-Unis.

Dans le cadre de la sociologie de l'action publique, l'analyse des acteurs prend en compte concomitamment leurs ressources, leurs représentations et leurs intérêts ainsi que leurs interactions et les contextes dans lesquels se déroulent ces dernières³. C'est donc sous la loupe de ce cadre théorique que nous regarderons l'avenir du G5 Sahel, actuellement pris dans les fragilités générées par la crise sanitaire liée au Covid-19. Le temps covidien est le

² Patrick Hassenteufel, *Sociologie politique : l'action publique* (Paris: Armand Colin, 2011): 115-156.

³ Ibid.

temps de la crise du Covid-19. Il est un moment de fragilité universelle⁴ qui soumet le monde à une régression historique⁵. Il constitue aujourd’hui un contexte particulier dont les manifestations et les conséquences peuvent avoir des répercussions sérieuses sur l’avenir du G5 Sahel. Déjà fragilisé par la concentration d’insécurité qui la secouent depuis plusieurs années, la région du Sahel⁶ est désormais prise dans des fragilités supplémentaires causées par le Covid-19. A tel point que la question pertinente aujourd’hui en ce qui concerne le Sahel n’est plus vraiment de savoir quelles fragilités le secouent, mais si le temps covidien portera un coup de grâce à une région déjà en prise à de multiples fragilités⁷.

La problématique de cet article trouve ici tout son sens: comment entrevoir l’avenir du G5 Sahel en ces temps de fragilités universelles? Autrement dit, quelles sont les conséquences du temps covidien sur la construction et la mise en œuvre du G5 Sahel? En quoi et comment ces conséquences peuvent-elles façonner (ou non) le futur de cette action publique? Annoncée comme la grande bénéficiaire des retournements géopolitiques du temps covidien, la Chine prendra-t-elle un rôle plus important au Sahel?

Nous y répondrons en trois temps. D’abord, nous jetterons un regard sur l’actualité du G5 Sahel en temps covidien. Car, des conséquences actuelles du Covid-19 sur la crise sécuritaire sahéenne et sur le G5 Sahel, dépendent les changements futurs que ce dernier pourrait subir. Ensuite, nous en

⁴ Expédit B. Ologou, “Penser la fragilité universelle. Notes provisoires sur le temps covidien,” in *Dossier du CIAAF N°2*, 6 mai 2020, <<https://www.ciaaf.org/covid-19/penser-la-fragilite-universelle-notes-provisoires-sur-le-temps-covidien/>>, (Consulté le 19 juillet 2020).

⁵ Winner Abbécy, “Le Covid-19 comme la Peste ! De la régression historique en Europe,” in *Dossier du CIAAF N°2*, 8 mai 2020, <<https://www.ciaaf.org/covid-19/le-covid-19-comme-la-peste-de-la-regression-historique-en-europe/>> (Consulté le 19 juillet 2020).

⁶ Il faut comprendre et considérer l’usage des notions «région», «Sahel» «région du Sahel» et «région sahéenne» dans cet article comme désignant l’espace que recouvre les cinq Etats du G5 Sahel.

⁷ Voir Emmanuel Odilon Koukoubou et Expédit B. Ologou, in *Dossier du CIAAF N°2*, <<https://www.ciaaf.org/covid-19/le-terrorisme-sahelien-en-temps-covidien/>> (Consulté le 19 juillet 2020).

déduirons l'avenir de l'action publique au regard des changements plausibles à court terme. Enfin, nous observerons l'avenir du G5 Sahel au regard des bouleversements géopolitiques que pourrait provoquer la crise sanitaire à long terme.

Les évidences du court terme: les fragilités covidiennees du G5 Sahel

La crise du Covid-19 a renforcé les fragilités déjà existantes du G5 Sahel. Au cœur des controverses et des rivalités de pouvoir entre plusieurs acteurs de la scène régionale et internationale, le G5 Sahel a, à l'avènement de la crise sanitaire, perdu une part de l'attention internationale dont elle était l'objet. En effet, le Sahel est aujourd'hui le théâtre d'une coexistence entre la crise sanitaire et la crise sécuritaire. L'attention des grandes puissances et des Etats de la région n'y est donc plus prioritairement captivée par la seule crise sécuritaire. Celle-ci la partage désormais avec la crise sanitaire.

Durement touchés par la crise du Covid-19 et la crise économique qui s'ensuit, les acteurs internationaux qui étaient les plus investis dans la mise en œuvre du G5 Sahel – la France et plus largement l'Union européenne – sont davantage préoccupés par la relance de leurs économies. S'ils n'ont manifesté aucun désintérêt pour le Sahel et continuent malgré tout d'y intervenir, on peut toutefois craindre un décroissement prochain de leurs efforts en faveur du Sahel et, à tout le moins, observer des retards dans le respect de certains de leurs engagements.

En effet, l'engagement pris par la France au sommet de Pau⁸, de renforcer la Force Barkhane par le déploiement de 220 soldats supplémentaires, a connu du retard dans sa mise en œuvre. Le Président français a parlé d'«aléa [qui]

⁸ Convoqué par le Président Emmanuel Macron dans un contexte où l'action française au Sahel est l'objet de contestations populaires, le Sommet de Pau a réuni autour de lui, le 13 janvier 2020, les cinq Chefs d'Etat du G5 Sahel. Il a été l'occasion de faire comme d'habitude le point de la situation sécuritaire dans la région, mais surtout de confirmer la volonté des Etats de la zone de continuer de bénéficier de l'appui de la France.

ralentit un peu les choses.»⁹ A cela, s'est ajouté le renoncement du Tchad à envoyer un bataillon supplémentaire dans le fuseau Centre de la Force conjointe du G5 Sahel (FC-G5S)¹⁰. La décision du Tchad est liée à des pertes enregistrées par l'armée tchadienne attaquée par les terroristes de Boko Haram dans le sud du pays¹¹. En outre, il faut relever le retard observé dans le déploiement des Forces Takuba dont le rôle est de conseiller, d'assister et d'accompagner «les Forces armées maliennes, en coordination avec les partenaires du G5 Sahel et d'autres acteurs internationaux sur le terrain.»¹²

Le G5 Sahel subit les conséquences de la fragilisation de ses bailleurs/partenaires. Malheureusement, ces Etats membres n'auront pas non plus les moyens de suppléer les retards et revirements de leurs partenaires étrangers. Déjà cités parmi les pays les plus pauvres de la planète, ces Etats ont dû recourir à des mesures relativement drastiques pour lutter contre le Covid-19: fermeture des frontières, et de plusieurs commerces, couvre-feu...¹³. Ces mesures ont davantage fragilisé l'économie de ces pays, tout en mettant un frein aux échanges commerciaux dans l'espace communautaire. Plusieurs acteurs du commerce local, de l'informel, voient ainsi leur pouvoir d'achat décroître du jour au lendemain¹⁴. En marge de la crise sécuritaire, les Etats de la région ont donc à faire face à ces conséquences économiques du Covid-19. C'est aussi dans

⁹ "Emmanuel Macron sur RFI. Nous devons la solidarité à l'Afrique face au coronavirus," *Radio France Internationale*, 15 avril 2020, <<https://www.rfi.fr/fr/podcast/20200415/emmanuel-macron-rfi-afrique-raoult-coronavirus-coviddette>> (Consulté le 18 juillet 2020).

¹⁰ Le fuseau Centre de la force conjointe du G5 Sahel correspond à la zone des trois frontières du Liptaco-Gourma entre le Mali, le Burkina et le Niger.

¹¹ "Tchad: face aux djihadistes, les coups de colère, de com' et de bluff du président Idriss Déby," *Le Monde*, 16 avril 2020, <https://www.lemonde.fr/afrique/article/2020/04/16/tchad-face-aux-djihadistes-les-coups-decolere-de-com-et-de-bluff-du-president-idriss-deby_6036841_3212.html> (Consulté le 18 juillet 2020).

¹² Il s'agit d'une force européenne de 3000 hommes devant s'inscrire dans le commandement de la force Barkhane. Voir Secrétaire général des Nations Unies, *Rapport sur la situation au Mali et au Sahel* (Juin 2020), S/2020/373.

¹³ Koukoubou et Ologou, "Le terrorisme sahélien en temps covidien," 9.

¹⁴ Ibid.

ce contexte que le Mali, épicerie de la crise sécuritaire, se retrouve confronter à une crise politique profonde, faisant suite aux élections législatives de mars-avril 2020¹⁵. Les manifestants qui réclament la démission du Président de la République Ibrahim Boubacar Kéïta restent fermés à toutes formes de concession. Cela vient en rajouter aux incertitudes actuelles du Sahel.

Le rapport du Secrétaire général de l'ONU sur la situation au Mali et comptant pour le deuxième trimestre de l'année 2020 qualifiait déjà les effets du Covid-19 de «déstabilisateurs»¹⁶ pour la situation sécuritaire dans la région sahélienne. Dans ce rapport, Antonio Guterres indique que la pandémie «est venue compliquer une situation déjà difficile au Mali et dans la région du Sahel. Elle a ralenti l'activité économique, aggravé la crise humanitaire et l'insécurité et eu des répercussions politiques.»¹⁷ Un mois plus tôt, le même Secrétaire général déclarait déjà dans son rapport sur la Force conjointe du Groupe des cinq pays du Sahel que «la situation catastrophique dans la région du Sahel est encore aggravée par la propagation [du] Covid-19 en Afrique, que des groupes terroristes exploitent dans leur propagande comme dans leur action, ce qui pourrait être lourd de conséquences pour la région.»¹⁸ Ces déclarations témoignent d'une aggravation potentielle des conditions sécuritaires dans la région. Cette aggravation passe donc par un renforcement des fragilités et une

¹⁵ "Mali: cinq questions pour comprendre la crise politique et sécuritaire qui embrase Bamako," *Franceinfo*, 16 juillet 2020, <https://www.francetvinfo.fr/monde/afrique/mali/mali-cinq-questions-pour-comprendre-la-crise-politique-et-securitaire-qui-embrase-bamako_4043975> (18 juillet 2020).

¹⁶ Secrétaire général des Nations Unies, Rapport S/2020/373.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Secrétaire général des Nations Unies, *Rapport sur la Force conjointe du Groupe des cinq pays du Sahel* (8 mai 2020), S/2020/373.

fragilisation des renforts qui voient se poursuivre les attaques terroristes malgré la propagation du Covid-19¹⁹.

Les constances du moyen terme: les augures des ajustements incrémentaux

S’inspirant de Peter Hall²⁰, Patrick Hassenteufel a identifié quatre dimensions interdépendantes du changement dans l’action publique²¹. Non hiérarchisées, à la fois indépendantes et interdépendantes, ces quatre dimensions offrent un excellent outil d’analyse des changements observés dans une action publique. Elles sont présentées dans le tableau de Hassenteufel reproduit ci-dessous.

Tableau N° 1: Quatre dimensions interdépendantes du changement

Dimensions du changement	Niveau d’action publique	Impacts potentiels sur les autres dimensions
Instruments (usage et création)	Modalités concrètes (mise en œuvre)	- Modification des interactions entre acteurs - Rend possible la reformulation des objectifs
Acteurs (renforcement/ affaiblissement,	Politique (au sens de Polity: rapports de pouvoir)	- Usage et définition des instruments - Redéfinition du cadre

¹⁹ Voir plus de détails dans Koukoubou et Ologou, “Le terrorisme sahélien en temps covidien.”

²⁰ Voir les trois ordres de changement de Peter Hall dans Peter Hall, “Policy Paradigm, Social Learning and the State,” *Comparative Politics* 25, 3 (1993): 275-296.

²¹ Patrick Hassenteufel, *Sociologie politique: l’action publique*, 247.

émergence/disparition)		institutionnel - Redéfinition des objectifs
Cadre d'interaction (règles du jeu institutionnelles)	Institutionnel	- Modalités d'usage et de définition des instruments - Redéfinition des positions et des ressources des acteurs - Modalités de définition des objectifs
Orientation de la politique publique (hiérarchie des objectifs et système de représentation sous-jacent)	Cognitif	- Usage et définition des instruments - Redéfinition des positions et des ressources des acteurs - Redéfinition du cadre institutionnel

Source: Patrick Hassenteufel, *Sociologie politique: l'action publique*, (Paris: Armand Colin, 2011), 247.

Pour ce qui concerne l'orientation de l'action publique, l'adaptation au contexte économique créé par le Covid-19 peut renforcer la tendance à une exclusive militarisation au détriment du volet lié au développement. Fondé sur le nexus défense-développement²², le G5 Sahel était, à ses débuts, porté

²² Le G5 lui-même parle de sécurité-développement. Et la littérature scientifique et journalistique a jusque-là répété le même vocabulaire. Ici, la sécurité fait référence exclusivement au volet militaire. Or, en ajoutant le volet développement, le G5 Sahel prône en fait une sécurité humaine qui couvre à la fois le volet militaire et le volet non militaire. Nous trouvons donc antithétique de mettre sécurité-développement. En lieu et place, nous préférons et emploierons défense-développement.

par une ambition plus développementale que militaire. Mais il a opéré un virage important, priorisant désormais presque exclusivement l'action militaire. Un fonctionnaire du ministère nigérien du développement qui en était le Secrétaire permanent a ainsi vu son mandat brutalement écourté pour être remplacé par un profil plus militarisant²³. L'action de développement a tellement marqué le pas par rapport à l'action militaire que la Force conjointe du G5 Sahel (FC-G5S) qui n'est en fait qu'une composante du G5 Sahel se confond avec ce dernier dans le discours de nombreux acteurs²⁴. En parallèle, les partenaires étrangers ont créé une Alliance Sahel censée s'occuper du volet développement, mais qui jusque-là, peine encore à donner des résultats probants.

Si déjà en temps ordinaire, les différents acteurs avaient déjà délaissé l'un des piliers du nexus fondateur du G5 Sahel au profit de l'autre, il est difficilement possible d'envisager qu'en temps extraordinaire, ils en reviennent à l'équilibre souhaitable. La fragilité économique mondiale générée par la crise pandémique du Covid-19 touchant la capacité financière des bailleurs du G5 Sahel, on peut donc affirmer que la marginalisation du volet développement se poursuivra au même titre que la priorisation de la militarisation. Nous pouvons donc dire que l'orientation de l'action publique ne changera pas fondamentalement à moyen terme. Pas plus que ne changeront les instruments. Tout au plus, assisterons-nous à quelques réajustements incrémentaux²⁵ – si cela s'avérait nécessaire – mais sans

²³ Nicolas Desgrais, sous la direction de Sada Hugo, "Cinq ans après, une radioscopie du G5/Sahel. Des réformes nécessaires de l'architecture et du processus décisionnel," *Fondation pour la recherche stratégique*, mars 2019, <<https://www.frstrategie.org/web/documents/programmes/observatoire-du-monde-arabo-musulman-et-dusahel/publications/201913.pdf>> (18 juillet 2020).

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ La théorie de l'incrémentalisme a été développée par Charles Lindblom en critique de l'analyse en terme de choix rationnel. L'auteur estime que les décideurs suivent plutôt un modèle de débrouille. Il initie alors la *science of muddling through*, science de la débrouille pour analyser la décision. Voir Charles Lindblom, "The Science of muddling through," *Public Administration Review*, 19 (1959): 79-88.

jamais fondamentalement remettre en cause l'orientation générale de l'action publique.

On peut en dire de même pour les acteurs et le cadre d'interaction. L'un des reproches souvent faits au G5 Sahel tient au caractère exclusif du compromis qui en est à la base. Dans la littérature scientifique, médiatique ainsi que dans le discours politique, l'on se demande régulièrement pourquoi le Sénégal ou encore l'Algérie n'en font pas partie. Dans les Etats côtiers vers lesquels se déplacent progressivement le terrorisme sahélien, l'on pense à une adhésion au G5 Sahel; ou à une reprise d'influence de la CEDEAO (Communauté économique des Etats de l'Afrique de l'Ouest) et de l'Union africaine qui se sont vues marginalisées dans la construction et la mise en œuvre du G5 Sahel qu'elles considèrent comme un concurrent illégitime²⁶. Il existe donc une controverse récurrente et constante sur l'ouverture ou l'extension du compromis à l'origine du G5 Sahel d'une part et sa disparition au profit d'un mécanisme sous régional ou régional d'autre part.

Malgré la controverse, le temps covidien risque de ne rien changer dans la configuration actuelle des acteurs. Les Etats à l'origine du G5 Sahel et leurs partenaires privilégiés (la France prioritairement) ne semblent pas dans la dynamique d'ouverture. L'adhésion au mécanisme est d'ailleurs verrouillée dès l'origine dans son acte constitutif²⁷. Mieux, toutes les initiatives d'ouverture sont prises à la marge et en parallèle du G5 Sahel. C'est ainsi qu'en lieu et place d'une extension ou d'une disparition du G5 Sahel, les acteurs ont préféré la création d'un Partenariat pour la Sécurité et la Stabilité du Sahel (P3S) lancé sous l'égide de la France et de l'Allemagne lors

²⁶ Niagalé Bagayoko, "Le multilatéralisme sécuritaire africain à l'épreuve de la crise sahélienne," *Centre FrancoPaix en résolution des conflits et missions de paix*, Rapport du projet Stabiliser le Mali, Juin 2019, 46-47.

²⁷ Voir la Convention portant création du G5 Sahel.

du Sommet du G7 à Biarritz (France) en août 2019²⁸. Et cinq mois plus tard en janvier 2020, ils ont en plus lancé, une nouvelle initiative: la Coalition pour le Sahel, présentée comme «une réponse collective et solidaire»²⁹ ayant «vocation à rassembler largement, avec le G5 Sahel, tous les pays, organisations internationales et institutions apportant un soutien à la sécurité, à la stabilité et au développement au Sahel.»³⁰

Toutes ces initiatives parallèles viennent en rajouter à ce que Nicolas Desgrais appelle l'embouteillage institutionnel au Sahel. A l'embouteillage institutionnel, s'ajoute maintenant un embrouillage volontairement créé dans le but de maintenir coûte que coûte le compromis initial de l'action publique. Le G5 Sahel résiste donc jusque-là à un changement au niveau de la configuration des acteurs. Les ajustements opérés sont pour l'instant incrémentaux et à la marge. On peut donc imaginer qu'au moins à court et à moyen terme, cette même logique continuera de guider l'action des acteurs. Il y a donc peu de chance que la configuration des acteurs du (et autour du) G5 Sahel change dans un avenir plus ou moins proche. Elle ne serait envisageable que dans le cadre d'un monumental mais hypothétique revirement de l'ordre mondial.

Les incertitudes du long terme: l'avenir du Sahel sera-t-il chinois?

Le nouvel ordre mondial post-covidien sera-t-il chinois? Le temps covidien a été fécond en réflexions sur l'ordre mondial et le rôle qui y serait désormais dévolu à la Chine³¹. La position dominante dans ces réflexions est celle qui

²⁸ *G7 Biarritz: Conférence de presse conjointe consacrée au Sahel* (video-recording), directed by Elysée, <<https://www.elysee.fr/emmanuel-macron/2019/08/26/g7-biarritz-conference-de-presse-conjointe-consacree-au-sahel>> (19 juillet 2020).

²⁹ "La coalition pour le Sahel, une réponse collective et solidaire," *Ambassade de France en Espagne*, 17 juillet 2020, <<https://www.ambafrance.org/La-Coalition-pour-le-Sahel-une-reponse-collective-et-solidaire-10465>> (Consulté le 18 juillet 2020).

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Voir entre autres à cet effet, Thierry S. Bidouzo, "La crise du Covid-19 ou la gestation d'un nouvel ordre mondial?", *Dossier du CiAAF N°2*, 7 mai 2020, <<https://www.ciaaf.org/derniers-articles/la-crise-du-covid-19-ou-la-gestation-dun-nouvel-ordre-mondial/>> (19 juillet 2020);

propulse la Chine au seuil d'un nouvel ordre international post-covidien³². Thierry Bidouzo signe l'une des réflexions les plus élaborées en la matière en observant d'une part que déjà, «l'ordre mondial n'est plus ce qu'il était» et qu'il «sera encore moins ce qu'il est». Croisant le déclin de l'Occident qui a provoqué «une communauté internationale sans commandement» avec l'implantation de la Chine comme une puissance économique durable et un acteur incontournable de la gouvernance mondiale, il en arrive à conclure qu'«entre la puissance dominante déclinante [l'Occident] et la puissance dominée montante [la Chine], la crise du Covid-19 peut être un accélérateur de passage de témoin.»³³

Face à une telle hypothèse, nous pouvons valablement nous demander si le chamboulement éventuel et supposé de l'ordre international post-covidien provoquerait une remise en cause de la configuration des acteurs du G5 Sahel. Autrement dit, il est question de savoir si dans un futur plus ou moins éloigné, la Chine prendra une place influente et importante dans la lutte

Pascal Boniface, "La crise du coronavirus va-t-elle profiter à la Chine?", *Edito*, 1^{er} avril 2020, <<https://www.iris-france.org/145768-la-crise-du-coronavirus-va-t-elle-profiter-a-la-chine/>> (19 juillet 2020); Pascal Boniface, "La faiblesse du monde occidental a été un choc," *Quartier Général*, 1^{er} mai 2020, <<https://qg.media/2020/05/01/la-faiblesse-du-monde-occidental-a-ete-un-choc-par-pascal-boniface/>> (19 juillet 2020); "Après la pandémie liée au Coronavirus: un ordre mondial à réinventer," *Le Monde*, 30 avril 2020, <https://www.lemonde.fr/idees/articles/2020/04/30/apres-la-pandemie-liee-au-coronavirus-un-ordre-mondial-a-reinventer_6038253_3232> (19 juillet 2020).

³² Les positions exprimées peuvent être classées en trois catégories. En plus de celle développée ci-dessus et qui fait de la Chine la prochaine première puissance, il existe une position beaucoup plus minoritaire qui réfute l'idée d'un nouvel ordre international post-covidien. Voir à cet effet: Nicolas Tenzer, "Débat: Il n'y aura pas de nouvel ordre international post-pandémique," 24/05/2020, <<https://www.theconversation.com/debat-il-ny-aura-pas-de-nouvel-ordre-international-post-pandemie-138983>> (19 juillet 2020). Une troisième position se montre plus prudente et parle soit d'une période transitoire ou d'un d'une gouvernance dominée par plusieurs acteurs. Voir à cet effet la position de Expédit Ologou qui parle d'un ordre «sino-américain ou américano-chinois» auquel devrait se greffer un troisième larron pour une gouvernance mondiale par un triumvirat: Thierry Bidouzo et Expédit Ologou, "La Chine au seuil du monde? L'entrechoc des idées," *Dossier du CiAAF N°2*, <<https://www.youtu.be/GaFCI4gA-A>> (19 juillet 2020).

³³ Thierry Bidouzo, "La crise du Covid-19 ou la gestation d'un nouvel ordre mondial?"

contre l'insécurité transnationale au Sahel en général et dans le G5 Sahel en particulier. Alors que la France sort du Covid-19 plus fragilisée que la Chine, peut-on imaginer un décroissement de l'influence française et un accroissement de la puissance chinoise au Sahel? Pour paraphraser Thierry Bidouzo, le Covid-19 sera-t-il un accélérateur de passage de témoin entre la France et la Chine dans la gouvernance sécuritaire au Sahel?

A cette question, il n'existe pas de réponse péremptoire. Le temps covidien étant un temps des incertitudes et de tous les possibles, il serait imprudent d'écarter sans réserve quelque hypothèse. Ceci dit, nous pouvons néanmoins avancer une réponse à la question.

Ici, il faut commencer par remarquer que la stratégie de puissance de la Chine se déploie de plus en plus sur le terrain militaire. Plus connue pour son *soft power* économique, la Chine développe depuis quelques années un intérêt de plus en plus croissant pour les questions de maintien de la paix en Afrique. En 2018 par exemple, l'Armée chinoise a effectué des manœuvres au Cameroun, au Gabon, au Ghana et au Nigéria³⁴. Ses unités médicales ont renforcé les capacités de prise en charge des victimes des combats des armées éthiopienne, sierra-léonaise, soudanaise et zambienne³⁵. Plus précisément au Sahel, la Chine est également présente sur différentes formes. Elle y a déployé un bataillon, dans le cadre de la Mission multidimensionnelle intégrée des Nations unies pour la stabilisation au Mali (MINUSMA), installé à Gao³⁶. Elle contribue à l'opérationnalisation de la

³⁴ Paul Nantulya, "Les activités stratégiques croissantes de la Chine en Afrique reposent sur le hard power chinois," *Centre d'Etudes stratégiques de l'Afrique*, 7 février 2019, <<https://africacenter.org/fr/spotlight/les-activites-strategiques-croissantes-de-la-chine-en-afrique-reposent-sur-le-hard-powerchinois/>> (20 juillet 2020).

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Souleymane Diallo, "Paix et sécurité en Afrique de l'Ouest: la Chine s'implique au Mali," *Institut d'Etudes politiques et stratégiques*, 22 décembre 2013, <http://www.ieps-cipsao.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=100:paix-et-securite-en-afrique-de-louest-la-chine-simplique-au-mali&catid=36:actualites&Itemid=48> (20 juillet 2020).

force conjointe du G5 Sahel avec une somme de 45 millions de dollars US³⁷. Le décaissement de cette somme a été annoncé en 2019 dans un contexte où l'Union européenne avait décidé de convertir les 100 millions de dollars de contribution qu'elle a promis à l'opérationnalisation du G5 Sahel, en fournitures de gilets pare-balles, en soutien logistique, en livraison de carburant, en ravitaillement etc.³⁸ La Chine a donc profité des tergiversations européennes pour marquer un nouveau coup diplomatique. Mieux, elle est allée plus loin en décaissant 1,5 millions de dollars US pour soutenir le fonctionnement du secrétariat permanent du G5 Sahel³⁹.

En clair, la volonté de puissance de la Chine en Afrique et plus précisément au Sahel ne fait plus l'ombre d'aucun doute. Inscrite dans son vaste projet de «La route de la soie», cette stratégie de (re)conquête diplomatique vise d'une part à accroître l'influence de la Chine en Afrique, mais également à protéger ses intérêts économiques sur le continent. Pour ce qui concerne le Sahel, les entreprises chinoises construisent des lignes ferroviaires pour relier le Mali qui est un pays enclavé, aux ports de Dakar et de Conakry. Mais certaines de ces infrastructures traversent des zones d'influence des groupes terroristes au nord du Mali. La sécurité des investissements et des milliers d'employés des chemins de fer chinois dans la zone peut donc justifier l'activisme de Pékin dans la région. Le Burkina Faso, membre du G5 Sahel, est également devenu récemment un partenaire stratégique de la Chine, en retirant sa reconnaissance à Taïwan.

La Chine montrait donc déjà un intérêt stratégique croissant pour la zone des cinq pays du G5 Sahel. Et l'accroissement de son influence coïncide avec une désaffection populaire pour l'action française dans la région du Sahel. Perçue comme un acteur profiteur ou un fauteur de trouble dans la zone, la

³⁷ Emmanuel DUPUY, "La France et la Chine, rivaux «systémiques» ou partenaires «stratégiques» dans le domaine de la sécurité en Afrique?," *Africapresse*, 9 mars 2020, <<https://www.africapresse.paris/Emmanuel-DUPUY-IPSE-La-France-et-la-Chine-rivaux-systemiques-ou-partenaires>> (Consulté le 20 juillet 2020).

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ibid.

France subit un rejet dans l'opinion publique africaine et une contestation de plus en plus grandissante, portée par des acteurs transnationaux comme des organisations de la société civile ou des figures individuelles emblématiques comme la star de la musique africaine Salif Kéïta. En plus de cette désaffection, la France n'a pas suffisamment de moyens pour assumer le statut spécial et la responsabilité particulière qu'elle semble revendiquer au Sahel. C'est pourquoi son option vise de plus en plus à impliquer l'Union européenne et d'autres puissances dans la gestion de la crise sécuritaire au Sahel, tout en se ménageant une place importante dans le dispositif.

On la voit donc difficilement accepter de perdre la main au profit de la Chine au Sahel. C'est aujourd'hui l'une des seules régions au monde où l'ancienne puissance coloniale peut encore prétendre conserver une influence réelle sur les acteurs gouvernementaux, même si elle subit une certaine contestation populaire. Dans l'hypothèse même d'un changement de l'ordre international, elle voudra se maintenir dans cette zone d'influence qui lui servira de levier pour continuer à peser dans la gouvernance sécuritaire mondiale. C'est dire que l'avenir du G5 Sahel peut se jouer dans les interactions géopolitiques entre la France et la Chine. La première y jouera la dernière carte de sa survie diplomatique; la seconde y jouera une nouvelle carte de son rayonnement diplomatique.

Conclusion

La naissance du G5 Sahel a suscité des questionnements sur sa pertinence. Ne serait-ce pas un «machin mort-né» ou juste une «organisation de plus»? Les six années de son action n'ont pas fondamentalement effacé les appréhensions. Le G5 Sahel reste encore aujourd'hui une action publique indéterminée, qui se cherche encore une place dans la marmaille de politiques publiques (inter)nationales en cours d'exécution au Sahel. Incapables de le financer, ses acteurs principaux comptent sur la générosité de bailleurs étrangers dont les promesses de financement peinent à se

concrétiser. On en était à ces atermoiements quand la crise du Covid-19 est venue en rajouter avec sa couche de fragilités.

L'avenir du G5 Sahel se trouve donc actuellement pris dans les fers de l'incertitude totale. Va-t-il se jouer avec la France, avec la Chine ou avec d'autres acteurs? Il est impossible à l'étape actuelle de donner une réponse intangible. Dans ce contexte, il est également inutile de s'engager dans un exercice de recommandations. Ici, l'objet d'étude est si mouvant, si imprévisible et si dépendant des options géopolitiques et géostratégiques des Etats qu'il est imprudent de s'avancer sur le terrain des propositions de solutions pour remodeler l'avenir du G5 Sahel. Nous faisons donc le choix de l'observation plus durable des événements plutôt que de l'implication experte par des propositions.

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Human Security and the Anarchy of COVID–19 in Regional and Global Cooperation

Penine UWIMBABAZI

u.penine@gmail.com

Abstract: *The outbreak and persistence of COVID-19 is revealing not only substantial global health crises, but also an unexpected destruction of social, political and economic status at an international level. Furthermore, pressure and frustrations as to how to manage the pandemic are leading to unexpected reactions. While it is not yet fully understood what the consequences of the virus will be, the daily news already presents uncomfortable realities, including different forms of geopolitical conflict in the cooperation against the spread of the pandemic, and tendencies towards discrimination which cause human rights violations, at the same time as hiding behind a veil of cooperation and regional identity. This paper raises questions on the collective action of the on-going virus control, and assumes that the reality of the virus has been a trigger for racial discrimination and issues related to social unrest. Could this be an opportunity to rethink and give a different meaning to the politics of global and regional corroboration? There is a need for openness and appreciation as to what COVID-19 has to teach the world. This discussion is motivated by the injustice and mistreatment of people of different colour in different countries such as China, among others, and regional misunderstandings affecting any collective action in the process of virus control. As it raises a number of different questions in this area, this paper would like to stimulate a re-evaluation of the current and future idea of global and regional cooperation.*

Key words: *cooperation, human security, violence, international political relations.*

Introduction

The outbreak of COVID-19, which is generally believed to have started in Wuhan, is by now understood to be one of the biggest threats which has enveloped the world. Most significantly, safety to human health has been undermined, the global economy upset as a result of the obvious threat to human social economic instability, and political leadership and accountability have been challenged. Following warnings from scientists

that this was a highly transmittable virus, the World Health Organisation obliged the imposition of measures that would help to stop the spread of the pandemic, and these have been received and responded to differently by different nations and societies.

The pandemic has the facility to cross any border, and it has managed to travel, affect and infect people in almost all countries of the world. As in all other parts of the world, the East African Region has taken collective measures to curb the pandemic and its immediate consequences. Measures have included closing borders against human movement, and this was not an easy decision to take and implement due to the geo-political nature of the region. Consequently, the measures implemented were at times accompanied by suspicions of who might be carrying the virus, dependent on which country announced the first case or in which country cases were highest. This is not particularly surprising, especially since there was already experience of 'the blame game' being played out, mainly between the United States of America and China, as to who was responsible for the outbreak of the virus. Though silent at a political level, this blame appeared very real as some states were judged as not being 'serious' with regard to the measures suggested by the World Health Organisation.

Moreover, the pandemic has also exposed a degree of fragility in international relations. Global discourse questions not only who is responsible for the outbreak of the virus, and consequently the death of millions of people, and for freezing the world economy and the movement of peoples and goods, but also questions how capable humans are to fight against such crises. A frequently-cited example is the United States' allegations that China was the instigator of the pandemic, and the ensuing stereotyping, as well as the discriminatory behaviours observed from different countries in the name of COVID-19 preventive measures. This is the focus of the current discussions, which question the status of regional and global collaboration especially in times of common problems such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This paper emphasises the need, now more than

ever, for openness to global collaboration through strengthening cooperation and respecting the rights of global humanity.

1. Human security and inequality due to the COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 crises offer a chance to anchor human security in the lives of the people and not in the weapons that states often wield. The Kashmir Observer, published on 4th May 2020, argues that security lies in reducing poverty, and in providing growth and opportunity, access to education, affordable health care, a cleaner environment, and human rights.¹

Infection, death, lockdowns, hunger, and economic collapse have tested the traditional concept of national security – which is usually understood as meaning that ‘the people are secure when there is a presence of military, political, and economic power’. Moreover, the current outbreak of COVID-19 has proven that the priority budget allocated and spent on national security in many countries has not made people safer during this time of COVID-19. Expensive and lethal weapon systems are currently no help at a time when hospitals are grappling with a lack of ventilators, doctors, and masks and other basic infrastructure, a reality to many societies including those known as economic superpowers.

The COVID-19 virus has proven that health crises will sink millions more people into poverty as growth rates plummet, exposing the basic weakness of the least-ready countries, leading to polarisation of regional states, scapegoating and xenophobia, and racism.

Furthermore, while COVID-19 continues to be unpredictable in our life-time, it is ruthlessly exposing the gaps between the ‘haves’ and ‘have nots’, both within and between countries as well as communities. It finds a comfortable stalking ground when more than half of the world’s people lack essential

¹ Saad Hafiz, “Covid–19 Pandemic & Human Security,” *Kashmir Observer*, 4 May 2020, <<https://kashmirobsvr.net/2020/05/04/covid-19-pandemic-human-security/>> (accessed on 26th June 2020).

health services and have little or no social protection. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) along with other analysts predicts that although all people are exposed to COVID-19, it is the vulnerable people, the poor, who will pay the highest price. Thus, the UNDP estimates for global human development that education, health and living standards are on course to decline for the first time since the concept was developed in 1990.²

‘The World Bank has warned that the virus could push between 40 and 60 million into extreme poverty with Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia hardest hit. The international Labour Organisation (ILO) also estimates that half of working people could lose their jobs and the virus could cost the global economy US\$10 trillion. The world food programme says 265 million will face crisis level of hunger unless direct action is taken.’³

One of the measures of slowing down the spread of the pandemic was the closure of different public and private sectors including education. With school closures and the divide in distance learning, due to lack of proper infrastructure, the UNDP estimates indicate that 86% of primary school age children in low human development countries are currently not getting an education, compared to just 20% in countries with very high human development. Moreover, the UNDP estimates that effective school drop-out rates could regress to levels not seen since the 1980s – the largest reversal ever – taking us back to a time before the Millennium Development Goals, and threatening the hard work and progress of the past 30 years.

2. Regional and global collaboration during COVID-19 crises

COVID-19 exposes the weakness in every society and widens the persistence of inequality in almost every country, thus COVID-19 outbreaks are a trigger

² “Features”, UNDP. 2020. *Coronavirus vs. Inequality*, <<https://feature.undp.org/coronavirus-vs-inequality/>> (accessed 24 June 2020).

³ *Ibid.*

on the moving ground of international relations and collaboration. What has been evident is that, while the global economy is suffering, global social politics has also been devastated. As mentioned above, COVID-19 has already hit the news headlines, due to examples in the media such as that of the US administration which has been taken as an illustration of softness in its response to the virus: choosing rather to blame not only China but also the leadership of World Health Organisation (WHO). Mulikita and Vairon argue that the United States, 'rather than promoting the laudable vision of collective human security, cynically undermines the WHO in order to punish China by erroneously alleging the WHO's director-general, the first from the African continent, lacks the requisite impartiality and professionalism of an international civil servant.'⁴

Although this had a strong impact on international relations and on the bilateral relationship between the United States of America and the Republic of China, in the midst of this pandemic, thousands of ordinary citizens are losing their lives daily, and the economy is collapsing due to the hold of the pandemic.

Knight and Oriola indicate that the pandemic has exposed the deep gaps in Euro-American countries indicating that people from the African diaspora are four times more likely than whites to die due to COVID-19. Although there should be a clear analysis on why this gap exists, Knight and Oriola quote the national statistics in the UK, which indicate that wealth, health, and education are, among others, factors contributing to that.⁵

COVID-19 has shone the spotlight on indecisive leadership and government accountability, while directing judgement for misguided priorities against

⁴ Michael N. Mulikita and Lionel Vairon, "COVID-19: Multilateralism and the quest for collective human security," *CGTN*, 2 May 2020 <<https://news.cgtn.com/news/2020-05-02/COVID-19-Multilateralism-and-the-quest-for-collective-human-security-Q9SJ3QvweQ/index.html>> (accessed 24 June 2020).

⁵ Andy Knight and Temitope B. Oriola, "Covid-19, George Floyd and Human Security," *African Security*, 13, no. 2 (2020): 111-115.

many government developmental plans. It has also had an impact on international politics and relations, ranging from possible rivalry over who is responsible for the outbreak of the pandemic to who comes first with the COVID-19 vaccine.

2.1 EAC Regional collaboration against COVID-19

From the first wave of the pandemic, there was a global fear about the capacity of African governments to deal with COVID-19. This is aggravated by the media, who touch on the truth and reality of poor infrastructure in most African communities. Knowing the reality, the fear was felt keenly by African governments, which sounded the alarm in the search for survival against this pandemic. By 30th March 2020, the East Africa countries had reported cases of coronavirus. Like any other countries around the world, a state of emergency was declared, mostly with lockdowns, quarantine, curfews, and social distancing measures to prevent the spread, imposed on each East African country as communicated by the WHO.

The East African Community (EAC) secretariat convened a joint meeting of Ministers of Health responsible for EAC Affairs to deliberate on joint and coordinated EAC responses to COVID-19 on 25th March 2020. Regional joint responses were agreed upon, with the aim of ensuring a joint and well-coordinated mechanism to fight COVID-19 in the region; facilitating the movement of goods and services in the region; minimizing the number of infected people; minimizing morbidity and mortality; reducing the burden on health systems; ensuring that the region has adequate capacity for surveillance; ensuring the region has timely access to medical therapeutics; mitigating fundamental impacts of the pandemic on the various economic and social sectors and facilitating a harmonized and coherent

implementation of priorities that will be instrumental for economic recovery in the short-term.⁶

However, it was noted that, in some countries, the measures agreed were not respected in the same way at the same time. Through knowing the reality of each state's own status with regard to its health facilities, and social political status, it is almost a matter of individual state survival. In mid-April as the pandemic was being identified and steadily increasing in the region, some counties blamed others for not taking it seriously enough and thus causing the number of COVID-19 cases to rise. While other countries in the region refused to follow the global measures, others had no choice than to focus on their own strategies to control the spread of the pandemic, which again raised some suspicions and mistrust on what was meant to be a joint fight in the control of the virus.

3. COVID-19 – a trigger for racism and violation of human security

The continuation of challenges and huge human losses, as well as social and economic losses due to COVID-19, has tempted and motivated this discussion to challenge and question the stability of the often-discussed global collaboration. The pandemic has exposed how real and sustainable global or region collaboration are, and opens up a discussion as to whether we could talk about it as a concept rather than a practice. How much global citizens would manage or fight a common enemy, is still a question exposed on the table for analysis, yet this requires basically a common understanding and an acceptance of global humanity which might or might not be realistic. A well-known example is the wide-spread discrimination that took place from April 2020 in China, especially in Guangzhou, as they were campaigning for a compulsory coronavirus test for Africans, and ordered them to self-isolate while hotels, shops, restaurants and public transport restricted them.

⁶ East African Community COVID-19 Response Plan, April 2020, East Africa Community, version 5, 27th April, 2020, <<https://www.tralac.org/documents/resources/covid-19/regional/3466-eac-covid-19-response-plan-april-2020/file.html>> (accessed 26 June 2020).

Why only Africans and no other national, is a constant question, with an answer that none of those would openly speak about, yet this continuously exposed the conspiracy of racism and xenophobia. Although the Chinese government, just like any other government such as those in Europe and America, claim 'zero tolerance' for discrimination, in this case related to racism, reports indicate that the authorities of Guangdong followed Africans to their homes and stopped them in the street, forcing them to self-isolate at home with surveillance cameras or alarms installed outside their apartments, even though there was no scientific proof that Africans were carriers of COVID-19.⁷

It was widely reported on the news that, in other provinces of China, cases of police and local officials and hospitals harassing Africans were witnessed. Reports of discrimination against Africans, mainly in China, sparked outrage among African communities around the world, to the extent that some African governments delivered direct messages to the Chinese ambassadors in their countries to stop the mistreatment indicated. On a positive note though, African countries collaborated at least in voicing their position on the matter. According to Human Rights Watch, more than 300 human rights groups and nearly 1,800 activists in Africa sent an open letter to the African Union calling for 'immediate action' over the xenophobic, racist and inhumane treatment of Africans in China.⁸

The attacks were not only directed against ordinary citizens, but also against the leaders of the so-called great nations. Again, the United States leader, Trump, openly attacked the WHO and specifically its leader Dr. Tedros, as not only the first WHO leader from the African continent but also as unprofessional in the manner in which he dealt with the crises. This sent out

⁷ Human Rights Watch, "China: Covid-19 discrimination Against Africans," 5 May, 2020, <<https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/05/05/china-covid-19-discrimination-against-africans>> (accessed 24 June 2020).

⁸ Ibid.

a message as to the way in which some leaders view other leaders of African origin.

Racial bias was also obvious when discussing the search for a vaccine against COVID-19: two French doctors made a public announcement about using Africans for the clinical trials of the vaccine.⁹ Although these attitudes undermine the multilateralist approach to the pandemic, they also open up opportunities for the world to establish a genuine cooperation which requires team work rather than pointing the finger at who is not doing what to whose expectations, and to focus on basic human needs. There is a need to see global interconnectedness not only for this COVID-19 pandemic but in any other challenge that collective efforts are needed to win the battle.

According to Burron, the basic human needs approach is being politicised.¹⁰ It springs from an unwillingness to blame violence or social actors for the pathologies in which they participate, and also from a refusal to see individuals and social groups as mere manifestations of uncontrollable external forces or structures. But this rejection does not constitute a political philosophy; it creates a space in which political philosophy may be constructed. Referring to basic human need theories, Galtung, indicates that when a basic human need is not satisfied, some kind of fundamental collapse will take place. Galtung identifies two broad categories of social disintegration; one of which signifies lack of participation, apathy, and withdrawal. Every human has a common need, even more so during this process in the fight to put an end to COVID-19; the current common needs require understanding, but at the same time must respect a commitment to curb the pandemic and any future ones that could occur.

⁹ Nur Özkan Erbay, "Time for Africa to rise up against European racism," *Daily Sabah*, 5 April 2020 <<https://www.dailysabah.com/politics/news-analysis/time-for-africa-to-rise-up-against-european-racism> (accessed 26 June 2020).

¹⁰ John W. Burton, *Deviance, Terrorism, and War: The Process of Solving Unsolved Social and Political Problems* (New York: St Martin's Press, 1979).

4. The anarchy of COVID-19 and human security

COVID-19 is, not only with regard to health crises but also to human security crises, depriving humans of their freedom from fear, but also their freedom from want and freedom to live with dignity.¹¹ Human security threats exceed even those of wars. By the middle of August 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) recorded that the pandemic had killed 761,018 people around the world. This includes 414,326 in America; 213,674 in Europe; 59,875 in South-East Asia; 45,361 in Eastern Mediterranean; 18,476 in Africa; and 9,293 in the Western Pacific,¹² undermining human security and safety. With the increase of new cases of COVID-19 and a rising death toll, and the inevitable impact on the global economy, the pandemic can be compared to a war which requires joint efforts to fight it. The pandemic demands human security approaches of comprehensive, across-the-board human protection and empowerment.¹³ As Mulikita and Vairon argue, the pandemic has demonstrated its capacity to kill human beings on an unprecedented scale, with ruthless and remorseless efficiency.¹⁴

Although in broad terms, human security refers to freedom from want and freedom from fear,¹⁵ human freedom relates to fundamental human needs, and amongst these is human security. Scholars of human security would distinguish human security from the traditional view of security as state security and military involvement. Non-traditional human security focuses on basic human needs, including health, poverty and social identity.

¹¹ Akiko Fukushima, "COVID-19 is a human security crisis," *East Asia Forum*, 16 April 2020 <<https://www.eastasiaforum.org/2020/04/16/covid-19-is-a-human-security-crisis/>> (accessed 26 June 2020).

¹² World Health Organisation, "WHO Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Dashboard," <https://covid19.who.int/?gclid=EAIaIQobChMlorD_ifah6wIVBLTtCh28uQcpEAAYASAAEgLio_vD_BwE> (accessed August 2020).

¹³ Fukushima, "COVID-19 is a human security crisis."

¹⁴ Mulikita and Vairon, "COVID-19: Multilateralism and the quest for collective human security."

¹⁵ Edward Newman, "Critical human security studies," *Review of International Studies*, 36 (2010): 77-94.

Newman argues that ‘human security is normatively attractive, but analytically weak. Through a broad human security lens, anything that presents a critical threat to life and livelihood is a security threat, whatever the source.’¹⁶

On the other hand, using a human security framework, many governments have come up with unusual new ways to link military operations to a broader civilian security agenda, encouraging them to centre their defence police on civilian populations, in the process of preventing and stopping the spread of COVID-19. This has indicated a shift in the view of human security, which was often based upon military defence of state territories, and on who is involved in what for which purpose. Protecting the population from COVID-19 reinforces many government’s approaches to human security. While the past practice of involving military personnel and police in state governance was seen as dictatorship, the world suddenly adopts the same practice to control the pandemic during the lockdowns. It is now observed that around the world the military or the police are seen holding guns, not for war but as a part of humanitarian assistance efforts, building emergency hospitals and in initiatives to stop the spread of the virus. Outside the field, the changing image of security is observed, and it is noted that the role of professional military is not only for war and border territory protection but also social and economic interventions.

Interestingly, the African Union (AU)’s commitment for 2020 was to have the year of ‘silencing the guns’ on the African continent; a great motivation to work on peace and responding to human security. Even when the year 2020 was still in its infancy, COVID-19 came to be a huge challenge which coincidentally ‘silenced the physical guns’ but opened up invisible guns with massive visible consequences for human security, which requires great intervention. Social and global political uncertainty has been exposed, but

¹⁶ Ibid, 82.

also, although at small scale, diplomatic signs indicating the political will in the collaboration of fighting the common challenge of COVID-19.

Conclusion

The global economy is depressed due to COVID-19, but global social politics has also been devastated. The outbreak of COVID-19, the responses to the pandemic, and its consequences (already known and as yet known) have an enormous impact on not only health but human security including social economy, leadership and accountability as well as regional and global collaboration.

The COVID-19 pandemic sends or reveals a message that, more than ever in our history, the world needs to collaborate. The pandemic does not care who is stronger than the other or wealthier than the other, who is black or who is white. On a positive note, this enables an open-minded approach and a willingness to open up for genuine cooperation that would shape and contribute to a regional and global coordinated response not only for COVID-19 but for other pandemics, extending to included poverty, which affects human security across the globe.

While the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic and the predictions of its heavy effect continue, the common agreement is that this pandemic will have affected global social politics and the economy, and most importantly, it is clear that it will definitely reshape the future of global politics and the economy for a generation to come. On a silent note, accompanying this is the respect for humanity regardless of skin colour, a matter which may well still not be a future priority for discussion on the table, although this is urgently needed and requires revisiting, as does the issue of safety in general as a common need and a shared responsibility, and a commitment to facilitating this need to be made. Knowing and maintaining that the world needs now more than ever to collaborate, especially since COVID-19 respects neither national borders nor individual wealth in its transmission,

none can claim to fight the pandemic alone without close and strong collaboration, and no-one is safe until everyone is.

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Langue: élément clé pour une intégration régionale effective

Clément BIGIRIMANA

clement.bigirimana@ub.edu.bi

Résumé: *D'aucuns ignore que la langue est incontournable dans la vie de tous les jours. Des échanges d'idées et de pensées se font par le biais de la langue. Et c'est par lesdits échanges que les communautés se construisent, se développent et se fortifient. Si l'on prend le cas de la Communauté Est-Africaine (CEA), l'on constate que les langues de travail et/ou officielles de ladite communauté sont l'anglais et le kiswahili. Ces deux langues sont le pilier de cette communauté et la fondent en la faisant vivre et vibrer. Partant de ce constat, il y a moyen de se demander si l'intégration au sein de cette communauté est réellement effective pour tous les pays membres du point de vue [socio]linguistique. Ainsi, par une approche empirique voire qualitative nourrie d'une recherche documentaire, l'on essaiera de démontrer l'importance de la langue dans la réussite de l'intégration régionale, les impacts du COVID-19 face à l'intégration, sans oublier d'explorer et d'interroger les réalités [socio]linguistiques des pays membres de la CEA pour une intégration effective.*

Mots clés: *langue, intégration, communauté, communication, CEA, Covid-19.*

Introduction

La communauté est-africaine est plurilingue dans l'ensemble. Cela n'est pas en soi mauvais, mais il est essentiel que les peuples des pays membres partagent des langues dans lesquelles ils peuvent échanger afin de concourir au développement de cette région. Chacun des pays de cette communauté a ses propres langues avec des statuts parfois différents comme langue nationale, officielle ou étrangère. Cela peut alors engendrer des obstacles à l'intégration effective au sein de cette communauté. Déjà, Bakari évoquant le récit des Camerounais plurilingues parle d'une pluralité linguistique qui

devient un obstacle à l'intégration nationale¹. Un autre, Tchoutio, s'exclame en ces termes: «Intégration régionale en Afrique: quelle mesure? Quand la langue divise les peuples!»². Ce cas peut s'observer en la CEA quand, par exemple, un Burundais se déplace dans un autre pays aux autres langues et accents. Loin de toute autre considération physiologique, intellectuelle, la langue peut être un élément d'inclusion ou d'exclusion d'une personne dans une communauté donnée. Ainsi, dans cet article, par une approche empirique voire qualitative nourrie d'une recherche documentaire, il sera question de démontrer l'importance de la langue, comme élément clé pour une intégration régionale effective, dans la réussite de l'intégration régionale, les différents obstacles de l'intégration, sans oublier d'explorer et d'interroger les réalités [socio]linguistiques des pays membres de la CEA pour une intégration effective.

1. LA CEA: Une communauté plurilingue

Il n'est pas facile d'explorer et d'expliquer les réalités sociolinguistiques des six pays membres de la CEA. Néanmoins, un aperçu global est possible, pour rendre compte de la pluralité des langues dans cette communauté. Une vue générale montre que le paysage sociolinguistique des pays membres de la communauté est-africaine est marqué par une pluralité de langues nationales qui cohabitent avec le kiswahili, le français et l'anglais. Ces dernières se retrouvent, à différents niveaux, dans chacun de ces pays. Par exemple, la Tanzanie compte une centaine de langues, l'Ouganda 35, le Kenya 70, le Soudan du Sud environ 80 langues, et exceptionnellement et rarement le Rwanda et le Burundi une seule langue. Le nombre de locuteurs de chacune de ces langues varie de -1% à plus de 50%.

¹ Bakari Louis, «Quand le pluralisme linguistique devient un obstacle à l'intégration nationale,» <http://www.Afrique-gouvernance.net/bdf_experience-36_fr.html> (consulté le 02 septembre 2019).

² Tchoutio Basile, «Intégration régionale en Afrique: quelle mesure? Quand la langue divise les peuples!,» <http://afrique-gouvernance.net/bdf_experience-45_fr.html> (consulté le 02 septembre 2019).

Il s'agit donc d'un pluralisme dans l'ensemble. Et par définition, ce concept, souvent assimilé à celui du bilinguisme, est expliqué par la présence de plus d'une seule langue dans une communauté donnée. Selon Siouffi et Van Raemdonck, on considère qu'il y a bilinguisme (ou généralement multilinguisme), lorsqu'une personne est capable d'user de deux (ou de plusieurs) systèmes linguistiques de manière égale, et sans qu'un système soit valorisé par rapport à un autre. Et l'on sait que la diversité des langues n'est plus à démontrer dans la mesure où chacune des sociétés veut se démarquer par sa propre langue. Cela amène à dire que «rares sont dans le monde les pays monolingues, autrement dit, où une seule langue est parlée.»³

Pour ce qui est de la CEA dont il est question ici, Mazunya parle de la promotion de la langue nationale et de l'instauration d'un multilinguisme fonctionnel au sein de la CEA. Pour lui, «le multilinguisme fonctionnel [...] résulte de la diversité linguistique et culturelle des différentes communautés qui sont obligées d'utiliser des langues non maternelles une fois sorties de leur univers familial⁴. À cette fin, le citoyen de la communauté est-africaine est appelé à devenir plurilingue pour pouvoir s'ouvrir à d'autres peuples swahiliphone, francophone, anglophone, etc. sans perdre sa propre identité linguistique». Cela est d'autant plus important dans la mesure où avant d'être une communauté, on était dans des pays diversifiés où chaque pays et chaque peuple avait sa langue. Mais comme «l'union fait la force», des efforts doivent être fournis de toute part pour une intégration effective sur le plan linguistique. De plus, les diverses réalités sociolinguistiques sont le résultat de l'histoire qu'a connue respectivement les pays concernés.

Notons aussi que l'Organisation des Nations Unies (ONU) évoque le [plurilinguisme] multilinguisme comme une composante essentielle de la

³ Siouffi Gilles et Van Raemdonck Dan, *Cent fiches pour comprendre la linguistique* (Paris: Bréal, 1982).

⁴ Mazunya Maurice, «Promouvoir la langue nationale et instaurer un multilinguisme fonctionnel au sein de la CEA,» *Synergie des Grands Lacs*, 5 (2016): 87-98.

diversité culturelle, une notion consacrée dans la Convention sur la protection et la promotion de la diversité des expressions culturelles, adoptée par la Conférence générale de l'UNESCO à sa trente-troisième session en octobre 2005, et dont l'Assemblée générale des Nations Unies a pris note à sa soixante-troisième session. Les organismes des Nations Unies assument une responsabilité collective et partagée dans l'application de cette valeur fondamentale dans toutes leurs activités quotidiennes et leurs relations avec leurs partenaires. Comme il a été affirmé dans le rapport du Secrétaire général sur le multilinguisme en 2006: «Facteur essentiel d'une communication harmonieuse entre les peuples, le multilinguisme revêt une importance toute particulière pour l'Organisation des Nations Unies. Favorisant la tolérance, il assure aussi une participation effective et accrue de tous au processus de travail de l'Organisation, ainsi qu'une efficacité plus grande, de meilleurs résultats et une plus grande implication. Le multilinguisme doit être préservé et encouragé par différentes actions au sein du système des Nations Unies dans un esprit de partage et de communication».

Ainsi, à l'image de l'ONU qui a adopté pour un multilinguisme avec six langues officielles à savoir l'anglais, l'arabe, le chinois, l'espagnol, le français et le russe, tout en soulignant que l'anglais et le français sont les langues de travail du Secrétariat, la CEA pourrait s'en inspirer et instaurer un multilinguisme avec les trois langues, l'anglais, le français et le kiswahili, tout en précisant que la langue de travail de son secrétariat est l'anglais. C'est par ailleurs ce qui est ressorti du 15^{ème} sommet ordinaire des Chefs d'État de la Communauté Est-Africaine qui s'est tenu à Kampala le 30 novembre 2013, ayant pris une décision politique importante en faveur du plurilinguisme, en validant le principe de l'usage du français comme langue de travail, en plus de l'anglais et du kiswahili⁵. Cependant, cette décision attend toujours sa mise en pratique, pour que les pays qui se servent de

⁵ Ibid.

cette langue en tirent réellement profit en jouissant pleinement des fruits de l'intégration régionale.

Il y a donc nécessité d'instaurer une langue commune aux pays membres de la CEA. Ceci parce que, selon Soutet, la notion de langue commune est conçue comme le dénominateur commun sous-jacent à la variété des usages particuliers «au-delà des variations locales et sociales et après suppression de tous les écarts.»⁶ Elle est toujours une approximation et une abstraction. La CEA, ayant défini l'anglais et le kiswahili comme langues officielles, considère ces langues comme «langues communes» à tous les pays membres. Ces pays forment une communauté, et avec le substantif «langue», l'on parlera de «communauté linguistique». Pour le sociolinguiste, la notion de *communauté linguistique* est un point d'ancrage essentiel pour l'observation et l'analyse des phénomènes linguistiques et sociaux car c'est au sein de cet espace de pratiques/usages et de représentations partagées, socialement structuré, qu'il est en mesure d'analyser le rapport entre langues et sociétés. Comme le souligne Martinet, «la notion de *communauté linguistique* est non seulement utile, mais inévitable dans notre discipline [la sociolinguistique] dès qu'une langue est conçue comme un instrument de communication s'adaptant aux besoins du groupe qui l'utilise: "communication" implique "communauté".»⁷

Labov affirmait ainsi qu'«il serait faux de concevoir la communauté linguistique comme un ensemble de locuteurs employant les mêmes formes. On la décrit mieux comme étant un groupe qui partage les mêmes normes quant à la langue.»⁸ Même s'il semble difficile de saisir les attitudes, les valeurs, les images qui sont affectées (implicitement et explicitement) aux pratiques linguistiques et à leurs formes, cette idée que la communauté

⁶ Soutet Olivier, *Linguistique* (Paris: Quadrige-PUF, 1999).

⁷ Martinet André, «Fonctions du langage et linguistique appliquée,» *Communication et langage*, 1 (1969): 9-18, <<http://www.persee.fr/doc/colan>> (Consulté le 15 Septembre 2020).

⁸ Labov William, *La sociolinguistique* (Paris: Ed. Minuit, 1976).

serait aussi définie par des représentations sociolinguistiques mais aussi sociales, que partageraient ses membres, semble s'être imposée aujourd'hui.

Mais que vit réellement chaque pays de la CEA socio-linguistiquement parler? Ici, il est question de passer en revue le paysage sociolinguistique des pays membres de la CEA. Ainsi, nous avons:

Le Burundi, traditionnellement monolingue, connaît actuellement plus de six langues dont le kirundi, langue de tous les Burundais, le français de la majorité des intellectuels, l'anglais de la minorité des intellectuels, le kiswahili de certains Burundais (généralement commerçants) et dans certaines localités, l'arabe, le chinois et l'allemand actuellement enseignées à l'université du Burundi aux volontaires. D'autres langues y sont aussi utilisées par les expatriés et/ou la diaspora. De ces langues, l'on retient que le kirundi, le français, le kiswahili et l'anglais sont les langues officielles (2019).

Le Kenya est, avec la prédominance de l'anglais et du Kiswahili, les deux langues reconnues par la loi comme officielles, un pays ethniquement diversifié et qui comprend environ les principaux groupes ethniques avec des langues spécifiques. Cette composition ethnique diverse fait du pays un pays multilingue avec de nombreuses langues différentes.

La Tanzanie, avec divers groupes ethniques qui font souvent recours aux langues nationales (environ une centaine) respectives, a le kiswahili comme langue officielle de la nation. L'anglais y est aussi largement parlé. Néanmoins, le kiswahili se parle par plusieurs locuteurs et semble être plus maîtrisé que l'anglais par la population tanzanienne.

Le Soudan du Sud, devenu indépendant en 2011, a choisi l'anglais comme langue officielle dans le but de s'opposer à l'arabe et à l'islam majoritairement pratiqué au Soudan. C'est un choix motivé par le rapprochement avec ses voisins anglophones, soit l'Ouganda et le Kenya,

mais aussi par référence à son ancien colonisateur britannique. À côté de l'anglais, environ 80 langues nationales y sont parlées et utilisées par la population, à majorité analphabète.

L'Ouganda, ancienne colonie britannique, compte environ une trentaine de langues nationales. Néanmoins, la constitution précise dans son article 6 alinéa 1 que l'anglais est la langue officielle et que le Kiswahili est la deuxième langue officielle (alinéa 2), et que d'autres langues peuvent être employées dans l'enseignement, la législation et les tribunaux (alinéa 3).

Le Rwanda, traditionnellement monolingue comme le Burundi, s'ouvre de plus en plus au monde extérieur, en introduisant dans son paysage sociolinguistique d'autres langues, à côté du Kinyarwanda. Désormais, les langues officielles sont le Kinyarwanda, le français et l'anglais. Ces deux dernières langues sont parlées plutôt maîtrisées aux différents niveaux. Il y existe d'autres langues minoritaires, les unes des pays environnants, d'autres des expatriés.

De ce qui précède, il est fort évident que la CEA est plurilingue dans l'ensemble et que des efforts d'harmonisation des politiques linguistiques, plus particulièrement dans le système éducatif, doivent être entrepris. Cela permettra, au moins, aux intellectuels de la région de pouvoir se comprendre pour le développement de cette communauté. En effet, les disparités plurilinguistiques entre citoyens de cette communauté ne lui permettent pas de renforcer et de régler les relations industrielles, commerciales, d'infrastructures culturelles, sociales, politiques et des États membres (Objectifs du Traité, article 5). Aussi, le développement accéléré, harmonieux et équilibré ainsi que l'expansion durable des activités recherchée (Traité, article 5) devient difficile à atteindre avec des barrières linguistiques entre citoyens d'une même communauté.

Pour cela, nous pensons que le renforcement de l'enseignement des trois langues: le Kiswahili, le français et l'anglais qui semblent avoir des locuteurs

non négligeables dans le monde en général et dans la région en particulier, est plus qu'une urgence pour une parfaite intégration. Celle-ci se fonde sur la réussite de la communication, du latin *communicare* qui veut dire *mise en commun, faire part, partager voire ensemble pour faire un*. La communication recouvre alors le sens d'échange de propos, d'action de faire-part. Et bien que, généralement, la communication cherche à établir des relations ou des liens, il arrive parfois, dans certains contextes que «la communication entre classes (ou, dans les sociétés coloniales ou semi-coloniales, entre ethnies) représente toujours une situation critique pour la langue utilisée quelle qu'elle soit.»⁹ Cela n'est qu'une conséquence directe des enjeux de la communication.

D'où la langue, comme un moyen de communication, doit être bien pensée dans le cadre d'une intégration régionale comme vecteur, facilitateur du processus que cela implique. Par conséquent, la communication étant un des piliers de la vie des communautés, elle demeure un vaste domaine à explorer compte tenu des paramètres qui entrent en jeu. En effet, dans une communication efficace, l'homme s'adapte à plusieurs types de contraintes d'ordre linguistique, culturel, sociologique et spatio-temporel. Par conséquent, le chemin à parcourir est long pour que chaque citoyen des pays de la CEA dispose des compétences linguistiques et interculturelles nécessaires pour tirer parti de la citoyenneté est-africaine.

2. Intégration régionale: problème conceptuel

Déjà, le concept d' «intégration» pose de problèmes. Le Petit Robert énonce plusieurs définitions à ce terme. Celle qui a retenu notre attention est la suivante: «opération par laquelle un individu ou un groupe s'incorpore à une collectivité, à un milieu (opposé à ségrégation). Intégration politique, sociale, raciale, culturelle (acculturation).»¹⁰ Dans le cas de l'intégration régionale des six pays de la CEA (et des autres qui voudront s'y associer

⁹ Bourdieu Pierre, *Ce que parler veut dire* (Paris: Fayard, 1982).

¹⁰ Le Petit Robert, 2004 ed. s.v. «intégration.»

[comme la RDC qui a déjà adressé une demande dans ce sens]), l'intégration sera la preuve des efforts, du désir, de la motivation, des potentialités des pays concernés ou des individus desdits pays à s'intégrer, en prenant en compte une dimension identitaire. Ici, il importe de noter que l'intégration effective suppose l'acquisition et/ou la perte de certains éléments de son identité d'origine. Une fois l'intégration atteinte, on ne parlera plus d'un Burundais, ni d'un Rwandais, ni d'un Tanzanien, ni d'un Kenyan, ni d'un Ougandais non plus d'un Sud-Soudanais mais d'un Est-africain.

On pourra alors juger de l'échec ou de la réussite (actuel ou projeté) de l'intégration à travers l'appropriation des langues qui seront alors décidées comme langues de travail et/ou officielles de la communauté. Actuellement, il est précisé que «La langue officielle de la CEA est l'anglais. Le Kiswahili est la lingua franca de la CEA» (Art 137) [voir aussi les art. 46 et 119 du Traité de la CEA]. La connaissance de ces langues (anglais et kiswahili) se traduit comme une condition d'appréciation de l'intégration des citoyens respectifs des pays membres de la CEA. L'anglais, en tant que langue de travail dans cette communauté, doit être maîtrisé par toute personne souhaitant travailler dans cette communauté. Sa maîtrise se veut aussi une condition d'acceptation dans ladite communauté.

Il est alors clair que si l'on considère le volet d'intégration linguistique dans la CEA, dans leur grande majorité, les études sur l'intégration linguistique des citoyens de la CEA ou des pays membres de la CEA portent essentiellement sur la compétence, la maîtrise et/ou sur l'utilisation en contexte d'une des deux langues définies comme officielles et/ou de travail de la communauté, à savoir l'anglais et le kiswahili. Il s'agit des langues en usage officiel et quotidien dans les activités de la communauté, alors des langues qui supplantent les autres langues nationales des pays respectifs. Néanmoins, une nécessité de renforcer l'apprentissage des langues nationales dans l'intérêt de sauvegarder la culture et une partie identitaire propre à chaque pays est à signaler.

Les clauses de l'intégration régionale ayant été arrêtées par les grandes instances des pays concernés, parfois sans prendre en compte des volontés citoyennes, l'intégration ne sera pas facile. C'est vrai que les contextes politiques diffèrent, mais l'intégration effective des citoyens devra tenir compte des réalités propres à chaque pays membre. Par exemple, au Burundi, se concentrer seulement sur la maîtrise de l'anglais et du kiswahili dans le sens de l'intégration régionale ne concordera pas avec certains articles de la loi portant statut des langues au Burundi où il est clairement fait mention que la langue nationale [Kirundi] est l'élément primordial constitutif de l'identité nationale et de tout Burundais quelle que soit son ethnie.¹¹ Pour cela, les politiques de gestion de la diversité linguistique dans la CEA doivent chercher à viser une cohésion sociale et culturelle autour des [et dans les] pays membres la CEA dans un est-africanisme convivial.

Dans la situation politico-linguistique officiellement instaurée en CEA, l'intégration est présentée comme reposant sur la pratique, l'utilisation et l'appropriation voire la maîtrise de l'anglais et du kiswahili. Cela suppose que les autres langues des pays respectifs sont mises de côté, alors déconsidérées. Par conséquent, le processus d'intégration est freiné car ces deux langues considérées comme seuls moyens de communication possibles pour pouvoir participer à l'ensemble des activités de la CEA ignorent les autres dimensions d'intégration comme économique, politique, éducationnelle, etc. On pourrait ainsi dire que l'on est intégré linguistiquement dans la CEA que si l'on a la maîtrise des deux langues officiellement arrêtées dans ladite communauté. L'intégration linguistique sera alors comprise dans le sens d'un processus qui commence par l'apprentissage de la langue ou des langues prédéfinies et qui se poursuit par une pratique de plus en plus fréquente de cette [ces] langue(s) dans les différentes situations de la vie quotidienne. Les choses sont à nuancer en

¹¹ Bigirimana Clément, «Enseignement des langues et construction identitaire,» *Synergie des Grands Lacs*, 7 (2018): 15-28, <http://gerflint.fr/Base/Afrique_Grnads_Lacs7/AfGrands_Lacs7.html> (Consulté le 03 septembre 2020).

essayant aussi d'intégrer d'autres langues internationales, comme le français, pour permettre une éventuelle coopération avec les pays francophones, d'ailleurs nombreux, qui font recours au français.

3. COVID-19 et l'intégration régionale

Partant du concept d'«intégration» précédemment évoqué, l'incorporation à une collectivité n'est pas une chose facile. Elle se heurte à certains obstacles qui sont de plusieurs ordres. Entre autres obstacles, il y a moyen de citer – sans être exhaustif – les problèmes frontaliers ou géographiques, les maladies pandémiques, les barrières linguistiques, les inégalités financières, les problèmes sécuritaires, l'enfermement sur soi, le manque de détermination de la part de certains États, la question identitaire, etc. Parmi tous ceux-là, nous allons nous attarder sur la pandémie de COVID-19, problème actuel, comme frein au processus d'intégration.

Le cas du coronavirus, connu sous le nom de COVID-19, découvert en Chine en décembre 2019 s'est propagé à grande vitesse dans les pays du monde, touchant la quasi-totalité des régions à différents niveaux. Cette maladie a créé une panique mondiale sans pareille, entraînant le confinement des pays et des personnes, empêchant ainsi la libre circulation des personnes pour jouir de leurs droits. En effet, «[...] un virus, préalablement à une contagion, ne demande pas la nationalité, le type de permis de séjour ou pire encore, le secteur économique dans lequel nous sommes employés.»¹² Ainsi, il n'a seulement fallu que l'annonce des premiers cas de contamination à la COVID-19 en Afrique pour qu'un plus grand nombre de pays du continent Africain – même ceux formant des communautés déjà solides, comme l'UE – formulent des restrictions, limitant voire interdisant la mobilité des personnes entre les pays voisins; ceux-là même avec qui l'on cherche à bâtir une intégration. Et comme le précise Ricciardi, «bien que les catastrophes pandémiques et les épidémies constituent également des

¹² Toni Ricciardi, «Les pandémies dans une perspective d'histoire globale,» in *COVID 19: Le regard des sciences sociales*, ed. Gamba Fiorenza et al, 29-44 (Genève: Seismo, 2020).

phénomènes sociaux de grande ampleur, dans ces cas, la mémoire tend à être plus individuelle que collective.»¹³

Mais, qu'entendre par pandémie? Étymologiquement parler, le mot «pandémie» vient du grec «*pan*» qui signifie «tout» et «*demos*» qui signifie «peuple». Il s'agit d'une maladie qui s'étend à toute la population d'un continent et dont l'impact et la gravité sont donc plus importants que ceux d'une épidémie¹⁴. Il s'agit généralement d'une épidémie de très grande envergure, qui se développe sur un vaste territoire, en dépassant les frontières des États. Parlant de COVID-19, nous ajouterons volontiers qu'il s'agit d'une maladie exceptionnelle à caractère mondial semant la panique partout et en toute personne les empêchant ainsi de réaliser le plus librement possible leur rêve, tout en impactant négativement sur leurs accords déjà conclus en terme de coopération, de communauté, d'échange, de marché, etc.

Et cela nous amène à évoquer le problème frontalier ou géographique entre les États. Ainsi, en cas d'une intégration, il est entendu que les frontières entre les pays d'une même communauté comme la CEA, l'UE doivent être moins visibles, du moins pour la circulation des personnes. Les peuples formant la communauté s'acceptent et s'accueillent comme des frères et sœurs. Mais, avec la pandémie de Coronavirus, les pays se sont [r]enfermés sur eux-mêmes, interdisant ainsi les mouvements des peuples d'un pays à l'autre, avec comme mots d'ordre «confinement» et «distance sociale». De même, des réunions d'intérêt communautaire ont été suspendues, en recourant aux Nouvelles Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication via les Vidéo-Téléconférences entre certaines personnalités seulement. Ici, il importe de souligner que tous les pays ne disposent pas

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ <<https://sante.journaldesfemmes.fr/fiches-maladies/2619795-pandemie-coronavirus-covid-19-definition-signification-difference-epidemie-exemple-historique/>> (consulté le 25 mai 2020).

des mêmes avancées technologiques, ce qui remet en cause les avantages de l'intégration.

La COVID-19 a alors réduit la mobilité des personnes, s'imposant comme une nouvelle donne et un facteur régulateur des volontés humaines. L'on ne peut en aucun cas réussir l'intégration si tous les discours actuels chantent le confinement et la distance sociale, avec la fermeture des frontières! Pour cela, Debarbieux (2020), parlant de la distance sociale et du confinement au temps de COVID-19 avance que «[...] on a vu des gouvernants se précipiter aux confins de leur territoire pour en fermer l'accès¹⁵. Pourtant, il est attesté par toutes les études scientifiques¹⁶ que la fermeture des frontières d'un territoire ne contient pas une épidémie quand la maladie est déjà présente sur ce territoire, a fortiori quand les pays voisins ont déjà adopté des mesures de confinement domestique et des restrictions à la mobilité des personnes.» Dans cette logique, l'Autre, avec la COVID-19, est devenu suspect, dangereux, «on ne sait jamais», étranger voire étrange chez soi, ce qui multiplie les sentiments de méfiance les uns envers les autres. Et selon toujours Debarbieux (2020) «la distance sociale rend compte de la différence qui existe entre deux individus ou deux groupes d'individus, du point de vue des intéressés eux-mêmes» – «il n'est pas du même milieu» ou pourquoi pas «du même monde», voire «je préfère garder mes distances» – ou du point de vue du sociologue avec les critères et indicateurs qui sont les siens: niveau de revenu, niveau d'éducation, pratiques langagières, etc.»¹⁷. Comment alors s'intégrer sans s'accepter mutuellement? Par ailleurs, Alain Boyer (1993) évoquant l'intégration des étrangers pose le problème en ces termes: «Disons d'abord qu'en l'absence d'intégration nous aurions une société repliée sur elle-même et totalitaire. Il faut déjà réfléchir sur le fait

¹⁵ Bernard Debarbieux, «Distance sociale et confinement au temps du COVID-19,» in *COVID 19: Le regard des sciences sociales*, ed. Gamba Fiorenza et al, 111-124 (Genève: Seismo, 2020).

¹⁶ Matteo Chinazzi, et al, «The effect of travel restrictions on the spread of the 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak,» *Science* 368, 6489 (April 2020): 395; Roojin Habibi et al, «Travel restrictions violate international law,» *Science*, 367 (6485): 1436 (2020).

¹⁷ Debarbieux, «Distance sociale et confinement ...», 111-124.

que l'opinion considère que la présence d'étrangers pose problème - mais ce problème n'est pas tant celui des étrangers que celui de la société globale [...]»¹⁸.

Cela résonne comme un clin d'œil pour le processus d'intégration. Chacun devrait être considéré tel qu'il est, au-delà de ses origines, de sa race, de son appartenance voire apparence. C'est là la richesse de l'intégration et c'est cela qui permettra de faire rayonner la communauté en en faisant une «communauté aux multiples couleurs». Pour nous, vu que la pandémie de COVID-19 n'a épargné presque aucun pays de façon générale, il nous semble important d'affirmer qu'elle se révèle comme un dénominateur commun de relance de coopération pour une solution commune ce qui animera un sentiment d'intégration, d'un vivre-ensemble pour le bien de tous les peuples. Dans ce sens, Cattacin (2020) se pose autant de question entre autres: «le COVID-19 serait-il un révélateur ainsi qu'un accélérateur d'une société de la solidarité? D'une communauté internationale solidaire? D'une héroïsation des stigmatisées? D'une société plus démocratique? La société des risques est-elle une société d'égalité des chances? On aurait pu le croire en écoutant la politique et les médias qui parlaient de la protection des personnes fragiles, qui se préoccupaient des effets sur l'Afrique ou sur les favelas, qui se voyaient, souvent sous contrainte, lire leur pays comme faisant partie d'un et unique monde à soigner ensemble»¹⁹. Il s'agit d'une solidarité que recommande d'ailleurs le communiqué de la réunion virtuelle qui a eu lieu le 13 mai 2020, organisée par la Commission économique pour l'Afrique en collaboration avec les communautés économiques régionales afin d'explorer les possibilités et les opportunités d'intégration accélérée de

¹⁸ Alain Boyer, «Les enjeux et les conditions de l'intégration,» *Autres Temps. Les Cahiers du Christianisme social* 39 (1993): 94-101, <http://persee.fr/doc/chris_0753-2776_1993_num_39_1_1614> (consulté le 21 septembre 2020).

¹⁹ Sandro Cattacin, «Stigmatisations inversées, renversées et rétablies,» in *COVID 19: Le regard des sciences sociales*, ed. Gamba Fiorenza et al, 149-158 (Genève: Seismo, 2020).

la santé en Afrique²⁰. Pour eux, «la coopération en matière de soins de santé est essentielle pour réaliser l'aspiration 1 et l'objectif 1 de l'Agenda 2063 de l'Afrique ainsi que l'ODD 3 sur la garantie d'une vie saine et du bien-être pour tous». Le même communiqué souligne qu'«un certain niveau d'intégration sanitaire se produit sur le continent, comme en témoigne la mise en place de nombreuses initiatives régionales et coopératives en matière de santé», telles que la Stratégie africaine pour la santé (2016-2030), le CDC africain, l'Agence africaine des médicaments, le Plan de fabrication pharmaceutique pour l'Afrique, entre autres. Cela est donc plus important dans la mesure où le rapport des Nations Unies avance qu' «entre 300 000 et 3 300 000 Africains pourraient perdre la vie à cause de COVID-19, en fonction des mesures prises pour stopper la propagation du virus.»²¹

Les discours doivent alors changer pour lutter contre cette pandémie de COVID-19 qui est une «crise sanitaire mondiale de notre époque et le plus grand défi auquel nous ayons été confrontés depuis la Seconde Guerre mondiale» selon le Programme des Nations Unies pour le Développement.

4. Langue et langage: fondements d'une communauté

Soulignons d'emblée que les concepts de «langue» et «langage» sont définis de manière diversifiée selon les spécialistes. Cela ne semble pas constituer une entrave car, comme l'écrit Mounin (1987), «une longue tradition philosophique nomme langage 'tout moyen quelconque d'exprimer des idées' (Larousse du XX^e siècle)». De cela, l'on peut parler de la notion de communauté, ici, CEA en matière de langues. Peut-on alors considérer la CEA comme une communauté linguistique à proprement parler? À cette question, l'on peut répondre par l'affirmative, si l'on considère que pour le sociolinguiste, la notion de *communauté linguistique* est un point d'ancrage essentiel pour l'observation et l'analyse des phénomènes linguistiques et

²⁰ <<https://www.afrik.com/afrique-plaidoyer-pour-une-integration-acceleree-de-la-sante-en-afrique>>, consulté le 25 mai 2020.

²¹ Commission Economique pour l'Afrique, *Rapport* (2020).

sociaux.²² C'est au sein d'une communauté que l'on étudie les différentes pratiques langagières ou linguistiques. Aussi, la langue est un élément fondamental qui caractérise une communauté donnée, d'où la définition d'une langue ou des langues d'usage dans toute communauté reste un facteur déterminant. La/les langue(s) ainsi définie(s) servira(ont) d'instrument de communication s'adaptant aux besoins du groupe qui l'(les)utilise. La communication implique alors communauté dans le sens de partager des valeurs linguistiques (voir supra). Les Est-africains pourront alors échanger leurs expériences dans différents domaines et ainsi se définir par rapport à ces langues. C'est ce que l'on appelle identité linguistique. L'identité, en général, selon Mucchielli (1986) se définit comme «un ensemble de critères, de définitions d'un sujet et un sentiment interne. Ce sentiment d'identité est composé de différents sentiments: sentiment d'unité, de cohérence, d'appartenance, de valeur, d'autonomie et de confiance organisés autour d'une volonté d'existence. Les dimensions de l'identité sont intimement mêlées: individuelle (sentiment d'être unique), groupale (sentiment d'appartenir à un groupe) et culturelle (sentiment d'avoir une culture d'appartenance).»²³

Toutefois, en ce qui est de la langue, un individu peut choisir d'adhérer à plusieurs communautés linguistiques, soit par volonté, soit par contrainte, généralement en situation d'apprentissage. C'est dans ce sens que Maalouf (1998) marque la différence entre la religion et la langue en ces termes: «la religion a vocation d'être exclusive, la Langue pas. On peut pratiquer à la fois l'arabe, l'hébreu, l'italien, le suédois, mais on ne peut être à la fois juif, musulman, catholique et luthérien; [...] La langue a cette merveilleuse particularité d'être à la fois facteur d'identité et instrument de communication».

²² Carmen Alén Garabato et Alexia Kis-Marck, Le concept de «*communauté linguistique*» face à la réalité du terrain (Lengas 2015), <<http://wwwjournals.openedition.org/lengas/866>> (consulté le 14 Octobre 2019).

²³ Alex Mucchielli, *L'identité* (Paris: PUF, 1986).

Il y a alors moyen de conclure que les notions de langue, langage et communauté sont intimement liées. Il n'y a pas de communauté sans langue ou langage; de même qu'il n'y a pas de langue sans la communauté qui la pratique. C'est donc la communauté qui fait la langue dans le sens de manipulation, amélioration ou déformation et non la langue qui fait la communauté. La langue reste tout de même un élément actif reflétant notre appartenance sociale, notre culture et notre identité.

Néanmoins, dans le processus d'intégration régionale des différents pays, il importe de ne pas considérer le niveau linguistique des ressortissants desdits pays comme un critère d'adhésion. Calinon (2013), parlant des fonctions attribuées à la langue, avance que lorsque l'intégration linguistique est appréhendée comme étant un objectif d'actions politiques, un objet de mesure, un outil d'évaluation, une compétence, voire un critère de sélection juridique, la langue revêt ici une fonction délimitante qui relèverait uniquement de l'individu locuteur et non de l'usage social qu'il peut en faire. Selon cette conception, la compétence en langue pourrait être isolée et évaluée indépendamment de la pratique sociale. Or, cela va à l'encontre de la notion d'intégration où la langue permettrait la rencontre avec l'Autre et au locuteur d'appréhender, de provoquer et de se positionner dans cette rencontre.

Elle poursuit sa réflexion en ces mots: «que l'on pense qu'une compétence en langue est une conséquence de l'intégration (Beacco et al 2008) ou un préalable, nous posons que l'intégration passe par la possibilité et l'accroissement d'une mobilité sociale, linguistique et langagière à l'intérieur d'un espace social donné. Cette mobilité à travers différents groupes sociaux est permise grâce à des compétences dans une ou des langues par l'intermédiaire d'une participation accrue à des interactions variant selon leur fréquence et leur valeur communicative.»²⁴

²⁴ Anne-Sophie Calinon, «L'intégration linguistique en question,» *Langage et société* 144, 2 (2013): 27-40, <<https://doi.org/10.3917/ls.144.0027>> (Consulté le 02 septembre 2019).

De plus, comme le souligne Adami et al., la langue est un élément nécessaire, mais non suffisant, dans un processus comme celui de l'intégration qui passe par de nombreux méandres, positionnements, repositionnements et «légitimités sociales, sociolinguistiques et socioidentitaires» dont on doit tenir compte²⁵. Dans le cas de la CEA, c'est la compétence en anglais et en kiswahili qui garantirait l'intégration des citoyens est-africains. Il est impératif que les divers États membres de la CEA puissent s'entendre sur une politique linguistique commune pour faciliter les individus dans l'apprentissage des langues et dans leur choix de langues d'étude. Par ailleurs, Mazunya va jusqu'à dire que «dans le cadre de la CEA les défis linguistiques et culturels sont réels et méritent des mesures appropriées. La sensibilisation des décideurs et des acteurs nationaux et régionaux sur l'harmonisation des politiques nationales plurilingues doit se poursuivre, pour que soit élaboré dans les meilleurs délais un cadre de référence régionale pour les langues maternelles, nationales, scolaires, officielles et étrangères.»²⁶

5. La CEA: une communauté aux bases solides

Fondée à l'origine en 1967, la CEA a connu des moments de difficultés jusqu'à la dissolution en 1977. Elle revoit le jour en 2000-2001 avec le Kenya, l'Ouganda et la Tanzanie. Ces trois pays ont signé un traité qui a été modifié en 2006 et en 2007 avec l'adhésion du Burundi et du Rwanda. Actuellement, la CEA est composée de six pays dont le Burundi, le Kenya, l'Ouganda, le Rwanda, le Sud Soudan et la Tanzanie. Aussi, la RDC a déjà exprimé son intention plutôt sa demande d'adhésion à la CEA, ce qui fortifierait davantage cette communauté.

Jean-Claude Beacco, «Les langues dans les politiques d'intégration des adultes migrants,» *Conseil de l'Europe* 2008 (Hal-00555105).

²⁵ Hervé Adami, «Parcours migratoire et intégration langagière,» in *L'intégration et la formation linguistique des migrants: état des lieux et perspectives*, ed. J.M. Mangiante, 37-54 (Arras: Artois Presses Université, 2011).

²⁶ Mazunya, «Promouvoir la langue nationale ...»

Ainsi, comme un adage français le précise «l'Union fait la force». Forts de cette idée, ces six pays forment une grande communauté, «la Communauté Est-Africaine» (en français) ou «East African Community» en anglais. L'échange de certaines valeurs, la mise en commun de certaines de leurs réalités respectives renforceront des liens déjà établis. Des efforts sont à conjuguer de toute part pour se comprendre et pour mieux vivre l'intégration régionale.

Selon le Traité pour l'établissement du traité de l'Afrique de l'Est, tel que modifié le 14 décembre 2006 et le 20 août 2007, l'Article 5 précise les objectifs ultimes de ladite Communauté²⁷ en ces termes:

Objectifs de la Communauté

1) Les objectifs de la Communauté sont de développer des politiques et des programmes visant à agrandir et approfondir la coopération entre les États membres dans les domaines politique, économique, social, culturel, de la recherche, de la technologie, de la défense, la sécurité, les affaires juridiques et judiciaires pour leur bénéfice mutuel.

2) Conformément aux dispositions du paragraphe 1 du présent article, les États membres s'engagent à établir entre eux et conformément aux dispositions du traité une Union douanière, un Marché commun, plus tard une Union monétaire et à la fin une Fédération politique afin de renforcer et de régler les relations industrielles, commerciales, d'infrastructure, culturelles, sociales, politiques des États membres. À cette fin il est nécessaire qu'il y ait un développement accéléré, harmonieux et équilibré et une expansion durable des activités économiques dont les bénéfices seront partagés équitablement.

[...]

²⁷ La version originale du Traité étant en anglais, la version française n'en est qu'une traduction.

Objectives of the Community

1) The objectives of the Community shall be to develop policies and programmes aimed at widening and deepening co-operation among the Partner States in political, economic, social and cultural fields, research and technology, defence, security and legal and judicial affairs, for their mutual benefit.

2) In pursuance of the provisions of paragraph 1 of this Article, the Partner States under take to establish among themselves and in accordance with the provisions of this Treaty, a Customs Union, a Common Market, subsequently a Monetary Union and ultimately a Political Federation in order to strengthen and regulate the industrial, commercial, infrastructural, cultural, social, political and other relations of the Partner States to the end that there shall be accelerated, harmonious and balanced development and sustained expansion of economic activities, the benefit of which shall be equitably shared.

[...]

Cet article démontre la force de cette communauté une fois le processus d'intégration est achevé.

Conclusion

L'intitulé de cet article était «**Langue: élément clé pour une intégration régionale effective**». Il a été débattu le concept d'intégration étant donné les multiples facettes de l'intégration. L'accent a été mis sur l'intégration linguistique des pays membres de la CEA dans la mesure où la langue officielle comme celle de travail ne sont pas partagées par tous les pays membres. Rappelons qu'il s'agit de l'anglais et du kiswahili, des langues connues par une minorité des Burundais. Le Burundi souhaite alors que le français soit admis dans ces langues afin de jouir pleinement des délices de l'intégration. L'on se dit que cette demande sera exaucée si jamais la RDC

est acceptée dans cette communauté. Cela touchera sans doute certaines des clauses du Traité de la CEA. Le fait de s'exprimer librement et aisément sans complexe dans une langue de son choix dans cette communauté avancerait le processus. Les idées seront débattues et mises en commun pour le bien commun des citoyens de la communauté. La langue, comme moyen de communication [au vrai sens de ce concept] s'avère incontournable dans les processus d'intégration. S'inspirant du plurilinguisme européen, mais aussi des Nations Unies, la CEA pourrait prendre en compte les langues qui rassembleront plus de locuteurs dans leurs diversités linguistique et culturelle pour une identité est-africaine et dans le respect des identités respectives. Le multilinguisme assure une participation effective et accrue de tous au processus d'intégration ainsi qu'une efficacité plus grande de ses acteurs en vue de meilleurs résultats et d'une plus grande implication.

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Securitisation of Global Health: Leveraging Africa's Innovative Potential Post-COVID-19

Lynette ODONDI

lodondi@yahoo.com

Abstract: *The declaration of the COVID-19 virus outbreak as a global pandemic has elevated the status of national health to a global security concern. It has invigorated innovation among African entrepreneurs and is calling for facilitation by scholars in creating linkages for implementation. The wisdom of Jean Monnet's vision of harnessing regional resources through EU/ACP may finally find relevance as COVID-19 revealed the urgency of collective action. It has also laid bare the reality of interconnectedness, and the harsh penalty of inertia. Whereas the dynamics of co-operation and conflict between China, Europe and America impact Africa directly, the continent has a unique opportunity to pursue its own course. The African Union (AU)'s Africa Centre for Disease Control (CDC) funded Nigeria, the frontrunner in its COVID-19 national response in January 2020. Inconsistencies in China's behaviour – construction of an 800-bed medical facility dedicated to COVID-19 in Zambia, a laudable act, followed by the landing of Chinese commercial airliner in Kenya on 28th February 2020 when other countries had banned such flights, raises ethical questions. Responses in Greater East Africa reveal weak regional cohesiveness. Kenya and Uganda locked down in April 2020, while Tanzania took minimal precautions. Burundi proceeded with political elections, as Rwanda instituted stringent measures and initiated a virtual meeting of the EAC heads of state on 12th May 2020, recommendations of which were not implemented. The wife of Burundi's president was admitted into an elite hospital in Kenya despite a ban on international travel. Allegations of impropriety in management of donations marred the spirited fight by medical personnel in Kenya. A positive perspective is the rise in innovation and creativity from different parts of Africa. The Export Processing Zone in Kenya was reported to be producing better quality masks than those previously imported from China. This paper explores the nexus between health and security. It argues that COVID-19 has raised the profile of global health security, providing an opportunity for Africa to leverage its innovative potential. This reinforces Jean Monnet's noble intentions for regional integration. The study applies desktop analysis.*

Key words: *Global health, COVID-19 pandemic, regional integration, securitisation, innovation.*

Introduction

This paper seeks to interrogate the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic on security in Africa and its implications for co-operation with the European Union and China. Adopting the broad definition of security, it argues that with its huge human capital and natural resource endowment, Africa should apply the advantages that accrue due to proximity to harness the innovations arising from the COVID-19 response in order to improve its competitive advantage. The COVID-19 pandemic has created an opportunity for Africa to harness its creative potential. A major threat to innovation and creativity however is corruption and governance which can cancel out major human effort and investment.

In the 19th and 20th Centuries, health and security were issues which were far removed from each other. The situation has however changed with health coming to the forefront of security discourse. From an understanding of security as the military and guns during the post Second World War period, it has changed to health security with some referring to it as the 'Third World War', being said to be being fought against an unseen enemy, a virus taking its toll in the millions, with lockdowns, social distancing, masks and sanitizers. Kisienko¹ however argues that it is presumptuous to refer to it as such since other pandemics also claimed large numbers but were never labelled as such. Buzan et al² envisaged an upgraded Security Complex Theory from a narrow focus on war and military aspects, to economic, social and political dimensions. The authors argued that it would have a more dispersed and regional character. At the time however, global health was still at the periphery of the discourse. Amartya Sen³ brought these concepts closer, defining well-being from a human development perspective. He also

¹ Arne Kisienko, "Comparing COVID-19 to past world war efforts is premature — and presumptuous," *The Conversation*, 12 July 2020, <<https://theconversation.com/comparing-covid-19-to-past-world-war-efforts-is-premature-and-presumptuous-140701>>

² B. Buzan, Ole Waever and Jaap de Wilde, *Security: A New Framework for Analysis*, 95-108 (London: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1998).

³ Amartya Sen, *Development as Freedom* (Oxford University Press, 1999).

acknowledged the world's increased interlinkages. Yuk-ping et al⁴ cite Smolinski et al's⁵ argument that due to interconnectedness, in what they refer to as a 'global village', an occurrence in one part of the world has implications for what happens in many other parts. The said occurrences transcend geographical and political limitations. Regardless of the nature of the happening, as long as it has the ability to disrupt the activities of mass populations, economies and government entities, they become issues of great concern. Some of the said disruptions may be caused by sickness, infirmity and death. The authors focus on the big picture, arguing that it is immaterial whether the calamities occur naturally, intentionally or through microbes.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought to the fore multi-dimensional debates on global leadership and governance, peace and security. With America, China and Europe grappling with their second and most severe waves of the pandemic, international actors have expressed concern about Africa and the implications of the pandemic for the continent which is already plagued with Ebola, HIV/AIDs and many other challenges. As states moved to arrest the fast-developing rise in morbidity and mortality from the pandemic among their own citizens, Africa, momentarily left to fend for itself, witnessed a sudden upsurge in innovations by local entrepreneurs and students from technical institutions. Improvised ventilators and hospital beds, water and sanitizer dispensers and face masks, are the products of untapped and yet viable sources, the informal sector. There is however no co-ordinated effort to promote such enterprise by facilitating them to perfect, patent and commercialize. Such innovations have served to fill in the gaps in the market previously occupied by Chinese products and others from Western states.

⁴ Catherine Lo Yuk-ping and Nicholas Thomas, "How is health a security issue? Politics, responses and issues," *Health Policy and Planning* 25 (2010): 447–453.

⁵ M. S. Smolinski, Hamburg M. A., Lederberg J., *Microbial Threats to Health: Emergence, Detection, and Response*, Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Emerging Microbial Threats to Health in the 21st Century (Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2003), Available from: <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK221486/>>

The policy frameworks and institutional infrastructure to support such innovation however already exists in some African countries.

At the other end of the spectrum, scholars have also busied themselves with research on the COVID-19 pandemic. They organize webinars and make presentations of their research findings. Once published, their works fill their shelves forming part of the background display in their computer screens. During a webinar organized to discuss the trends in state responses to the pandemic, Professor Maria Nzomo lamented that there was a disconnect between academia and practice as the two sectors worked in silos. Citing the provisions of the Addis Ababa Declaration of 1973 and the Abuja Treaty of 1994, Nzomo⁶ argues that Africa had a strong institutional and policy framework to support mobilization of African response to issues of common interest. She posits that the political will to implement such initiatives is lacking, and that this does not auger well for Africa's integration initiatives under the AU. The scholar argues further that academics therefore have a responsibility to point the way forward.

When the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the COVID-19 a pandemic on 11th March 2020, immediate attention turned to Africa with initial prognosis sounding the death knell. So far, the responses are varied with some states complying to World Health Organisation (WHO) guidelines while others are only reluctantly observing aspects like wearing of protective masks for the sake of conformity. There is however scope for integrated effort as provided for in regional protocols and regimes. Sonya Sceats⁷ argues that the COVID-19 pandemic has elicited a growing sense of shared humanity and vulnerability, and the importance of collective action.

⁶ Maria Nzomo, Speech during conference, "Retreat to Nationalism in the 21st Century Globalization: Lessons for Africa from COVID-19," The Institute of Diplomacy and International Studies (IDIS), in partnership with the HORN International Institute for Strategic Studies, 16 July 2020.

⁷ Sonya Sceats, "COVID-19 Brings Human Rights into Focus," *Chatham House*. 9 April 2020), <<https://www.chathamhouse.org/2020/04/covid-19-brings-human-rights-focus>>

Ganatra⁸ enhances this argument, positing that it has thrust human health into the global security arena, bringing it to the forefront of International Relations discourse because it is a threat to global stability. HIV/AIDs and Ebola were classified as global pandemics, but did not cause the level of devastation that COVID-19 has.

1. Theoretical Framework

This study is analysed within the framework of the Neoliberal Institutionalism and African Renaissance Theories. This provides a framework of analysis with regard to the formal regional structures. The African Renaissance Theory applies strategies which galvanize collective action and communion among peoples with *Ubuntu*, *Harambee* both of which are different variations of collective effort – uplifting one another or looking out for each other and pulling together respectively. It is based on the African Socialism paradigm.

Liberalism seeks to explain circumstances on co-operation and collaboration among states and non-state actors. It assumes co-operation on issues of common interest like development and trade.⁹ This brings some level of peace among them. Keohane et al¹⁰ provide perspectives on this theoretical approach. Cox, writing with Keohane, situates the theory between the operation of system of states and the capitalist world economy. It provides insights into how the two interact. In explaining the said interaction further, Keohane differentiates co-operation and harmony. He argues that harmony is when interests of states coincide while co-operation is where they are not in agreement, but require negotiation for them to be in tandem. He borrows

⁸ Anbar Ganatra, Class Presentation on *Global Health Security*, University of Nairobi, Institute of Diplomacy and International Studies, 21st April 2020.

⁹ Paul Viotti and Mark V. Kauppi, *International Relations Theory. Liberalism: Interdependence and Global Governance* (Longman, 2012).

¹⁰ Robert O. Keohane, "Co-operation and International Regimes: Harmony, Co-operation and Discord," in *Classic Readings and Contemporary Debates in International Relations* ed. Phil Williams, Donald M. Goldstein, and Jay M. Shafritz (Thomson Wadsworth, 2006).

renowned management scholar Charles Lindblom's definition of such a process as 'policy co-ordination'. Robert Axelrod¹¹ analyses evolution of co-operation. He argues that there are no hard and fast rules as to what should be done by either party as the natural course of events determines the direction the co-operation relationship takes. He posits that the key factor in driving the process is reciprocity. Further relationship requires that the parties remember and acknowledge things which have been done for them in the past.

Tadadjeu et al¹² discuss the African Renaissance Theory. Highlighting the decadence witnessed in Africa in the 1970's and 1980's through Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAPs) to perpetual indebtedness in the 1990s onwards, the scholars visualize an opportunity to leverage the resources of both Africa and its diaspora population to champion its interests. According to them, African Renaissance was introduced as an alternative concept to the external theoretical models tried on Africa, which had failed to yield growth and development. Propounded by South Africa's former president, Thabo Mbeki, it is founded on political, economic, linguistic integration in a United States of Africa as envisaged by Libya's former president, Muammar Gaddafi. It would also apply Cheikh Anta Diop's contention of an African struggle integrating cultural aspects with political and scientific elements. It also builds on pan Africanist postulations of Kwame Nkrumah. He proposed an African history based on African experience rather than that of Western explorers.

¹¹ Robert Axelrod, "The Evolution of Co-operation," in *Classic Readings and Contemporary Debates in International Relations*, ed. Phil Williams, Donald M. Goldstein, and Jay M. Shafritz, 331 (Thomson Wadsworth, 2006).

¹² Johanna Menda'a Tadadjeu and Victorine Ghislaine Nzino Munongo, "African Renaissance in the United States of Africa: A Historical and Political Approach of a Pan Africanist Vision of Africa," *Journal of Pan African Studies*, 9 (2016): 34-51.

2. The Securitisation of Health

Wright¹³ argues that health is a critical aspect of state security. He posits that the current pandemic will be the greatest test for the said nations as it will impact on their national systems depending on their preparedness and also how they react to it. No matter what their response, they will all emerge greatly changed. Health and other systems are likely to clash due to strife. The liquidity of states will be tried with some resorting to stimulus packages. Others will be weighed down by escalating debt. An extended crisis will reveal the competence of states. It would be difficult for the said states to undertake extensive virus testing, keep up with requirements for surveillance and isolation while at the same time maintaining their industries and viable health systems. Voters who suffer all these shocks are not likely to remain sympathetic to political systems which cannot meet their expectations.

The World Health Organisation (WHO)¹⁴ co-ordinated concert for international celebrities during the COVID-19 pandemic. They came out to make statements in response to America's withdrawal of funding for COVID-19. Oprah Winfrey, an American show host, called upon black American communities to take heed and follow outlined precautions. She also participated in Lady Gaga's '*One World: Together at Home*' concert held on 18th April 2020 alongside famous singers Elton John, the Rolling Stones and others. The concert was hosted by the WHO and attended by the United Nations Secretary General. Ganatra,¹⁵ a member of Kenya's COVID-19 Rapid Response Team, discusses human agency in the securitisation of health. She

¹³ Thomas Wright, "Stretching the International Order to Its Breaking Point: The greatest error that geopolitical analysts can make may be believing that the crisis will be over in three to four month," *The Atlantic*, 4 April, 2020, <<https://www.theatlantic.com/ideas/archive/2020/04/pandemic-lasts-18-months-will-change-geopolitics-good/609445/>>

¹⁴ World Health Organisation, *One World: Together at Home Concert*, 2020, <www.globalcitizen.org/togetherathome>

¹⁵ Anbar Ganatra, Class Presentation on *Global Health Security*, University of Nairobi, Institute of Diplomacy and International Studies, 21st April 2020.

cites the example of Nelson Mandela's statement about HIV/AIDS which led to its securitisation in the year 2000. Mandela argued that HIV/AIDS was claiming more lives than the sum total of all wars, famines, floods and the diseases like malaria. If not checked, it would relegate development gains, threatening the very future of mankind. War had cause 200,000 deaths while HIV/AIDS had killed 2 million.

Dr. Ganatra argues that travel, improved communication and social media facilitate the securitisation of health. Other elements which define it are speech, acts, urgency and funding. HIV/AIDs and Ebola outbreaks both of which were declared as global health security issues by the United Nations Security Council, long before the outbreak of COVID-19, are evidence of global health security. HIV/AIDS was securitized because of its high prevalence among military officers and thus a threat to state security. Zika Virus also had security implications because it caused neonatal deformity to children. Ebola outbreak in West Africa threatened travel and trade. COVID-19 is a threat to world economies as it has put a stop to travel and trade. Dr. Ganatra cites the World Health Organisation's definition of threat to security. She emphasizes some of their features as proactive and reactive acute public health occurrences spanning geographical regions.¹⁶

3. Limitations of Donor Funding

Africa's response to the COVID-19 pandemic is mainly characterized by external funding. Both multilateral and bilateral engagement do not seem to auger well for Africa. Romero¹⁷ highlights Western multilateralism as the bane of African integration efforts. The scholar argues that in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, attention has been drawn to issues like poverty, nepotism, historical injustices, categorized as underlying issues in health

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ María José Romero, "Development Finance in Times of COVID-19: Time for a Rethink of the World Bank," *SLUG*. 29 May 2020, <<https://slettgjelda.no/nyheter/2020/development-finance-in-times-of-covid-19-time-for-a-rethink-at-the-world-bank>>

systems. Medical emergency preparedness of states, the roles and responsibilities of International Non-Governmental Organisations (INGO)s like the Bretton Woods institutions, the WHO and other organisations have also come under scrutiny. Despite the Bretton Woods institutions having accepted to reschedule debt repayment and, in some cases, provide additional financing to enable African and other Third World states to focus their resources and energy on fighting the pandemic, the pandemic shock has exposed the consequences of years of austerity policies and privatization measures which have ravaged social protection and health systems.

Kapata et al¹⁸ argue that the WHO created the World Health Emergencies Programme which is co-ordinating the response in liaison with the American funded Centres for Disease Control (CDC), and other externally funded health consortiums. The experience of HIV/AIDS and high death from the mid-1980's, and the outbreak of Ebola in West Africa between 2014 and 2016 and again in the Democratic Republic of Congo from 2018 to 2019 demonstrated the continent's lack of preparedness to manage such disasters. This is also bearing in mind that other diseases such as measles, malaria, dysentery, cholera and other communicable diseases, have stressed the already weak health systems in the respective countries.

4. Contradictions in the Actions of States

Decisions by government officials in Africa and beyond have raised questions of responsibility and integrity. According to Shimanyula¹⁹, a commercial flight from China with 239 passengers on board was allowed to land in Kenya on 28th February 2020, causing an uproar from Kenyans on

¹⁸ Nathan Kapata, et al, "Is Africa prepared for tackling the COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) epidemic. Lessons from past outbreaks, ongoing Pan-African public health efforts, and implications for the future," *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 93 (2020) 233–236.

¹⁹ Andrew Wasike Shimanyula, "Uproar as Chinese plane lands in Kenya with 239 onboard," *Anadolu Agency*. 28 February 2020, <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/africa/uproar-as-chinese-plane-lands-in-kenya-with-239-onboard/1747746>>

social media. Kapata et al²⁰ posit that, indeed, the WHO had by then declared the disease a pandemic, citing the fear of the spread to vulnerable African countries. This is because it was happening at a time when other countries were already restricting flights from China, the epicenter of the outbreak. Kenyans questioned the country's preparedness to deal with an outbreak hence the risk posed. It raised governance and ethical issues.

In South Africa, Transparency International²¹ raised the flag on the potential for corruption related to COVID-19 in public procurement, dispensation of development aid, whistleblowing and media freedom. Okech et al²² cite allegations of Chinese philanthropist Jack Ma's donation of test kits, masks and protective gear having been reported stolen at Jomo Kenyatta Airport in Kenya. In Burundi, the late President Pierre Nkurunziza's wife was admitted into an elite medical facility in Nairobi at a time when there was a flight ban. *Netizens* made resounding complaints about this.

According to the East African Community (EAC),²³ Rwanda convened a meeting of heads of EAC states on 12th May 2020. The ministers in charge of health and transport had met and deliberated on COVID-19 response strategy, but this was never actualized. The meeting resolutions on collective action to mitigate the impact of the pandemic were however not implemented. Ongoro²⁴ argues that the failure by the East African states to

²⁰ Kapata, et al, "Is Africa prepared for tackling the COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) epidemic. Lessons from past outbreaks, ongoing pan-African public health efforts, and implications for the future," 233–236.

²¹ Transparency International, "Four Anti-Corruption Priorities for Southern Africa During COVID-19," 13 May 2020, <<https://www.transparency.org/en/news/corruption-risks-in-africas-response-to-the-coronavirus#>>

²² Angela Okech and Brian Wasunna, "Scanty Information on Theft of Donated COVID-19 Equipment," *Daily Nation*, 20 June 2020, 6.

²³ EAC, "Heads of State Consultative Meeting of the East African Community Communique," Arusha, 12 May 2020, <<https://www.eac.int/communique/1725-communiqu%C3%A9-heads-of-state-consultative-meeting-of-the-east-african-community>>

²⁴ Brian Ongoro, "Drivers standoff turns EAC states relations on its head," *The East African*, 9 May 2020.

agree on a common approach to fight the COVID-19 pandemic was demonstrated when miles and miles of lorries piled up at the borders of the respective states. The stalemate was due to all states trying to limit the spread of the COVID-19 to their populations. They all had different suggestions for entry ignoring existing protocols. Adar²⁵ lists some of the institutions created to focus on health as The East African Integrated Disease Surveillance Network (EAIDSNET), and the EAC Partner States National Regulatory Authorities and Experts Committee on Pharmaceutical and Medical Products.

5. Postulations on Regional Integration

Langan²⁶ argues that Jean Monnet realized the importance of collective action when he witnessed devastation suffered in Europe from the Second World War. He applied regional integration to reinforce human security. He was recognized as the architect of European unity after the Second World War.²⁷ He later extended this principle of co-operation to the EU/African Caribbean and Pacific states development and trade initiative. Citing Manners, Mark Langan²⁸ argues that whereas Monnet's European supranational Project was intended to uphold ethical principles and well-being of states it interacted with through international trade, human rights and military policy, the opposite seems to have happened. He argues that the EU ought to replace 'normative power' with he refers to as 'moral

²⁵ Korwa Adar, "East African Community. First International Democracy Report 2011," Centre for Studies on Federalism, <http://www.internationaldemocracywatch.org/attachments/458_EAC-adar.pdf>

²⁶ Mark Langan, "Normative Power Europe and the Moral Economy of Africa–EU Ties: A Conceptual Reorientation of 'Normative Power'," *New Political Economy*, 17, 3 (2012): 243-270.

²⁷ Trygve Uglan, "'Designer' Europeanization: Lessons from Jean Monnet," *The European Legacy*, 14, 2 (2009): 149–161.

²⁸ Ian Manners, "Normative Power Europe: A Contradiction in Terms?" *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 40, 2 (2002): 235-258 in Mark Langan, "Normative Power Europe and the Moral Economy of Africa–EU Ties: A Conceptual Reorientation of 'Normative Power'."

economic perspective' to mitigate the negative impact their engagements have had.

6. The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic in Africa

The United Nations (UN)²⁹ discusses the popular prognosis for COVID-19, and the associated narrative that, Africa is likely to suffer the greatest impact of the outbreak, has persisted. The immediate effects in different states is varied. Though the casualties in terms of infections and deaths is lower than America, the EU and China, it is said to be too early to measure the real impact of the pandemic. Kapata et al³⁰ highlight a 2016 WHO report which suggests that Africa doesn't have the capacity to respond to an International Health Regulation hazard such as COVID-19. It found further that most health facilities in Sub-Saharan Africa were already operating at a maximum capacity. The impact of COVID-19 on Africa can however not be discussed in isolation from that of the rest of the world, particularly the Big Powers, America, the EU and China. This is due to the interconnectedness of the states through globalization.

Chen et al³¹ argue that the first cases of COVID-19 were reported in Wuhan, China. There are however, contestations between America and China over its origins and genesis. COVID-19 has so far had a more serious impact on America and Europe. Their health systems have been tried to the limit and their economies, in the case of Europe and America greatly impacted.

²⁹ United Nations, *Policy Brief: Impact of COVID-19 in Africa*, 20 May 2020, <<https://unsdg.un.org/sites/default/files/2020-05/Policy-brief-Impact-of-COVID-19-in-Africa.pdf>>

³⁰ Kapata, et al, "Is Africa prepared for tackling the COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) epidemic. Lessons from past outbreaks, ongoing Pan-African public health efforts, and implications for the future," 233–236.

³¹ Sophia Chen, Deniz Igan, Nicola Pierri, Andrea Presbitero, "The economic impact of Covid-19 in Europe and the US: Outbreaks and individual behaviour matter a great deal, non-pharmaceutical interventions matter less," 11 May 2020, *VOX. CEPR Policy Portal*, <<https://voxeu.org/article/economic-impact-covid-19-europe-and-us>>

Campbell³² posits that China has provided projections which in comparison to those of other countries are optimistic, but these are said to be just that – statistics. Its economy is said to have contracted by 6.8% in the first quarter of 2020 as compared to J. P. Morgan’s prediction of America’s as 40% for the second quarter of 2020. Further, in China, cases of loss of jobs and business closure with livelihoods taking a downturn present a different picture. Thomas Wright³³, a Senior Fellow at the Brookings Institution’s analysis of the impact of COVID-19 confirms this. He argues that its impact on public health, economics and geopolitics will be extensive, going beyond four to five months.

Africa CDC organized training for nationals from African countries early in the year. This included Nigeria, Egypt, Kenya, Uganda among others. Among the African countries, Nigeria was the forerunner with regard to response on the COVID-19 pandemic. They organized a multi-sectoral and nationwide effort on 7th January 2020 to combat the virus even before the first case was reported. Their initiative came exactly one week after China declared its first case. This was also before the WHO declared COVID-19 an issue the countries needed to take heed of. Nigeria also established diagnostic laboratories. Uganda quarantined more than 100 people while Zambia set aside two medical facilities with 800 bed capacity. Kenya and Zambia instituted mandatory screening at all points of entry into the countries. South Africa established rapid response teams to combat COVID-19 at national and provincial levels.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in the securitisation of global health to the level that no other pandemic occurring in the past has. The situation in

³² Charlie Campbell, “‘How Can I Get Through This?’ The Impact of Coronavirus on China’s Economy Is Only Just Beginning,” *Time Magazine*, April 21, 2020.

³³ Wright, “Stretching the International Order to Its Breaking Point: The greatest error that geopolitical analysts can make may be believing that the crisis will be over in three to four months.”

Africa is still difficult to predict although with minimal assistance from donors and philanthropists abroad, local innovation has risen to fill the gaps. There is no co-ordinated effort to tap on and grow the innovations despite various calls for self-reliance and promotion of intra-African trade. Failure to implement protocols at the borders has resulted in retaliation, bringing the issue of reciprocity in diplomatic relations to question. The assumption that when states have some semblance of trade relations, there will automatically be harmony among them does not hold true as evidenced by the stalemate on the East African and Zambian/Tanzania borders. African leaders are yet to wake up to the reality that a co-ordinated response is advantageous to their respective citizens.

Ironically, the citizens seem to display the will to work together as evidence by drivers at the East African borders acting in unison to abandon their lorries unless their terms are accepted. Common language and culture seem to be a point around which they coalesce. Even as the African Union (AU) and other donors provide assistance at national level, the philosophies of *Ubuntu* and *Harambee* also seem to be applied at the national borders. Each one of the states has been busy organizing its own response. Even strategies for protection and innovation are implemented in a disjointed manner at national level, to the exclusion of even their regular trading partners. Interestingly, the *Ubuntu* and *Harambee* spirit are exhibited through the initiatives from the international community in America and the rest of the world, providing support to WHO with the intention of having it cushion the vulnerable members of the global community, particularly Africa. Oprah Winfrey and others work together to support the efforts of the WHO following America's withdrawal.

The advantages that accrue from proximity are however not harnessed. The EU and the Organisation of African, Caribbean and Pacific States (OACPS) and especially the original EAC were viable models, elements of which have been replicated in other regional networks. Applying the regional networks would yield better results, especially bearing in mind the lack of co-

ordination among the East African states and the opportunity cost at the borders. Riding on regional initiatives like the EAC and other regional blocks, responses to global pandemics and other issues which affect the regions should be applied instead of the national responses which are cumbersome and expensive. Leaving some latitude for individual states to articulate some level of independence.

Jean Monnet and others left sound policy frameworks within a viable regional model, which they established with positive intentions having learnt lessons from the Second World War. These were lost somewhere along the way. The said policies are not being adhered to with negative results for the OACPS states. Scholars, with their superior understanding, are well placed to make the connections between the research innovations and practice. These are compelling enough reasons for them to engage in what Kenya's former Chief Justice, Willy Mutunga describes as 'activism' to ensure that their postulations are actualized. This gives them the responsibility of instituting creativity to nurture and implement innovations, hopefully yielding the industrialization which has eluded many African states.

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Contributors

Clément BIGIRIMANA est titulaire d'un Doctorat (PhD) en Sciences du Langage, option Langue et Linguistique Françaises. Il est enseignant-chercheur (Chargé de cours) à l'Université du Burundi, Faculté des Lettres et Sciences Humaines, mais aussi est actuellement Chef du Service de Promotion des Innovations et Vulgarisation des Résultats de la Recherche dans la même Université. Il est auteur de plusieurs articles et chapitres d'ouvrages collectifs publiés en Europe, aux États-Unis et en Afrique. Ses recherches concernent la sociolinguistique, l'analyse du discours, les politiques linguistiques et le contact des langues.

Elvis Mbembe BINDA (PhD) is Lecturer at the School of Law, University of Rwanda, where he has been teaching since 2007 business law related modules. His academic area of interest includes legal aspects of foreign direct investments in the context of regional integration with a focus on Chinese investments in the East African Community. He is also the founder and CEO of Initiatives for Peace and Human Rights (iPeace), an NGO that promotes human rights and good governance in the Great Lakes region.

Luis COLLADO-CUETO is senior professor of Applied Economics at the Department of Economic Structure and Development Economics at the Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM). His academic specialisation focuses on the analysis of economic development, in particular on issues related to rural development and sustainable development, and the EU policies in these areas. He is currently Head of the Economic Structure and Economic Development Department of the UAM. Since 2019, he is co-coordinator of the *Africa, Mediterranean and Europe* Jean Monnet Network (AMENET). In this framework, he is currently analysing the applicability of the EU's rural development models and policies to the reality of Africa.

Odilon KOUKOUBOU est Doctorant en Science politique, à l'Université de Parakou (Bénin). Ses recherches portent sur *Le G5 Sahel. Sociologie d'une action publique internationale de sécurité*. Assistant de recherche au Civic Academy for Africa's Future (CiAAF), il est auteur ou co-auteur d'articles

dont l'un, publié en juin 2020, porte sur les conséquences à court, moyen et long termes du Covid-19 sur le mouvement terroriste au Sahel.

Nicelate MATERERE is Advisor in the Department in charge of Education, Sports, Culture and Social Affairs at the Ministry to the Office of the President Responsible for East African Community Affairs in Burundi. He is also a Doctoral Student at the University of Burundi in Bujumbura.

Serge Magloire MBOUNGOU est économiste spécialiste des études internationales et européennes et de développement local et gestion des collectivités territoriales, diplômé de l'Université de Grenoble 2 et de l'université Ouagadougou 2. Enseignant chercheur, chargé des cours d'économie et de gestion à l'École Nationale Supérieure d'Agronomie et de Foresterie et à la faculté des Sciences économiques de l'Université Marien Nguouabi, ancien attaché économique au ministère de l'économie et des finances et du budget, au Congo de 2013 à 2016.

José MELLA is Emeritus Professor of Applied Economics at the Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM), Department of Economic Structure and Economic Development, and Principal Investigator of the AMENET *Jean Monnet* Network '*Africa, the Mediterranean and Europe in the Era of Global Integration*', co-funded by the Erasmus Programme of the European Union. He is an Associate member of the EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network. His academic specialisation focuses on the analysis of economic development of Africa, particularly of Sub-Saharan countries. He is coordinator of the Africa, Mediterranean, and Europe Jean Monnet Network (AMENET).

Leonidas NDAYISABA is co-editor of this special issue. He is Professor of Political Science and Director of the Research and Training Centre for Peace (CERFOPAX) at the University of Burundi, where is also the Burundi Representative of the EU-EAC Jean Monnet Network. He studied Law at the University of Burundi, and Sciences of Communication and Political Science at the University of Salzburg (Austria). He holds a PhD in political science

with a focus on International Politics, Conflict analysis and Peace, and Organisation Development. He has a long experience in teaching and research on topics related to security, conflict and peace, peace building, development, and communication in the African context. He has led numerous training activities in the Great Lakes region and across central Africa.

Lynette ODONDI is Lecturer at the Institute of Diplomacy and International Studies, University of Nairobi and Senior Researcher at the National Crime Research Centre, Nairobi (Kenya). Lynette is an associate member of EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network.

Helen TROUILLE (PhD), co-editor of this special issue, is a Senior Lecturer in Law at York St John University (UK). She has a research interest in international criminal law, access to justice and reconciliation in post conflict states, with a focus on East Africa. She has published in international criminal law journals on trials of Rwandan genocide suspects by the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda and by the French courts. She is an Associate Partner of the EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network, where she focuses on the benefits of the freedom of movement of legal services to regional integration, the economy and peace. She is also a Solicitor and Court interpreter.

Jean-Marc TROUILLE, editor-in-chief of this special issue, is Jean Monnet Professor in European Economic Integration at the University of Bradford, UK, and EU Commission Independent Ethics Expert on Horizon 2020 for the DG Research & Innovation. He is the Principal Investigator of the *Jean Monnet* Network '*The European Union, Africa and China in the Global Age*' (EU-EAC), co-funded by the Erasmus Programme of the European Union.

Penine UWIMBABAZI, PhD, is Professor of Policy Analysis and Conflict Transformation and Deputy Vice Chancellor for academics at the Protestant Institute of Arts and Social Sciences (PIASS) in Huye, Rwanda. She is the

representative of the EU-EAC *Jean Monnet* Network in Rwanda. Her research interests include social policies and development, rural-urban and regional migration and integration, as well as conflict transformation related issues.

Who's Who

Honorary Council

Co-Presidents:

Nico GROENENDIJK

Professor, Faculty of Behavioural, Management and Social Sciences, Twente University, Enschede, Netherlands

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Jean Monnet Professor

Ioan HORGA

Professor, Department of International Relations and European Studies,
University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Dean, Faculty of History, International Relations, Political and
Communication Sciences, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education,
Bucharest, Romania

President, Forum Oradea Foundation, Oradea, Romania

Director, Institute for Euroregional Studies, Oradea, Romania

Vice-President, ECSA Romania, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Helena TENDERA-WLASZCZUK

Professor, Cracow University of Economics, Cracow, Poland

Head, Department of European Economic Integration, Cracow University of
Economics, Cracow, Poland

Director, Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence, Cracow University of
Economics, Cracow, Poland

Expert, Erasmus+, European Union

Jean Monnet Professor

Members:

Francisco ALDECOA LUZARRAGA

Professor, Faculty of Political Science and Sociology, Complutense University
of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Co-Director, Jean Monnet Centre for Excellence "Antonio Truyol",
Complutense University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Director, Tiempo de Paz, Madrid, Spain

Jean Monnet Professor

Alexandru ARSENI

Professor, Faculty of Law, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova
Lawyer, Chisinau Bar, Chisinau, Moldova

Elchin BABAYEV

Professor, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan
Rector, Baku State University, Baku, Azerbaijan
Executive Director, Science Development Foundation under the President of
the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku, Azerbaijan

Enrique Lorenzo BANUS IRUSTA

Professor, School of Humanities, University of Piura, Piura, Peru
Dean, School of Humanities, University of Piura, Piura, Peru
Professor, University of Navarra, Pamplona, Spain
Jean Monnet Professor

Iordan Gheorghe BARBULESCU

Romanian Diplomat
Professor, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest,
Romania
Dean, Department of International Relations and European Integration,
National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania
President, Senate of the National School of Political and Administrative
Studies, Bucharest, Romania
Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education,
Bucharest, Romania
President, ECSA Romania, Bucharest, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Leonce BEKEMANS

Professor, University of Padova, Padova, Italy
President, ECSA Belgium, Brussels, Belgium
Secretary-General, ECSA World, Damme, Belgium
Jean Monnet Professor

Christophe BERTOSSI

Professor, Paris Institute of Political Studies, Paris, France
Senior Researcher, French Institute of International Relations, Paris, France
Director, Centre for Migration and Citizenship, French Institute of International Relations, Paris, France
Expert, Erasmus+, European Union
Jean Monnet Professor

Mircea BRIE

Professor, Faculty of History, International Relations, Political and Communication Sciences, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Editor-in-Chief, Annals of the University of Oradea, Series of International Relations and European Studies, Oradea, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Georges CONTOGEOORGIS

Professor, Panteion University, Athens, Greece
Coordinator, Master Programme in European Studies, Panteion University, Athens, Greece
Scientific Director, National Centre for Scientific Research, Paris, France
Member, European Political Science Association, Wicklow, Ireland
Jean Monnet Professor

Larisa DERIGLAZOVA

Professor, Faculty of History, Tomsk State University, Tomsk, Russia
Director, Centre for European Studies, Tomsk State University, Tomsk,
Russia

Expert, Erasmus+, European Union

Jean Monnet Professor

Ioan DERSIDAN

Professor, Faculty of Letters, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Council Member, Department of Romanian Language and Literature, Faculty
of Letters, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Gaga GABRICHIDZE

Professor, School of Law, New Vision University, Tbilisi, Georgia
Dean, School of Law, New Vision University, Tbilisi, Georgia
Board Member, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi,
Georgia

President, ECSA Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia

Professor Jean Monnet

Ihar HANCHARONAK

Professor, Department of Doctoral Studies, Graduate School of the National
Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Minsk, Belarus

Rector, Graduate School of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus,
Minsk, Belarus

Member, European Association for International Education, Amsterdam,
Netherlands

Wilfried HELLER

Professor Emeritus, Institute of Geography, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

Member, Research Centre for Germanic Connections with New Zealand and the Pacific, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

Asteris HULIARAS

Professor, Department of Political Science and International Relations, University of the Peloponnese, Corinth, Greece

Member, Hellenic Political Science Association, Athens, Greece

Jean Monnet Professor

Victor JUC

Professor, Institute for Legal and Political Research, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Deputy Director, Institute for Legal and Political Research, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Thomas KRUESSMANN

Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

Director, Russian, East European and Eurasian Studies Centre, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

Chair, Supervisory Board of Higher School of Jurisprudence, Higher School of Economics, Moscow, Russia

President, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi, Georgia

Jean Monnet Professor

Anatoliy KRUGLASHOV

Professor, Department of Political Science, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Head, Department of Political Science, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Director, Institute for European Integration and Regional Studies, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Jean Monnet Professor

Ariane LANDUYT

Professor, Faculty of Political Science, University of Siena, Siena, Italy

Jean Monnet Professor

Ewa LATOSZEK

Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Expert, H2020, Bruxelles, Belgium

President, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Vice-President, ECSA World, Damme, Belgium

Jean Monnet Professor

Ani MATEI

Professor, Faculty of Public Administration, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Secretary-General, National Commission of Romania for UNESCO, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Jose Maria MELLA MARQUEZ

Professor, Faculty of Economics and Business, Autonomous University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Jean Monnet Professor

Snezana PETROVA

Professor, Faculty of Philology “Blaze Koneski”, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, Macedonia

President, Association of French Language Teachers of Macedonia, Skopje, Macedonia

Oliver REISNER

Professor, Department for Central Asian Studies, Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany

Professor, School of Arts and Sciences, Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Board Member, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi, Georgia

Jean Monnet Professor

Maria Manuela TAVARES RIBEIRO

Professor, Faculty of Letters, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Director, PhD Programme in European Studies, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Corresponding Member, Academy of Sciences of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Member, ECSA Portugal, Lisbon, Portugal

Jean Monnet Professor

Grigore SILASI

Professor, Faculty of Economic Sciences, West University of Timisoara, Timisoara, Romania

Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Mihai SLEAHTITCHI

Professor, Institute of Education, Chisinau, Moldova

Scientific Coordinator, Institute of Education, Chisinau, Moldova

Tudorel TOADER

Professor, Faculty of Law, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iasi, Iasi, Romania

Honorary Member, Scientific Council of the Institute for Legal Research “Acad. Andrei Radulescu”, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania

Member, Scientific Council of the National Institute of Magistracy, Bucharest, Romania

Member, Romanian Association for Constitutional Law, Iasi, Romania

Member, International Association of Criminal Law, Paris, France

Member, Commission of Venice, Venice, Italy

Grigore VASILESCU

Professor, Faculty of International Relations, Political and Administrative Sciences, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Director, Centre for European Studies, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Scientific Committee

Co-Presidents:

Marta PACHOCKA

Associate Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Member, Polish Economic Society, Warsaw, Poland

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Jean Monnet Professor

Victoria RODRIGUEZ PRIETO

Lecturer, Department of International Relations, Nebrija University, Madrid, Spain

Member, Spanish Association of Teachers in International Law and International Relations, Madrid, Spain

Member, Madrid Press Association, Madrid, Spain

Vice-Presidents:

Diana EERMA

Associate Professor, School of Economics and Business Administration, University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia

Member, Estonian Economic Association, Tallinn, Estonia

Mihaela Narcisa NIEMCZIK-ARAMBASA

Researcher, Institute of Geography, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

Expert, Intercultural Counseling, Potsdam, Germany

Anna VISVIZI

Associate Professor, American College of Greece, Athens, Greece
Member, Academic Council, Institute of Diplomacy and Global Affairs,
American College of Greece, Athens, Greece
Director of Research, Institute for Central and Eastern Europe, Lublin,
Poland
Jean Monnet Professor

Members:

Paulo Emilio VAUTHIER BORGES DE MACEDO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de
Janeiro, Brazil
Vice-Coordinator, Master and Doctorate Programme in Law, Faculty of Law,
University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Editor-in-Chief, Cosmopolitan Law Journal, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Legal Adviser, Brazilian Naval School, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
President, Brazilian Section, Communio Journal, Washington, United States
of America

Paulo Jorge TAVARES CANELAS DE CASTRO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Macau, SAR Macau, China
Coordinator, Master Programme in European Union Law, International
Law and Comparative Law, Faculty of Law, University of Macau, SAR Macau,
China
Judge, Red Cross International Humanitarian Law Moot Court, Hong Kong,
SAR Hong Kong, China
Member, Association of European Law and Economics, Coimbra, Portugal
Member, Association of Auditors on National Defence, Lisbon, Portugal
Member, Association of International Law, London, United Kingdom
President, ECSA Macau, SAR Macau, China
Jean Monnet Professor

Georgeta CISLARU

Associate Professor, French Language Centre, New Sorbonne University, Paris, France

Member, Editorial Committee “Les Carnets du Cediscor”, SYLED-CEDISCOR, New Sorbonne University, Paris, France

Simion COSTEA

Associate Professor, Department of History and International Relations, “Petru Maior” University of Targu-Mures, Targu-Mures, Romania

Editor-in-Chief, L’Europe unie, Paris, France

Policy Officer, European Commission, Brussels, Belgium

Jean Monnet Professor

Klara CZIMRE

Associate Professor, Department of Social Geography and Regional Development Planning, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary

Dorin DOLGHI

Lecturer, Department of International Relations and European Studies, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Editor-in-Chief, Romanian Journal of Security Studies, Oradea, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Sanna ELFVING

Senior Lecturer, School of Law, University of Bradford, Bradford, United Kingdom

Programme Leader, LLM Programme, School of Law, University of Bradford, Bradford, United Kingdom

Associate Fellow, Higher Education Academy, York, United Kingdom

Member, United Kingdom Environmental Law Association, Dorking, United Kingdom

Member, Socio-Legal Studies Association, Birmingham, United Kingdom

Sedef EYLEMER

Associate Professor, Department of International Relations, Izmir Katip Celebi University, Izmir, Turkey

Jean Monnet Professor

Agnieszka KLOS

Associate Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Vice-President, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Eva KOVAROVA

Assistant Professor, Department of Public Economics, Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czechia

Aurelian LAVRIC

Associate Professor, "Alexandru cel Bun" Military Academy, Chisinau, Moldova

Senior Researcher, Centre for Defence and Security Strategic Studies, "Alexandru cel Bun" Military Academy, Chisinau, Moldova

Kerry LONGHURST

Associate Professor, European Research Institute, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, United Kingdom

Associate Professor, Department of International Relations and Sustainable Development, Collegium Civitas, Warsaw, Poland

Deputy Head, Department of International Relations and Sustainable Development, Collegium Civitas, Warsaw, Poland

Associate Professor, Department of European Interdisciplinary Studies, College of Europe, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Jose Luis DE SALES MARQUES

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